

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

Deliverable D2.1

Critical ChangeLab Cycle 2

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Executive Summary

This deliverable, *Critical ChangeLab Cycle 2*, presents the key efforts and activities of Work Package 2 (WP2) during Participatory Action Research (PAR) Cycle 2. WP2 focuses on the implementation of Critical ChangeLabs across 19 European locations, engaging local partners while ensuring adaptability to diverse learning environments. Building on the foundational work of WP1 (Map & Design), WP2 refines and iterates upon the Critical ChangeLab Framework and Process, originally developed through PAR Cycle 1. Additionally, WP2 supports the evaluation activities conducted in WP3 (Evaluate), which assesses and analyses the outcomes of the Critical ChangeLabs.

This deliverable details the process taken to prepare project partners for PAR Cycle 2, provides details on the implementation and facilitation of Critical ChangeLabs during this cycle, and summarizes learnings related to both implementation strategies and the engagement of partners in a Community of Practice (CoP). It does not provide a detailed analysis of the overall findings from PAR Cycle 2; this analysis will be presented in Deliverable 3.1 (Critical ChangeLab Process and Recommendations for Practice).

Key insights from PAR Cycle 2 highlight the need for continued refinement of implementation approaches for the upcoming PAR Cycle 3. The insights reveal that young people often perceive democracy as distant and inaccessible, with limited avenues for participation in decision-making. However, participatory research and creative methodologies have proven effective in fostering engagement, particularly when discussions are rooted in local issues and involve hands-on approaches.

Additionally, learnings emerged regarding the CoP, which serves as a support network for partners implementing Critical ChangeLabs. Enhancements to the CoP were made by creating participatory workshops based on partner needs, strengthening engagement and better facilitating knowledge exchange. These insights will inform the next PAR Cycle.

As the project progresses into PAR Cycle 3, these findings will guide refinements to methodologies, strengthen the Community of Practice, and ensure that the project continues to address the challenges and aspirations of young people across Europe. The iterative nature of the project highlights the importance of adaptability and co-creation, ensuring that each cycle builds upon previous learnings to enhance impact and sustainability.

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Glossary

Table 1 - Glossary of terms

Critical ChangeLab	Democracy meets arts: Critical change labs for building democratic culture through creative and narrative practices
CCLAB	Critical ChangeLab
CoP	Community of Practice
D	Deliverable
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
PAR	Participatory Action Research
PAR Cycle	Participatory Action Research Cycle
T	Task

1. Introduction

Critical ChangeLab is a project that brings together young people, educators, civic organizations, and key stakeholders to critically engage with democracy through Participatory Action Research (PAR). By fostering an inclusive and reflexive approach, Critical ChangeLab creates spaces where participants can explore democratic processes, co-create knowledge, and develop actionable insights to strengthen civic engagement. The project is grounded in the belief that meaningful participation in democracy requires not only theoretical understanding but also active experimentation and reflection. To this end, the project integrates research with practice, ensuring that participants contribute to both research and tangible democratic outputs.

As part of this research, partners of Critical ChangeLab have implemented ChangeLabs in both formal and non-formal educational settings during PAR Cycle 2, which took place between August 2024 and February 2025. PAR Cycle 2 is part of the implementation of three PAR Cycles, with the PAR Cycle 1 taking place October 2023 through March 2024 and PAR Cycle 3 taking place February through July 2025. The goal of the ChangeLabs is to create dynamic spaces where participants design and test democratic interventions, critically examined power structures, and identify opportunities for collective action. Through an iterative and participatory process, the ChangeLabs aimed to empower participants to take ownership of democratic engagement and develop solutions tailored to their respective contexts. This document provides an overview of the methodologies, processes, and key learnings from this cycle of implementation.

Chapter 1 introduces the document as well as the scope.

Chapter 2 details the process of creating and implementing a Community of Practice. In addition, it focuses on the actions taken to engage PAR Cycle partners, plan for the Critical ChangeLabs, and implement and monitor the ChangeLabs.

Chapter 3 presents narrative accounts of each partner's Critical ChangeLabs. Each section follows a similar format, including a description of the ChangeLab, documentation of activities conducted and their alignment with the Critical

ChangeLab process, reflections on impact and key learnings, and data on Key Performance Indicators. While most partners adhere to this structure, Tactical Tech worked with external partners to implement multiple ChangeLabs. As such, their section includes details on the external partner onboarding process, an overview of each external partner's ChangeLab, and corresponding Key Performance Indicators.

Chapter 4 summarizes the key learnings from PAR Cycle 2, offering a high-level analysis of the insights gained by partners in implementing ChangeLabs. Additionally, this chapter examines best practices and challenges encountered in facilitating a Community of Practice, drawing from the collective experiences of the participants.

Chapter 5 concludes the deliverable by framing the findings and reflecting on the broader implications of PAR Cycle 2. This chapter also outlines ambitions for PAR Cycle 3, which will be an iteration of PAR based on the efforts of PAR Cycle 2.

The deliverable also includes Annex 1, which contains the PAR Cycle plans created by each partner. These plans served as foundational documents to assist partners in the planning and implementation of the Critical ChangeLabs; the plans, however, were intended to be flexible and adaptable. The plans detail partner information, the proposed activities, objectives, outcomes of the Critical Change Labs, as well as obstacles and risk mitigation efforts. Annex 2 contains the workshop outline provided by Tactical Tech to external partners.

1.1 Scope

This deliverable covers the results of the efforts of PAR Cycle partners and tasks related to their Critical ChangeLabs during PAR Cycle 2. This document details the process of setting up the Critical ChangeLabs, provides a narrative summary of each Critical ChangeLab, and reflects at a high-level on key learnings related to the Critical ChangeLabs and execution of the Community of Practice.

This deliverable is not intended to provide detailed analysis on each Critical ChangeLab, nor a cumulative analysis of the ChangeLabs. This analysis will be detailed in Deliverable 3.1 (Critical ChangeLab Process and Recommendations for Practice). D2.1 and D3.1 will serve as complimentary deliverables – one providing a

narrative picture of the labs and their efforts, the other delving into analysis and key insights on implementing the labs overall.

2. Process

2.1 Establishment of the Community of Practice

To kick off PAR Cycle 2, a Community of Practice (CoP) was established. A CoP is commonly considered to be a group of people with a shared interest who regularly collaborate to exchange knowledge, learn together, and improve their practice. In the case of Critical ChangeLab, the CoP brought together the partners of the project focused on implementing and facilitating the labs. The CoP was also open to external stakeholders as well as left space for presentations and conversations with external presenters, should the CoP find this valuable.

Waag Futurelab, lead of WP2 and Task 2.1 (Building a Community of Practice) created a proposal for the structure of the CoP. This proposal was shared with the consortium to gather feedback and ensure that the CoP met the needs of all partners. After incorporating the feedback, the CoP was launched in May 2024. The CoP serves as a dynamic, collaborative space to guide and support the implementation of the Critical ChangeLab Framework through labs conducted by PAR cycle partners. The CoP fosters continuous learning, knowledge exchange, and critical reflection among partners, creating a structured yet flexible environment to address challenges, share successes, and drive impactful change. The CoP target audience and key stakeholders are the partners implementing the PAR cycles.

The CoP was designed to promote critical reflection and a growth mindset, maintain an open learning environment that encourages active participation and mutual support, minimize barriers by using a streamlined, tool-light approach, and adapt flexibly to the unique needs and challenges of PAR cycle partners. By embedding knowledge exchange and collaborative engagement at its core, the CoP ensures that all activities contribute to the overarching mission of driving sustainable, transformative change through the Critical ChangeLab project. The CoP was not only built to encourage knowledge exchange and reflection but was constructed with a view to ensure sustainability of practices beyond the project; this also includes reflection on the way we engage with stakeholders running the labs to ensure that the legacy of the project continues after its conclusion.

The CoP was also designed co-creatively with partners, to ensure that all partners have a voice in the process. In addition, the CoP is open to ideas, workshops, initiatives, or topics suggested or led by partners. The aim is not that the WP2 lead dictates the form and content of the CoP, but that it is shaped and re-shaped by partners based on their pressing needs.

Throughout PAR Cycle 2 and Par Cycle 3, the work of the CoP will help define and operationalize the local Critical ChangeLabs' roadmap using the Critical ChangeLab Framework, support and monitor the implementation progress of the labs and facilitate knowledge sharing to enhance collaborative outcomes and support formative evaluations of PAR Cycles 2 and 3 to refine and optimize processes. The CoP is built around three main activities, ensuring a clear and adaptable design:

- 1) Live Meetings:** Three in-person or live, longform virtual meetings will provide critical touchpoints for collaborative exchange.
 - Meeting 1: Prior to PAR Cycle 2 - Identifying challenges, opportunities, and creating PAR Cycle Plans
 - Meeting 2: Between PAR Cycles 2 and 3 - Refining approaches, sharing progress, and planning for PAR Cycle 3
 - Meeting 3: After PAR Cycle 3 - Reflecting on the legacy and outputs of the PAR cycles
- 2) Bi-weekly PAR Cycle Partner Meetings:** Regular online sessions, occurring every other week, ensure a supportive space for partners to exchange knowledge and experiences, learn about topics relevant to Critical ChangeLab, share project updates, successes, and challenges, and engage with a wide range of engaging content sourced from the consortium.
- 3) Online Communication and Documentation:** A shared Miro board acts as a collaborative platform to plan and document PAR cycle progress, facilitate communication and feedback among partners, highlight shared challenges and opportunities for growth, and provide visibility to stakeholders and allow tagging for specific insights.

Figure 1 – A section of the Miro board used by CoP to track updates and collaborate

The CoP aims to translate democratic ways of doing into ways of operating; it also serves as a space to make decisions between partners. In this way, it brings together the ‘ways of doing’ of the partners and the activities taken together with youth. Furthermore, the CoP will explore how its learnings – including the opportunities and challenges of implementing and facilitating labs – can be used to inform key project outputs such as the MOOC and the CCL Educator’s Handbook.

2.1.1 Community of Practice Kick Off Workshop – Paris Consortium

During the consortium meeting in Paris, participants gathered to collaborate and exchange ideas. Leading up to the event, each partner had been asked to submit the top three topics they believed would be most valuable for discussion during a workshop. These submissions were then reviewed and grouped into broader themes by Waag, ensuring the workshop would focus on the most relevant and pressing issues.

The session kicked off with a brief Introduction and topic determination phase. The grouped topics were presented to the participants, and they were encouraged to share any additional concerns or ideas that might have been overlooked. Through a live poll on Slido, attendees ranked the topics by urgency and importance. After gathering everyone’s input, the top five discussion topics were selected.

Next, participants split into smaller discussion groups for a 40-minute session. Each group was led by a moderator, who was given a set of guiding questions to get the conversation started. Attendees were free to choose which group they wanted to join based on their interests or expertise. Halfway through the session, an announcement was made to give participants the option to switch groups if they wished. This added flexibility allowed people to explore multiple topics or dive deeper into their initial choice.

As the group discussions ended, it was time for the wrap up. Each group gave a summary of their key takeaways, highlighting the most important insights and points of agreement (or disagreement). To conclude the session on a collaborative note, participants were asked to write down the names of two people they would like to contact in the coming month to continue the conversation. This exercise was designed to encourage further ongoing dialogue beyond the workshop.

2.2 PAR Cycle 2 Planning Workshops

Task 2.1 (PAR Cycle 2: implementation of the first iteration of the Critical ChangeLabs), led by WP2 leader Waag, involves the first iteration of Critical ChangeLab. To ensure plans for PAR Cycle 2 were well developed and aligned with the goals of the project, a series of online workshops brought together the PAR cycle partners to refine and iterate on their PAR Cycle plans in May 2024. This workshop was the first live meeting of the Community of Practice, the first key activity of the CoP. The workshops were designed to promote feedback, reflection, and collaboration, helping each partner develop a roadmap for the execution of their PAR cycle.

Session 1: Foundations of PAR Cycle Plans

The first session focused on developing foundational elements for PAR Cycle plans. It was structured in two rounds - Round 1 for brainstorming and development, and Round 2 for feedback.

In Round 1, participants split into six groups to address key questions:

WHY: What are the primary goals of the PAR cycle?

HOW: How will it achieve these goals?

WHAT: What will the participant experience be?

WHERE: How does it connect to the CCL literacies framework?

After 35 minutes of collaboration on Zoom and Miro, Round 2 involved rotating breakout rooms to share insights and refine plans through peer feedback. The session ended with key takeaways, including the need for clearer success metrics and actionable strategies.

Session 2: Refining PAR Cycle Plans and Roadmap Planning

This session focused on refining plans and developing actionable roadmaps. Participants regrouped to reflect on the first session, identify knowledge gaps, and address logistical aspects. A central discussion point was: What additional research is needed for success? Teams then shared refined plans, highlighting key insights, areas needing input, and feedback that helped improve their approach.

2.3 PAR Cycle 2 Planning

Planning for PAR Cycle 2 was directly informed by the knowledge and feedback gathered during the in-person workshop in Paris and the two subsequent online workshops. Drawing from these exchanges, each PAR partner completed a planning template developed by the WP2 lead. This template asked partners to articulate their plans for PAR Cycle 2, including details on key stakeholders, target groups, intended outcomes, planned activities, and potential risks with corresponding mitigation strategies. WP2 leads reviewed the plans, offering feedback and guidance so partners could enrich their plans. While not intended to be fixed blueprints, these plans served as guiding frameworks for each partner's implementation of the PAR Cycle. They are documented in Annex 2. As a next step, each partner presented their PAR Cycle plan during the bi-weekly CoP calls. These presentations not only allowed the community to become familiar with one another's approaches but also served as a space for inspiration and feedback. Partners shared ideas, posed questions, and suggested refinements to one another,

Crucially, the design of PAR Cycle 2 plans reflected key learnings from PAR Cycle 1. Rather than treating the cycles as isolated phases, iteration was emphasized – adapting and improving the model as it progressed. One of the most persistent challenges in PAR Cycle 1 was the tension between the participatory aims of the labs and the hierarchical, time-bound nature of formal education settings. In

response, PAR 2 introduced a clearer articulation of learning objectives, led by WP3, particularly regarding competencies. This shift was both conceptual and practical: clearer objectives helped facilitators and participants navigate the balance between structure and openness. Materials developed by WP3 lead University of Barcelona played a central role, offering concrete frameworks to align activities with desired outcomes while remaining adaptable to evolving participants needs.

Another major learning from PAR Cycle 1 concerned the friction between participatory methods and institutional norms. In PAR Cycle 2, greater flexibility was introduced – particularly in non-formal learning environments – by loosening structural expectations. This allowed facilitators to cultivate the open-ended, creative atmosphere necessary for deeper engagement. By acknowledging the diverse contexts in which CCLabs operate, these adjustments helped reduce institutional barriers and enhanced students’ sense of agency.

Finally, the relatively underdeveloped participatory research component in PAR Cycle 1 prompted a renewed focus in PAR Cycle 2. While the hands-on, creative activities supported engagement, the dimension of youth-led inquiry remained limited. PAR Cycle 2 responded by placing stronger emphasis on student-driven research processes. Youth were encouraged to formulate questions, gather and interpret data, and contribute to knowledge construction – moving from passive participation to active co-research. This deepened the participatory ethos of the model and brought it into closer alignment with its democratic aims.

2.4 Key Performance Indicators

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were also established to ensure that the target number of students, educators, and organisations were met. These KPIs were tracked via a spreadsheet on SharePoint. Individual KPIs per partner can be found in chapter 2; cumulative KPIs for PAR Cycle 2 are listed below:

Table 2 – Cumulative KPIs across labs

	KPI Target	Actuals
Participants in PAR cycle	400	1086
Educators	130	146
Number of Civil Society Organisations	15	30

3. PAR Cycle 2 Critical ChangeLabs

This chapter provides narrative descriptions of each partner's Critical ChangeLab facilitated during PAR Cycle 2. Some partners (Trinity College Dublin, Ars Electronica, University of Oulu, Institute for Social Research, and University of Barcelona) conducted multiple labs to ensure that they engaged their targeted number of students and educators. Each partner report, apart from Tactical Tech, includes a summary of the lab's activities and how they align with the Critical ChangeLab Process, impact and key learnings, and KPIs. Tactical Tech's summary is slightly different as they coordinated the efforts of nine external labs. One key difference between Tactical Tech and the other partners is that, in the other partners labs, a researcher was always present to take notes; this made their data collection and observation robust. In the case of Tactical Tech, the external labs do not include researchers within the labs but aim mainly to expand impact and observe the feasibility of the labs in different contexts.

The Critical ChangeLab Process (detailed in D1.4) is supported by the Critical ChangeLab Framework, depicted below.

Figure 2- The Critical ChangeLab Framework

The Critical ChangeLab Process consists of five phases, which can be abbreviated into three phases. In this deliverable, partners have reflected on how their activities and methods align with the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Long version	Short version
P0: OnBoard	P0: OnBoard
P1: Question	P1: Question and Analyse
P2: Analyse	
P3: Envision and Examine	P2: Envision and Act
P4: Act	
P5: Reflect	P3: Reflect

Figure 3 - The Critical ChangeLab Process

The framework and process of Critical ChangeLab was applied to a diverse set of contexts. Through the labs, the Framework and Process were tested in multiple countries, with a wide range of youth. This diversity can be seen in the local environment (engaging youth in both urban and rural context), youth that were both 'local' and 'migrant', and youth of different ages and gender identities. The aim was to test methods across a wide range of youth and local contexts to ensure that the framework, processes, and methods, can be applied and adjusted to a large range of contexts.

Reflecting on the gender identities of participants, the participation of those identifying as male and female was quite balanced overall. Some labs, however, displayed gender imbalances. The lab facilitated by Kersnikova saw a greater number of male participants, while the Institute for Social Research conducted sessions in two all-female dormitories. These variations shaped the dynamics within each lab and at times influenced which topics were surfaced and explored. Gender itself emerged as a point of discussion – particularly in conversations about democracy, where gender equality was proposed by youth as a pressing theme warranting further inquiry.

In PAR Cycle 2, gender emerged not only as a standalone theme but also as an underlying current in broader conversations about equity, care, and responsibility. In the lab conducted by European Alternatives in French Guinea, gender roles were brought into focus even though the lab's central theme revolved around food and democracy. In several other labs, gender was not only discussed but chosen as a primary topic. At the Institute for Social Research's UDNZ lab, for example, students selected gender inequality in education as their focus. Through structured role-playing and reflective exercises, participants explored how gendered expectations influence academic experiences and long-term opportunities. Facilitators observed a shift: while students initially understood inequality in individual terms, they gradually came to see the larger systemic patterns at play.

This shift toward structural thinking was echoed in multiple labs. At HTL Spengergasse, participants drew connections between gender and other forms of marginalisation, including ability and experiences of domestic violence. Their discussions moved toward a critique of systemic issues that shape vulnerability and access. Similarly, at BAU, students initially surfaced themes such as sexism,

emotional labour, misinformation, and climate change. Through a deliberative democratic process, they selected affective responsibility as the central lab topic – a choice that reflected a deepening understanding of the gendered dynamics embedded in emotional awareness and social responsibility. At UDMJ, gender surfaced among the top three themes positioned for the lab; while participants chose equity in access to enrolment as the primary focus, varying socioeconomic elements emerged in discussion. Meanwhile, Teyit’s participants, one of Tactical Tech’s external labs, approached the topic through advocacy, designing projects that highlighted gender inequality and explored strategies for change within their communities. These examples show how, across labs and contexts, participants repeatedly returned to gender – not always as an explicit theme, but as a critical thread running through many aspects of public life.

The diversity of youth involved in each lab, containing some detail on gender, can be seen in the below overview; the following chapter includes detail on each lab.

Table 3 – Overview of PAR Cycle 2 labs

Partner	Lab	Location	No. of Sessions	Topic	Participant Demographics
Trinity College Dublin	CrossCare	Arklow, Wicklow, Ireland	7	Climate Action, focused on local river	15 youths, 3 male and 12 female, aged 14–18
Trinity College Dublin	Design Your Future City	Dublin, Ireland	5	Future of Dublin with focus on sustainability	18 participants, all aged 15–16, mix of male and female
University of Oulu	Growing up with social media: Kastelli school	Oulu, Finland	8	Online wellbeing and digital empathy	43 participants, 7th graders, 12–14 years. Group A: 25 students (10 girls, 15 boys). Group B: 18 students (10 boys, 8 girls)

University of Oulu	Growing up with social media: Norssi school	Oulu, Finland	7	UNESCO-aligned social themes in social media	21 participants. 7th graders, 12–14 years, 11 boys, 10 girls, diverse backgrounds
European Alternatives	Saint-Laurent-du-Maroni	French Guiana	2	Food, fishing, and environmental access	Participants aged 11–14
European Alternatives	Lycée Michel-Ange	Villeneuve La Garenne, France	2	Artificial intelligence and social media	17-year-old students, school level premiere
European Alternatives	Palermo (Exploratory Lab)	Palermo, Italy	2	Human-animal relations and ecology	Children aged 3–11 from disadvantaged backgrounds
LATRA	Loutra Elementary School	Lesvos, Greece	12	Democracy, inclusion, and community via theatre	11-year-old school children and refugee children
Institute for Social Research	UDDP	Zagreb, Croatia	7	Youth mental health and educational inequality	High school girls aged 15–18 in a student dorm
Institute for Social Research	UDNZ	Zagreb, Croatia	8	Stigma and invisibility of dormitory students	14 students aged 15–18 from rural areas, mixed gender
Institute for Social Research	UDMJ	Zagreb, Croatia	8	Inequality in secondary school enrolment	15 girls aged 17–19, from various towns, in dorm

Ars Electronica	Open Lab - create your world	Linz, Austria	6	Imagining futures, social tech impact and mental health	12 youth aged 14-18, diverse backgrounds
Ars Electronica	HTL Spengergasse	Vienna, Austria	5	Human rights, discrimination, and climate change	29 students aged 17-18, diverse backgrounds
Kersnikova	Center Rog	Ljubljana, Slovenia	8	STEAM, digital governance, civic engagement	10 youth aged 11-15, mostly boys
Waag Futurelab	Corderius College	Amersfoort, Netherlands	3	Identity, relations, and racism	100 students aged 15-17, VMBO level, diverse backgrounds
University of Barcelona	BAU	Barcelona, Spain	7	Lack of affective responsibility in society	26 design students aged 17-18, 22 girls and 4 boys
University of Barcelona	Vapor Moli	Barcelona, Spain	7	Seven youth-defined topics incl. racism, safety, rent	25 students aged 15, mix of genders and backgrounds
University of Barcelona	CAN FABRA	Barcelona, Spain	9	Lack of care toward others (humans and non-humans)	9 participants aged 12-14 in a maker space

3.1 Trinity College Dublin (Ireland)

Trinity College Dublin (TCD) completed two labs during PAR Cycle 2 - one with the organisation CrossCare and another with Academy of the Near Future. Reports on both labs are described below.

3.1.1 CrossCare

Table 4 - Details of CrossCare lab

Geographical location	Arklow, Wicklow, Ireland
Demographic characteristics of participants	Approximately 15 youths. Approximately 3 male, 12 female. Aged between 14-18 years old.
Number of sessions	7
What is the topic of the cycle?	The general theme for the cycle was Climate Action. Ultimately, this theme was narrowed to focus on the local river.

TCD, in collaboration with CrossCare Ireland, a prominent provider of youth services within the Archdiocese of Dublin, led a lab which sought to empower youth in making a tangible impact on their environment. This lab took place in Arklow, Wicklow. Here, a group of young people from the Monday Mixers and the LGBTQI+ afterschool youth groups worked together to explore, understand, and act on climate issues.

The lab consisted of seven sessions; the theme of climate action was decided in collaboration with the educator. This was informed by the educator’s experience with the young people and projects they had completed previously. While it was TCD’s understanding that the topic could focus on any aspect of climate action it became evident during time with the group that the educator’s interest was in the local river and, while youth were also interested in this, other interests in the area of climate action were disregarded in favour of this.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

The CCLAB began with an open call to youth groups, inviting them to participate in a programme focused on climate action. The group, consisting of approximately fifteen young people aged 14-18, gathered at The Vault, a community space in Arklow. Many arrived with a curiosity about environmental issues but without a clear sense of how they could contribute to meaningful change.

The initial sessions were structured to build engagement and critical thinking. Through methods like *Walking Debate*, participants actively discussed democracy, climate action, and personal agency. The debates revealed differences in perspective but also highlighted a shared concern for the environment. Another early exercise, *Mapping*, encouraged participants to outline their knowledge, interests, and the challenges they faced in taking climate action.

Figure 4 - Values Tree activity during CrossCare lab

As the sessions progressed, the group's focus gravitated towards their local waterway - the Avoca River. A key moment came during a *River Walk*, where Justin from LAWPRO (Local Authorities Water Programme) guided the youth through an exploration of the river's ecosystem, discussing conservation efforts and the historical significance of the area. Some participants, initially disengaged, found

themselves drawn in as they saw first-hand the impact of pollution and habitat destruction. During the walk, a spontaneous discussion emerged about a barren concrete area near CrossCare's offices. What started as a casual observation evolved into a brainstorming session on creating a 'pocket forest'—a small, densely planted green space that could enhance biodiversity. This marked a turning point where the youth began to see themselves as active participants in shaping their environment.

Despite moments of inspiration, a recurring tension surfaced regarding agency. While the programme aimed to be youth-led, many participants hesitated to take ownership of initiatives. Discussions about the upcoming Youth Assembly on Climate Action revealed an imbalance – youth had expressed interest in addressing both sustainable lifestyles and water conservation, yet the final agenda focused exclusively on the latter, largely determined by adult facilitators. Another tension became apparent though creative exercises like the *Group Collage* session, where the aim was to envision alternative futures for the Avoca River. Instead of exploring radical possibilities, many participants remained grounded in present realities, hesitating to suggest changes that felt too distant or ambitious. The hesitation reflected a broader challenge: the struggle to move beyond existing frameworks and propose innovative solutions.

Figure 5 - Group Collage Envisioning the Future of the River during CrossCare lab

In the final phase, the youth engaged in creative activism through *Meme-making*. While some struggled with the medium, others demonstrated a sharp, critical awareness of systemic climate issues. One participant cleverly used the ‘Kid Named Finger’ meme to highlight how responsibility for climate action is often deflected onto younger generations. Another participant initially hesitated to share a meme criticizing their school council’s inaction but ultimately decided to post it, taking a small but significant step in civic engagement.

As the lab concluded, reflections from participants and educators highlighted both achievements and areas for growth. Youth appreciated the hands-on, local focus of the lab, which made climate action feel tangible rather than abstract. However, the challenges of fostering youth agency remained evident. Many felt enthusiastic about acting but lacked confidence in their ability to lead initiatives and related work independently.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process:

Table 5 – Methods used during CrossCare lab

Process Step	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Walking Debate	Participants physically position themselves between "agree" and "disagree" sides of the room in response to statements about democracy and climate change, creating a visual map of opinions.
Question	Glossary	This exercise pairs participants to define and discuss key climate-related vocabulary, creating a collaborative glossary that ensures shared understanding of terminology while identifying and clarifying knowledge gaps.
Question	Mapping	This activity maps participants' climate action insights across four areas (knowledge, challenges, interests, and experience), using sticky notes to collect individual responses before group discussion.
Question	Values Tree	This exercise combines rapid ideation and small group voting to help participants identify and prioritize shared group values, culminating in a visual representation of the most important collective values for guiding decisions.
Question	River Walk + Talk	A guided river walk led by a water conservation expert combines classroom learning with outdoor exploration, demonstrating local biodiversity and specific community actions for protecting waterways.
Analyse	Historical Roleplay	A historical roleplay simulation that transforms participants into characters through physical embodiment exercises and guided scenarios, allowing them to explore complex social issues through interactions and debates.
Envision	Group Work - Imagining Futures	A guided reflection exercise where small groups explore their river's future through structured prompts about improvements, challenges, and local significance, sharing insights via post-its for broader group discussion.
Envision	Group Collage	A collaborative art activity where participants collectively visualize their river's future by drawing, collaging, and building upon each other's contributions on shared canvas.
Act	Meme Making	Students formed small groups to discuss local climate change issues, created memes, and uploaded them to Padlet for potential inclusion in a social media video aimed at politicians.

Impact and Key Learnings

The lab helped to increase youth awareness and critical thinking about climate action, creating a deeper connection to their local environment. Participants realized that environmental issues feel more urgent when they are directly visible in their daily lives. Many were eager to stay engaged through projects like river health monitoring, community clean-ups, and policy advocacy, though institutional constraints and time limitations posed challenges. Educators and facilitators recognized the need for mentorship, resources, and formal integration into community planning to sustain youth-led initiatives.

Hands-on, interactive learning methods - such as the *River Walk*, *Historical Roleplay*, and *Meme-making* - were particularly effective in fostering engagement. However, some activities, like the *Collage Session*, lacked clear guidance, making it harder for participants to engage in visionary thinking. Another challenge was ensuring equal participation, as more outspoken individuals often dominated discussions while quieter participants hesitated to contribute. Structured turn-taking, written reflections, and smaller group discussions could help create a more inclusive environment.

2.1.2 Design Your Future City

Table 6 - Details of Design Your Future lab

Geographical location	Dublin, Ireland
Demographic characteristics of participants	18 participants in total. 9 male, 9 female. All aged 15-16 years old. 17 participants living in Dublin city/county, one participant from Meath (county adjacent to Dublin). All in Transition Year of school.
Number of sessions	5
What is the topic of the cycle? How was it defined?	The overall topic was the future of Dublin, which is the focus of the 'Design Your Future City' programme, with a focus on sustainability as it was Trinity Climate Action and Biodiversity Week.

Youth gathered in Dublin for a week-long lab titled *Design Your Future City*. Hosted by the Academy of the Near Future in collaboration with TCD and multiple stakeholders, the lab sought to empower young people to reimagine their city with sustainability, innovation, and inclusivity at its core. The eighteen participants came from diverse backgrounds but shared the goal to shape a city that reflects their aspirations. Over five days, they engaged in hands-on learning, critical discussions, and creative exercises that challenged their perceptions of urban life, sustainability, and democratic engagement.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

The first day began with *Icebreakers*, which helped build a sense of community as students introduced each other and shared their hopes and worries for the lab. Through *Speculative Design*, they imagined living on different planets, challenging themselves to think beyond traditional urban constraints. This activity laid the groundwork for understanding how space, resources, and community needs shape urban environments.

The *Active Travel Mapping Exercise* invited students to examine their local environments, pinpointing areas where infrastructure hindered pedestrian and cycling mobility. Through discussions and creative mapping, they identified challenges – poor bike lanes, unsafe crossings, and limited green spaces. The exercise triggered a realization: reimagining the city wasn't just about large-scale futuristic ideas but also about practical, small-scale interventions that could have a significant impact.

Midweek, the participants went on a *Biodiversity Walk* through Trinity College Dublin, guided by sustainability experts. They explored the ecological significance of urban green spaces, considering how nature could be integrated into the city's landscape and considered some of the challenges facing Dublin city specifically in the face of climate change.

The *AI Workshop* was particularly eye-opening. Students engaged in hands-on activities, sculpting physical representations of AI and discussing the ethics of technology in shaping public spaces. One group crafted an AI "eye" that symbolized both the potential for surveillance and the possibility of enhancing civic

engagement. The discussions that followed challenged them to think critically about the role of technology in democracy and personal agency.

Figure 6 - A (Eye) - a model of AI in clay during the lab

A turning point occurred during the ethics *Walking Debate*. As facilitators presented statements about urban development, students positioned themselves along a spectrum of agreement and disagreement, justifying their perspectives. For many, this was their first experience engaging in structured debate about civic responsibility, economic constraints, and the balance between progress and preservation. Some even found their opinions shifting mid-discussion.

With insights from the week's previous activities, the students transitioned to prototyping solutions. The *Idea Generation* workshop introduced methodologies like the '5 Whys' and 'Break It Before You Make It' - techniques that allowed them to deconstruct urban issues before proposing solutions. Each team selected a pressing problem: traffic congestion, digital inclusivity, sustainable housing, and public space accessibility. In a culminating exercise, participants created prototypes of their ideas using simple materials. They envisioned smart pedestrian crossings powered by renewable energy, interactive green spaces that doubled as

educational hubs, and AI-driven public transit systems. The prototyping stage was not just about creativity but also about feasibility - each team had to justify the economic and social viability of their solution.

Friday involved the activity of *Pitching*. Each team presented their project to a panel of judges from Dublin City Council, Smart Dublin, Trinity’s Sustainability Office, and the School of Education (TCD). The feedback was both encouraging and challenging, pushing students to refine their ideas. One standout moment came when a group working on traffic solutions was invited to a city council meeting to further discuss their concept.

Throughout the week students engaged in *Zine Making*, capturing their learnings, frustrations, and hopes for the future. At the end of the lab many felt more confident in their ability to ideate and propose solutions related to systemic issues themselves, and reflected on how individuals and communities have implemented change in their areas supported, rather than led, by their local authorities.

Figure 7 - Participants using the Mirror Board to reflect on their learning

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 7 – Methods used during Design Your Future lab

Process Step	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Icebreaker	This activity helps participants get to know each other through a series of exercises, including introductions, sharing hopes and fears, creating a group manifesto, and organizing themselves in line-ups based on personal attributes.
Question	Speculative Design	Groups were assigned different planets and asked to design colonies addressing biological, security, and social needs using materials like LEGO, paper, and markers.
Analyse	Active Travel Talk & Mapping Exercise	This activity engages participants in exploring Active Travel by mapping their local areas and collaboratively reflecting on barriers through visual and interactive activities.
Reflecting	Zine Making	Zine-making is a creative reflection activity where participants explore the day's learnings by responding to prompts and adding personal content to their own mini-publications.
Analyse	Biodiversity Walk	This activity involved a guided tour of Trinity College Dublin's campus led by the Sustainability Manager, providing participants with insights into its biodiversity.
Analyse	AI Workshop	This activity encourages students to think critically and creatively about AI through discussions, hands-on sculpture building, storytelling, and critique, exploring AI's role, limitations, and impact on society.
Analyse	Water Walk and Sustainable Building Workshop	This activity engaged students in exploring water and sustainable building through a campus tour and a hands-on project where they design and construct a sustainable building model while balancing economic and environmental considerations.
Analyse	Ethics: Walking Debate	This activity engages students in ethical debates by having them physically position themselves as 'Agree' or 'Disagree' in a House of Commons-style setup, where they justify their opinions and engage in structured discussions.

Analyse	Gamification Workshop	This session featured presentations from Bold Donut and Smart Docklands, followed by an individual mobile game and a group activity where students designed games on sustainability and urban technology topics.
Analyse	Dublin Through the Years workshop	This interactive session engaged participants in exploring Dublin's history and transformation through surveys and map comparisons, informing their visions for the city's future.
Envision	Idea Generation	This method fosters idea generation for addressing Dublin's urban challenges through analysis of student-generated ideas, root cause exploration with the '5 Whys' technique, playful deconstruction of urban systems, and rapid brainstorming of innovative solutions.
Analyse	Communication Workshop	This method involves a presentation on communication styles followed by a creative activity where participants create memes to effectively convey a message.
Envision	Prototyping	This method guides participants in negotiating and refining their ideas to create a prototype and develop a compelling pitch for a solution to a specific issue.
Act	Pitching	This involved teams pitching their prototypes to a panel of judges, followed by a question-and-answer session where they receive feedback on their ideas.

Impact and Key Learnings

The impact of *Design Your Future City* extended beyond the week itself. Several students committed to continuing their work, returning for a follow-up session in May where they would develop their solutions further with potential funding from the city council. Others left with a deeper awareness of the interconnectedness of environmental, technological, and social issues.

As facilitators and stakeholders reflected on the lab's impact, several key learnings emerged. Structured reflection throughout the week proved essential, as iterative feedback helped refine ideas into more meaningful solutions. Creative methods—like *Speculative Design*, *Prototyping*, and *Zine-Making*—made complex issues accessible and inspiring. A major takeaway was the importance of fostering

agency in young people. While many began disillusioned about influencing city planning, engaging with decision-makers gave them confidence. The lab also highlighted the need to connect education with real-world impact, with the next challenge being continued support and implementation.

Looking ahead, future iterations of the lab could benefit from deeper explorations of long-term urban sustainability challenges, incorporating historical perspectives on city evolution to further engage critical thinking. Additionally, expanding opportunities for mentorship and ongoing collaboration between students and professionals would reinforce the belief that young people are not just the future of the city, but that they are active contributors to its present.

2.1.3 Trinity College Dublin Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged cumulatively between TCD's CCLABs.

Table 8 - Trinity College Dublin KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	34
Participants from underrepresented groups	27
Educators	15
Other stakeholders	5
Researchers-facilitators	2
Number of participants (in final focus group)	11
Number of educators (in final interview)	2
Number of CSOs	5
Number of formal education organizations	1
Number of non-formal education organizations	3

3.2 University of Oulu (Finland)

The University of Oulu (Oulu) completed two iterations during PAR Cycle 2 around the theme “Growing up in social media: Issues and challenges” - one conducted at Kastelli school (that ran two twin labs) and the other one at Norssi school. Reports on both iterations are described below.

3.2.1 Growing up with social media: Experiences from Kastelli school

Table 9 - Details of Kastelli lab

Geographical location	Oulu, Finland
Demographic characteristics of participants	43 participants, 7th graders from the local school; 12–14-year-old students taking an ICT compulsory course Gender: 25 boys and 18 girls
Number of sessions	8
What is the topic of the cycle?	Online wellbeing – being nice to each other on the internet, empathy, social media (online safety), learning to use software systems used at the school to communicate and collaborate

At Kastelli Koulu in Oulu, Finland, two groups of 7th-grade students participated in 2 Critical ChangeLabs exploring the challenges and responsibilities of growing up with social media. Facilitated as part of their Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) compulsory course, two groups of students (Group A and Group B) engaged in parallel learning experiences, investigating online behaviour, digital democracy, and social interactions in virtual spaces. The project was connected to the *Oulu Loves Me* initiative, promoting anti-racism and social inclusion. At the end of the lab, students’ work was showcased in the public exhibition *Youth against Racism: Voices for Change*, open to the public from 11th until the 24th of March 2025 at the Valve cultural centre as part of the Week Against Racism program.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

The researchers and facilitators introduced the labs to students by presenting the goals and methods of the lab through interactive discussions and digital tools. While the researchers had prior experience collaborating with the school, this was their first time working directly with these student groups. The project was structured into eight sessions, with each group following a similar sequence of activities but reflecting their own unique discussions, perspectives, and challenges.

Both groups started with a session aimed at understanding democracy and its connection to everyday activities of young people. Students completed an activity, *Mentimeter Questions*, where they responded to questions like "What is democracy?". Their responses highlighted varying perspectives, with some students associating democracy with formal government structures, while others linked to the idea of deciding things together. Some of the examples include: "Demokratiassa kaikki saa tuoda omat mielipiteet kuulluksi" (In a democracy, everyone gets to make their opinions heard); "siellä on yhteistä päättämistä" (it means deciding together) and "It is like everybody in the country can vote and decide of some things". The responses led to a discussion regarding how democracy appears as part of everyday life practices such as social media interactions. This was followed by another question "How is growing up with social media?". The broader theme of the lab *Growing up with Social Media: Issues and Challenges* was defined with the teacher by keeping in mind the contents of the ICT course. The students were invited to participate in the lab as research partners to explore this topic and see what issue and challenges they find in this research.

One of the first interactive activities, *Scenario Writing: How Do We Make Others Feel with Our Comments?*, encouraged students to explore the impact of everyday interactions. Participants were given a situation, an emotion (e.g., jealousy, anger, supportiveness), and a character (such as a cat, robot, or teenager). They then created storyboards depicting everyday interactions based on the assigned roles. The activity allowed for conversation on how tone and wording shape digital communication. While some initially found the exercise amusing, their reflections changed as they considered the real-world consequences of online comments. This led to a discussion where students created a collective code of conduct for respectful behaviour in online and face to face interactions.

Another key activity, *Researcher ID: All of Us Are Researchers!*, positioned students as active investigators of their digital experiences. They were tasked with collecting real-world examples from social media-screenshots of interactions they found problematic or noteworthy. These included bullying, misinformation, and unrealistic beauty standards. Students shared their findings in small groups, reflecting on why certain content stood out and how it influenced their perceptions of social media.

As sessions progressed, groups moved toward transforming their research insights into creative outputs. Through *Thinking Hats* activity, they explored competencies - such as critical self-reflection, openness to different worldviews, and democratic decision-making - by metaphorically "wearing" these skills while analysing collected data. This approach helped make abstract concepts more tangible.

The groups then engaged in *Thematic Analysis of the Collected Data* where they categorized their findings and voted on key topics to focus on in their final projects. Chosen themes included bullying, hate comments, appearance pressures, and racism. These became the foundation for their research and creative outputs. During the analysis, while some struggled with making connections between personal experiences and larger societal patterns, facilitators guided them in recognizing how individual actions contribute to broader digital cultures. The analysis continued with making mind maps to explore the chosen topics and interviewing other groups to have broader insights about the topics explored.

Figure 8 - Making mind maps for an in-depth exploration of the chosen topic

In the later sessions, students worked on designing creative apps designs for future social media apps that would promote online wellbeing and safety by promoting inclusion, diversity and respect for all. They designed wireframes, logos and design features for these futuristic apps that would be the solution of the current tensions they found during their data collection and analysis. The students designed digital posters to share their research and innovative solutions with the school community. For example, one of the groups found examples of bullying on social media based on appearance during their research. While making mind maps, they focused on exploring the causes/reasons of bullying and discussed race, appearance, social status and physical appearance as the main reasons. Later, while designing the social media app, they laid stress on design features that would help in filtering the negative comments by using the power of AI. They named their envisioned app “*Some Cleaner*” (Some is a Finnish slang for social media). Finally, their digital poster had a background image of a girl sitting on the floor and being pointed at by a hand coming from a phone screen. Speech bubbles with characters representing insults and bullying are shown.

Figure 9 - Designing posters with students

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the 17 sessions of the CCLAB (eight session per group and one combined onboarding session), indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process:

Table 10 - Overview of methods used during Kastelli lab

Process Step	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Mentimeter Questions	This activity engages students in discussions on everyday democracy and social media by prompting them to answer key questions via QR codes, facilitating peer discussions that highlight diverse perspectives and connections to real-life experiences.
Onboard	Scenario writing: How do we make others feel with our comments?	This activity encourages critical thinking about everyday interactions by having students create storyboards with assigned emotions and characters, leading to discussions on how emotions and comments impact others, followed by the development of group rules for respectful communication.
Question	Researcher ID: All of us are researchers!	This activity empowers students as active researchers by equipping them with research tools and guiding them through data collection, analysis, and discussion on social media interactions, encouraging critical thinking and envisioning better digital futures.
Question	Researcher ID: Collecting data	This activity empowers students as active researchers by equipping them with research tools and guiding them through data collection, analysis, and discussion on social media interactions, encouraging critical thinking and envisioning better digital futures.
Question	Thinking Hats: Competences	This method engages participants in identifying and prioritizing key competencies by using simplified competence cards and a "thinking hat" metaphor, encouraging reflection, discussion, and self-assessment to guide their learning focus.
Analyse	Researcher ID: Analysing Data	This activity deepens participants' understanding of their collected data by identifying themes through group discussion, asking analytical questions, and organizing findings visually to guide further exploration.

Analyse	Mindmaps	This activity encourages participants to explore an issue from multiple perspectives by creating mind maps that define the theme, identify key actors, roles, causes, and impacts, and visualize connections between different aspects.
Analyse	Self-documentation Interviews	This activity reinforces participants' roles as researchers by having them interview other groups about their mind maps, using guiding questions to explore different perspectives while documenting the process with GoPros.
Envision	Presentation by "Oulu loves Me" (Week against racism)	This activity introduces young people to local services and community initiatives while fostering discussions on prejudice, racism, and AI biases, encouraging them to engage in events and envision future solutions.
Envision	AI generated Image detection game	This activity encourages critical thinking about AI-generated images by having participants analyse and identify AI-created visuals through an interactive quiz, followed by a discussion on their reasoning.
Envision	Designing future social media apps	This activity fosters imagination and creativity through speculative design by having participants envision future social media features that prevent bullying and racism, create logos and wireframes, and present their ideas to the class.
Act	Designing posters: Sharing thoughts with the community	This activity engages participants in putting together their insights from the lab by creating digital posters using Adobe Express, helping them explore different ways to voice their ideas, raise awareness, and share their messages with the community.
Act	Presentations: sharing with class & follow up discussion	This activity allows participants to present their posters to the class and visitors, receive feedback, and elaborate on their ideas using previously created materials like thematic analyses, mind maps, and app designs.
Reflect	Focus Group discussion:	These sessions provide a space for students to reflect on their experiences, discuss the insights they gained, evaluate how their perspectives have evolved, and

	evaluation and feedback	share feedback on the democratic values they explored throughout the process.
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Impact and Key Learnings

Throughout the project, both Group A and Group B faced challenges in engaging deeply with certain concepts. In some sessions, students hesitated to share personal experiences, particularly when discussing difficult topics like racism or cyberbullying. Researchers noted a moment of collective silence in Group B when they were presented with the statement: "Racism is something that is part of it (social media), you can't do anything about it." This hesitation suggested an emotional impact, though it also highlighted the difficulty of openly discussing sensitive social issues in a classroom setting.

Another challenge was the varying levels of engagement with the *Researcher ID* activity. While some students enthusiastically collected and analysed social media screenshots, others were less motivated, with some failing to complete the assignment. The researchers noted that requiring students to do this task as homework may have contributed to lower participation and suggested more in-class collaborative analysis in future iterations.

Despite these challenges, the lab provided valuable insights into students' digital lives and their perceptions of online interactions. Many students demonstrated an increased awareness of their role in shaping digital spaces and the impact of their online behaviour. The project reinforced that young people are not just passive users of social media but also active participants who shape and influence digital culture.

By engaging with democratic principles through digital platforms, students also began to see connections between their online experiences and broader societal issues. The discussions on self-reflection, responsibility, and digital citizenship encouraged students to think critically about their own interactions and the power dynamics embedded in social media.

As the final session concluded, students reflected on their learning journeys. Some noted that they had never considered how their words online could influence and impact others, while others expressed a desire to continue exploring digital ethics

in future courses. The work produced in the labs was later presented at the *Oulu Loves Me* exhibition, bringing their reflections and findings into a public space where their voices could contribute to a wider conversation on responsible digital engagement.

3.2.2 Growing up with social media: Experiences from Norssi school

Table 11 - Details of Norssi lab

Geographical location	Oulu, Finland
Demographic characteristics of participants	21 participants, 7 th graders from the local schools; 12–14-year-old. Gender: 11 boys, 10 girls. The students in this group have migrant backgrounds, which reflects in the repertoire of languages mastered by students in their family contexts (8–10 different spoken by students).
Number of sessions	7
What is the topic of the cycle?	MOK course – required by Finnish curriculum (phenomenon based learnings) based on UN 17 goals, also UNESCO goals. The theme for 7 th grade MOK lessons was based on UNESCO themes – tolerance, sustainable development, democracy education, etc. The researchers linked it with the theme of tensions young people see in their everyday social media interactions.

At Oulun Normaalkoulu, a group of 21 seventh-grade students engaged in a Critical ChangeLab exploring the role of social media in their daily lives. The lab was part of their MOK course, which follows the Finnish curriculum’s focus on phenomenon-based learning, addressing themes such as democracy, tolerance, and sustainability. Facilitated in collaboration with the University of Oulu, the research was structured into six sessions, culminating in a final presentation of student-led insights at the *Oulu Loves Me* exhibition during the *Week Against Racism*. An international association Designing for Children’s Rights (D4CR), who advocates for

designing services and products targeting children from a child-centred rights-based approach perspective, was also involved when planning of the envisioning activities, which focused on design. They contributed to the lab design by offering advice and sharing the D4CR guide, which gathers design-aid materials to guide the design of services and products mindful of children's rights.

The student group was diverse, with participants representing 8-10 different language backgrounds. The facilitators noted that, although the students had enthusiasm for new challenges, they had not previously engaged in eco-social projects. Given this, the research team aimed to connect their coursework to real-life experiences with social media, encouraging critical reflection on digital interactions, bullying, racism, and online pressures.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

The initial session introduced the concept of everyday democracy using *Mentimeter Questions*. Students responded to the question "What is democracy?" and were prompted to reflect on how democracy appears in their digital interactions. Their responses varied, with some associating democracy with political systems while others related it to fairness in social settings. A subsequent question - "How is growing up with social media?" - generated both positive and negative reflections, with students mentioning its role in communication but also concerns about racism, bullying, and harmful content.

Students also participated in an interactive icebreaker, *This or That*, where they physically positioned themselves in response to prompts about group work preferences. This activity helped students consider democratic values such as participation and decision-making within collaborative settings. From there, they moved to co-defining competencies, using example cards to match abstract concepts like openness to worldviews and critical self-reflection with real-life scenarios.

Figure 10 - Co-defining competences

A key component of the project was *Researcher ID: All of Us Are Researchers!*, where students collected social media screenshots representing digital issues such as bullying, misinformation, and appearance pressures. They uploaded their findings and wrote short reflections explaining their relevance. While some students actively participated, others struggled to connect their research to personal experiences. The facilitators noted that although students could identify issues like racism and hate speech in broader contexts, they hesitated to relate them to their own online interactions.

During the *Thematic Analysis* session, students categorized their collected data into recurring themes and each group chose one topic to explore in detail. Using mind maps, they expanded on their chosen topics by identifying key actors (e.g., bystanders, influencers, victims), locations of digital conflicts (e.g., social media platforms, messaging apps), and underlying causes. After completing *Mindmaps*, each group interviewed one other group to discuss what they have explored in their mind maps. This activity helped in gaining a deeper understanding of the issues under discussion. The facilitators observed that while students were comfortable analysing public digital behaviours, they were less forthcoming about discussing personal experiences, often framing discussions in a detached manner.

Figure 11 – Self-documentation interviews

To transition from research to action, students participated in *Speculative Design* activities envisioning ethical digital futures. They brainstormed improvements for social media platforms, proposing features that could reduce online harm. Using wireframing techniques, they designed mock-up interfaces with functions like automated hate-speech filters, enhanced content moderation, and community-driven reporting tools. Students also created new logos for their imagined platforms, ensuring their designs reflected values such as inclusion and fairness.

Figure 12 – Designing wireframe for envisioned social media app

Another activity, *Multiple Perspectives*, had students assume roles such as social media CEOs, influencers, and advertisers to explore how different stakeholders impact digital culture. Through guided discussions, students considered the ethical responsibilities of platform designers and content creators. Students created pamphlets to advertise their envisioned apps and presented them to their classmates.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process:

Table 12 - Overview of methods used during Norssi lab

Process Step	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Mentimeter Questions	This activity engages students in discussions on everyday democracy and social media by prompting them to answer key questions via QR codes, facilitating peer discussions that highlight diverse perspectives and connections to real-life experiences.
Onboard	This or That (Icebreaker) and group rules	This activity encourages critical thinking about everyday choices and group dynamics by having participants physically move to represent their decisions, engage in discussions on democracy in teamwork, and collaboratively establish group rules.
Question	Competences: Co-defining meaning	This activity helps understand competencies by linking abstract concepts to real-life examples, engaging in group discussions to match competencies with relevant examples, and conducting a needs analysis to determine which competencies they want to focus on.
Question	Researcher ID: All of us are researchers! Collecting data	This activity empowers students as active researchers by equipping them with research tools and guiding them through data collection, analysis, and discussion on social media interactions, encouraging critical thinking and envisioning better digital futures.
Analyse	Ice breaker: Getting to know one another	This activity encourages participants to reflect on everyday choices and cultural naming traditions by organizing themselves alphabetically by their second

		names, fostering discussions on different naming conventions and perspectives.
Analyse	Researcher ID: analysing data	This activity deepens participants' understanding of their collected data by identifying themes through group discussion, asking analytical questions, and organizing findings visually to guide further exploration.
Question	Self-documentation	This activity enhances research competence by having participants document their research process step by step using cameras, guiding questions, and group discussions to reflect on their theme selection and decision-making process.
Question	Homework: Questioning our everyday Interactions with technologies	This activity encourages participants to critically interpret images related to technology use, connecting them to their chosen themes and reflecting on conflicts and tensions in everyday digital interactions through a guided digital homework task.
Analyse	Mindmaps	This activity encourages participants to explore an issue from multiple perspectives by creating mind maps that define the theme, identify key actors, roles, causes, and impacts, and visualize connections.
Analyse	Self-documentation-Interviews	This activity reinforces participants' roles as researchers by having them interview other groups about their mind maps, using guiding questions to explore different perspectives while documenting the process with GoPros.
Analyse	Warm up activity: Multiple perspectives	This activity encourages participants to explore an issue from multiple perspectives by assuming different roles, reflecting on their viewpoints, and engaging in discussions to contrast ideas and deepen understanding.
Envision	Speculative Design: Designing new features for future social media apps	This activity fosters imagination and creativity through speculative design by having participants envision and design new social media features that prevent bullying and racism, create wireframes, and develop logos that reflect their envisioned changes. As inspiration material to aid the design process, participants were introduced to the Designing for

		Children’s Rights Guide and some of its design principles.
Act	Advertising their app designs: Designing brochures	This activity encourages participants to practice voicing their ideas by creating brochures that promote their social media app designs, using visuals and slogans to explain how their features address current issues and enhance digital platforms.
Reflect	Focus group discussion: Evaluation and feedback	These sessions provide a space for students to reflect on their experiences, discuss the insights they gained, evaluate how their perspectives have evolved, and share feedback on the democratic values they explored throughout the process.

Impact and Key Learnings

Despite the students’ enthusiasm, several challenges emerged throughout the project. Participation varied, with some students actively engaging while others remained reserved. Facilitators observed that abstract discussions about democracy and ethics were initially difficult for students to relate to, but hands-on exercises like role play and speculative design helped bridge this gap. Another challenge was students’ reluctance to share personal digital experiences, possibly due to discomfort discussing sensitive topics in a group setting. This highlighted the need for structured, trust-building activities before engaging in discussions about online behaviour.

However, key learning moments also emerged. The thematic analysis session helped students recognize recurring digital tensions and consider their broader implications. Some students, initially hesitant, became more engaged when allowed to express ideas visually, using drawings and concept maps to illustrate digital challenges. The *Speculative Design* exercise was particularly effective, as it allowed students to shift from identifying problems to envisioning actionable solutions, reinforcing their role as active digital citizens rather than passive social media users.

The discussions on democracy and digital culture helped the students to critically reflect on their online interactions and recognize their agency in shaping digital spaces. While challenges in engagement and personal reflection remained, the

combination of research, discussion, and creative exercises provided a foundation for continued exploration of digital citizenship.

The final outputs of the project, including mind maps, speculative design models, and thematic reflections, were presented at the exhibition *Youth against Racism: Voices for Change* displayed from 11th until the 24th of March 2025, during the Week Against Racism. The exhibition was arranged in collaboration with the multicultural center Villa Victor and Valve, a local cultural centre, to showcase students' views and contribute to a broader conversation on responsible digital engagements.

3.2.3 University of Oulu Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged cumulatively between the University of Oulu's CCLABs.

Table 13 - University of Oulu KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	71
Participants from underrepresented groups	71
Educators	5
Other stakeholders	5
Researchers-facilitators	5
Number of participants (in final focus group)	60
Number of educators (in final interview)	3
Number of CSOs	3
Number of formal education organizations	2
Number of non-formal education organizations	2

3.3 European Alternatives (France)

European Alternatives conducted three labs – one in Saint-Laurent-du Maroni (French Guiana), a second at Lycée Michel-Ange (France), and the third in Palermo (Italy). The lab in Palermo included students under the age of 11, and is thus noted as an exploratory lab.

3.3.1 Saint-Laurent-du-Maroni

Table 14 - Details of Saint-Laurent-du-Maroni lab

Geographical location	French Guiana
Demographic characteristics of participants	People from 11-14 ages
Number of sessions	2
What is the topic of the cycle?	Food, fishing, environment and access to food in water areas

At a public high school in Saint-Laurent-du-Maroni, French Guiana, students participated in a Critical ChangeLab facilitated by Fondazione Studio Rizoma in collaboration with an art teacher. Designed to explore young people’s relationship with the sea and food, the lab aimed to raise awareness about environmental issues related to local marine resources. Over three sessions, students engaged in discussions and creative activities that encouraged them to reflect on traditional fishing practices, the environmental impact of their food choices, and the economic challenges facing their community.

The participants included students aged 14 to 16 from diverse sociocultural backgrounds. While some had family ties to traditional fishing and cooking practices, others were more influenced by industrial food and imported products. The discussions highlighted this diversity, as well as varying levels of environmental awareness. Some students expressed concerns about overfishing, pollution, and food sustainability, while others were less informed about these issues.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

Each session was structured around key themes, including sustainable fishing, food sovereignty, and environmental pollution. The art teacher moderated debates and encouraged students to share their knowledge and experiences. Discussions often centred on the tension between traditional food practices and modern consumption habits. Some students took pride in their knowledge of traditional dishes and fishing techniques, while others admitted preferring industrial fish products, such as fish sticks, because they did not want to see the whole animal. This contrast revealed a disconnect between cultural identity and contemporary dietary habits, leading to reflections on how food choices shape personal and collective identity.

One of the most debated topics was illegal and unregulated fishing. Students recognized that some fishing practices were unsustainable but also noted the economic pressures facing local fishermen. The issue of illegal fishing by neighbouring countries added complexity to the discussion, with students questioning who should be responsible for regulating marine resources. Facilitators observed that while students initially viewed overfishing as a distant problem, they gradually began connecting it to their own habits and the economic realities of their community.

The impact of mercury contamination from gold mining was another central topic. While some students were aware that gold mining polluted local rivers, they were surprised to learn about its long-term impact on fish and human health. This realization led to discussions about economic survival versus environmental damage, as some families depend on mining while also suffering from its consequences. The debate on imported food further expanded these reflections, with students noting that local fishing is declining, leading to greater reliance on frozen fish and processed foods. This prompted conversations about colonial history, economic dependence, and the loss of food sovereignty in French Guiana.

Facilitators introduced creative and research-based methods to help students engage with the project themes. One key activity, *From River to Plate: Exploring Sustainable Fishing and Food Traditions*, encouraged students to document their community's fishing practices and food traditions. Students gathered insights from fishermen, vendors, and family members, then created videos, photographs, and reports to share their findings. While some students were confident in discussing

their knowledge, others struggled with media documentation, highlighting a need for further technical training in storytelling and digital literacy.

Another method involved case studies and testimonials, where students examined concrete examples of marine pollution and reacted to local environmental issues. Facilitators observed moments of tension as students realized the complexity of balancing ecological preservation with economic survival. Some students strongly criticized overfishing and pollution but had difficulty acknowledging that many local families depend on fishing for their livelihoods. This tension highlighted the need for continued discussions on sustainability that consider both environmental and economic realities.

In the final session, a *Proposal Workshop* encouraged students to imagine solutions for more sustainable consumption. They reflected on ways to take local action, such as promoting traditional recipes that have a lower environmental impact. Some students proposed awareness campaigns about responsible fishing, while others suggested using social media to document and share knowledge on food sustainability.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process:

Table 15 - Methods used during Saint-Laurent-du-Maroni lab

Process Step	Activity or Method	Description
Question/ Analyse/Act/ Reflect	From River to Plate: Exploring Sustainable Fishing and Food Traditions	This activity engages youth in exploring the ecological and cultural significance of traditional food practices by investigating local fishing and food sources, documenting their findings through media, and fostering discussions on sustainability and community impact.
Question/ Analyse/Act/ Reflect	Case Studies and Testimonials	This activity involves the review and debate of concrete examples of marine pollution and local environmental issues.
Question/ Analyse/Act/ Reflect	Proposal Workshop	In this activity, students imagine solutions for more sustainable consumption.

Impact and Key Learnings

Throughout the discussions, students experienced shifts in understanding and engagement. They began questioning everyday contradictions in their food choices - such as why traditional foods often cost more than imported processed ones. This sparked debates on economic inequality and food policies, with some arguing that current systems favour large businesses over local producers.

Another key learning moment came during conversations about gender roles in fishing and cooking. Some male students assumed women didn't fish, only to be challenged by peers who shared real-life examples from their families. Similarly, while some dismissed traditional dishes - like fish heads or iguanas - as "disgusting," others defended them as part of their cultural heritage. These exchanges encouraged students to confront their assumptions and appreciate the diversity of food practices in their community.

Many also developed a greater sense of agency, recognizing that their diets are shaped by broader environmental and economic systems. Students who were previously indifferent to sustainability expressed a desire to learn more and take action. While not all were ready to change behaviours, most left with a clearer awareness of their role as consumers and community members.

The lab at the high school in Saint-Laurent-du-Maroni produced videos, photos, and reflections on food sustainability and marine issues. These materials now serve as both documentation and a springboard for future advocacy. Facilitators noted that combining discussion, research, and creative media helped students connect with complex topics in meaningful ways.

Figure 13 - Drawing created during the lab

3.3.2 Lycée Michel-Ange

Table 16 - Details of Lycée Michel-Ange lab

Geographical location	Villeneuve La Garenne, Ile de France
Demographic characteristics of participants	17-year-old students, school level premiere
Number of sessions	2
What is the topic of the cycle?	Artificial intelligence and social media

At Lycée Michel-Ange in Villeneuve La Garenne, France, a group of 18 students participated in a Critical ChangeLab focused on AI and social media. Facilitated by European Alternatives in collaboration with a professor and an educator, the lab aimed to provide students with a space to critically engage with the opportunities and risks posed by AI technologies. Over two sessions, students explored the implications of AI in their daily lives, participated in structured debates, and engaged in creative activities designed to foster critical thinking and democratic decision-making.

The participants, aged around 17, had no prior experience engaging with eco-social conflicts beyond their academic coursework and their lived experiences growing up in the suburbs of France. Their involvement in the project was facilitated through their teacher, who played a key role in making the time and space available for the PAR Cycles. The sessions focused on key competencies such as knowledge and critical understanding of the world, openness to different worldviews, imaginative and inventive thinking, transformative agency, and democratic dispositions.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

The first session began with an introduction to the lab, highlighting the importance of critical engagement with AI and social media. Students participated in a round-circle debate stimulated by a five-minute podcast from a mainstream media radio chronicle. The discussion was structured around three main questions: How do you use AI and social media in your daily life? What are the advantages and potentials of AI and social media? What are the risks associated with these technologies?

The debate lasted for about an hour, with many students sharing their personal experiences with AI tools such as chatbots, recommendation algorithms, and automated systems in education. The discussion also touched on privacy concerns, misinformation, and the ethical implications of AI-driven decision-making.

Following the debate, students engaged in a role-playing exercise, *Role Game*, designed to help them understand different perspectives on AI regulation. They were divided into small groups, each representing a specific stakeholder: the Prime Minister, an Internet magnate, a human rights organization, an anarchist, and a grandmother. Each group was given time to discuss their positions and negotiate common proposals for AI governance.

Students were engaged in this exercise, with some showing enthusiasm in defending their assigned roles. The discussions highlighted competing viewpoints, such as the balance between technological innovation and privacy rights, the role of governments in regulating AI, and ethical concerns surrounding data usage. Each group presented their findings, leading to further debate on the complexity of decision-making in AI policy.

The second session began with a reflective discussion on the previous debate, allowing students to share any further thoughts or insights they had developed since the first session. This was followed by a creative exercise known as *Living Portraits*, in which students created "tableaux vivants" (living pictures) to represent different future scenarios of AI in education. They were split into groups and tasked with creating two contrasting scenes: one depicting a best-case scenario in which AI is used to enhance education, and another portraying a dystopian future where AI has taken control in a negative way.

Students worked to embody their assigned roles, using body language and positioning to communicate their vision. Once the tableaux were presented, other students were asked to interpret the scenes by describing what they saw and discussing what messages were being conveyed. While some groups depicted AI as a tool for innovation and accessibility, others presented cautionary tales about surveillance, lack of teacher autonomy, and the depersonalization of education.

In the final segment of the project, students worked in teams to propose regulations for AI governance. They chose three key topics for regulation: the environmental impact of AI data centres, data protection and international treaties, and age restrictions on AI usage. Each team was tasked with defining their regulation, identifying who would be responsible for enforcement, and outlining potential consequences for violations. [Three videos](#) with AI generated images were produced based on the voice recording prepared by the students.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process:

Table 17 - Methods used during Lycée Michel-Ange lab

Process Step	Activity or Method	Description
Onboarding / Question	General debate // Discussion in a round circle	This activity fosters reflection on the benefits, limitations, and potential risks of AI and social media through guided group discussions.
Analyse / Envision / Examine	Role Game	This activity enhances teamwork, deliberation, and perspective-taking through a role-playing exercise where students assume different societal roles to discuss and negotiate solutions on a given topic. They also need to present their results to the other groups and then discuss all together on whether they agree/disagree
Reflect	Discussion in a round circle: Feedback from previous session and deepening of the reflection based on questions such as: What do you recall from last session? Did last session lead you to further reflections on the use and development of AI?	The students sit in a circle (formed by them helping move the seats and tables around the classroom, i.e., the sitting is not very formal – it's ok to sit on tables too for instance) and questions were asked regarding their experience in the previous session and whether they had any further reflections after the previous session. This provided the opportunity for short feedback on what was discussed the previous time, refreshing ideas.
Envision / Examine	Living Portraits	This activity promotes teamwork and future scenario planning by engaging participants in creating and analysing tableaux vivants that depict both ideal and dystopian visions of AI integration in education.
Act / Reflect	Regulations proposals for AI	The students recorded the results of teamwork in which they refined their proposals in the areas they had identified as key when it comes to AI : the environment, an age limit and transnational cooperation on the regulation of AI. Each of the 3 groups of students sent their voice recording to

		<p>the facilitator from EA by emails. Then videos were produced with the use of a software using AI generated videos – the videos were sent back to each group and to the teacher for further consultation and reflection.</p>
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Impact and Key Learnings

Throughout the sessions, several significant learning moments emerged. One key realization for students was the recognition of contradictions in AI regulation. While many supported stricter data protection measures, they also acknowledged the challenges of enforcing such regulations in a digital world where data flows across borders. This led to discussions about corporate accountability and the role of international agreements in safeguarding users' rights. The most astonishing result was that the whole group agreed that AI use should be forbidden before the age of 16 (while they were only 17). This was their own recommendation and suggestion, at the surprise of the facilitators. The whole group kept defending such a proposal over the 2 sessions.

Another critical moment occurred during the *Living Portraits* exercise, where students expressed discomfort with the idea of a fully automated education system. Some noted that while AI could provide valuable tools, it should not replace human teachers, as education requires emotional intelligence and adaptability. This led to a discussion on the irreplaceable aspects of human interaction in learning environments.

Students also demonstrated increased openness to different perspectives. The role-playing exercise challenged some initial assumptions, particularly regarding government regulation versus corporate responsibility. While some students initially viewed regulation as overly restrictive, they later acknowledged its necessity in ensuring ethical AI usage.

While some students entered the sessions with limited knowledge of AI, many left with a deeper understanding of its implications and the societal debates surrounding its use. Facilitators observed that by the end of the project, students had developed stronger analytical skills and a greater awareness of the ethical complexities of AI.

3.3.3 Palermo (Exploratory Lab)

Table 18 - Details of Palermo lab

Geographical location	Palermo, Italy
Demographic characteristics of participants	Children of all genders; between 3 and 11 years old; coming from disadvantaged background
Number of sessions	2
What is the topic of the cycle?	Relationship as humans to other living beings (animals); deepening vision that children living in Palermo have on the ecological aspect of their city; acceptance of difference

At Ex-Cinema Edison in Palermo, Italy, a group of children aged 3 to 11 took part in an exploratory Critical ChangeLab, coordinated by Corrente Associazione. The lab was exploratory in nature as it worked with youth under the targeted aged of 11 – 18. It was decided to work with these students because we planned to do a series of CCLABS in Paris and Palermo with disadvantaged young people on themes of environmental change, displacement, education and democracy as a way to experiment in three ways: i) using films as a prompt for developing the CCLAB as a kind of ‘mirror’, both watching documentary films and through young people making videos; ii) with adapting the CCLABS methodology for isolated underage migrants who cannot commit to being in several sessions.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

This lab was designed as an early and open-ended engagement with key themes of environmental belonging, human-animal relationships, and urban inclusion. The lab combined film screenings with creative expression and dialogue, offering very young participants a gentle introduction to thinking critically about their surroundings.

The choice of venue - a former cinema repurposed as a community space - offered an inspiring and accessible environment for the children. The screenings, featuring animated films, created a soft entry point into deeper conversations. The films served not only as entertainment but as a mirror and lens through which children

could observe and process the world around them. The animated narratives provided symbolic language and imaginative settings that invited projection and reflection.

Figure 14 – A screening during the lab in Palermo

The sessions were structured around these films, which depicted relationships between animals and humans in both magical and urban settings. These screenings provided a shared reference point for guided conversations. Facilitators asked questions such as “Would Ponyo like living in Palermo?” and “What would Koda think of the traffic?”. These questions encouraged children to speak about their opinions through fictional characters, making it easier to voice worries and hopes for their environment. The children began speaking about pollution, traffic, rubbish, and the treatment of animals – issues that they recognized from daily life.

Beyond conversation, the lab focused on creative activities. Drawing exercises allowed children to visualize an ideal version of Palermo. In their initial drawings, familiar city scenes were common, but following collective discussions, children began to add green spaces, clean seas, and accessible parks. These shifts in their

illustrations reflected evolving perceptions and the incorporation of others' ideas. The act of modifying their drawings after discussion became a subtle, tangible form of collaborative imagination.

Figure 15 - Youth drawing during PAR Cycle in Palermo

In another activity, children engaged in basic role-playing exercises. They acted out imagined scenarios from the viewpoint of animals navigating the city. Some chose to be dogs looking for water, others imagined being birds dodging pollution or fish swimming in a dirty sea. These role-plays helped surface emotions - worry, fear, excitement - and made abstract issues more relatable. Facilitators observed how children's language and ideas expanded during these exercises, incorporating themes of care, empathy, and responsibility.

Democratic processes were also gently introduced. Children participated in voting exercises, choosing which ideas to draw or which animal stories to act out next. Group decisions were made on what kinds of changes they would want to see in their city. Some children voiced suggestions such as "cleaning the sea," "letting animals walk free," or "planting more trees." Others suggested that "humans should

listen more to animals.” These discussions – while informal and intuitive – served as early steps in collaborative decision-making and values-based dialogue.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process:

Table 19 – Overview of methods used during Palermo lab

Process Step	Activity or Method	Description
Question	Reflective discussions	This activity aims to develop reasoning, empathy, and verbal articulation through guided discussions and reflections on ethical treatment and inclusivity, using fictional characters like Ponyo or Koda as prompts.
Question	Visual storytelling and Art-Based learning	This activity encourages creative expression and exploration of social inclusion by having participants illustrate and collaboratively adapt scenes featuring fictional characters living in Palermo.
Act	Role playing and perspectives	This activity uses immersive role-play and storytelling to help participants understand diverse social perspectives and collaboratively solve challenges.
Envision / Examine	Collaborative problem solving and debate	This activity involves students debating and collaboratively proposing ways to make Palermo more inclusive for fictional characters.

Impact and Key Learnings

While the lab was exploratory in nature, it demonstrated that even very young children can engage in participatory and reflective activities. Their ability to connect fiction with real-life concerns, to imagine alternatives, and to respond to one another’s ideas with curiosity revealed the potential of Critical ChangeLabs as a format for early civic and ecological learning.

The impact of the lab could be seen in the subtle but meaningful shifts in how children talked about their environment and each other. Through creative and participatory methods, they became more comfortable articulating their ideas,

collaborating in group decisions, and expressing empathy for both human and non-human perspectives. The gentle, imaginative structure allowed for moments of insight, play, and shared vision—laying the groundwork for future, deeper engagements with eco-social issues and democratic learning processes.

3.3.4 European Alternatives Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged cumulatively between the European Alternatives' CCLABs.

Table 20 - European Alternative's KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	113
Participants from underrepresented groups	101
Educators	3
Other stakeholders	1
Researchers-facilitators	0
Number of participants (in final focus group)	113
Number of educators (in final interview)	2
Number of CSOs	1
Number of formal education organizations	1
Number of non-formal education organizations	0

3.4 LATRA (Greece)

3.4.1 Loutra Elementary School

Table 21 - Details of the Loutra Elementary School Lab

Geographical location	Loutra, Mytiliene, Lesvos, Greece
Demographic characteristics of participants	Local school children (11-year-olds) – primary target of research as the project focuses on understanding how democratic values resonate with them; Refugee children (11-year-olds) – also a key target audience, as their experiences and interactions within local classrooms are central to the study’s objectives.
Number of sessions	12
What is the topic of the cycle?	Fostering an understanding of democracy, inclusion, and fairness and redefining what it means to live together in a community, through creative methodologies like interactive theatre and role-playing.

In the town of Loutra, Mytilene, young students from diverse backgrounds gathered at Loutra Elementary School to take part in a lab designed to foster an understanding of democracy, inclusion, and fairness. The group gathered included both local Greek students and refugee students, offering an opportunity to explore and redefine what it means to live together in a community.

The CCLAB, structured around twelve interactive sessions, aimed to bring together children, teachers, parents, and the broader community. With the help of creative methodologies like interactive theatre, role-playing, and reflective discussions, students began to uncover the complexities of fairness, power, and representation in their daily lives.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

From the outset, facilitators faced a challenge: bridging the social and cultural gaps between local and refugee children. Many local students had never deeply interacted with their refugee classmates, and preconceived notions about each

other were evident. Through icebreakers and collaborative activities, the children slowly began breaking these barriers.

One of the first key exercises was a role-playing game that placed students in scenarios requiring them to make collective decisions. In a simulated village council, they debated how to distribute community resources, engaging with concepts like fairness and representation. Initially, some students dominated the discussion while others hesitated to speak up. But as facilitators encouraged quieter voices, the group began recognizing the importance of inclusive dialogue. To foster inclusive dialogue, facilitators introduced “circle practice” – a method inspired by restorative practices – where students sat in a circle and used a talking piece to ensure each voice had space. They also employed “equity sticks” to randomly select speakers, preventing dominant voices from taking over and ensuring equal participation. Additionally, elements of Socratic dialogue were used to promote open-ended questioning, active listening, and deeper reflection. Through these combined approaches, students gradually began to recognize the importance of equitable dialogue and the value of every perspective.

Figure 16 - Workshop with PAR2 participants prior to the theatre performance

Students then engaged in *Interactive Theatre Play*, using George Orwell's *Animal Farm* to engage students in democratic principles, power dynamics, and social justice. At several points during the play, students were given control over the storyline through voting. This interactive element forced them to make difficult choices, often leading to disagreements. However, through structured reflections, they learned to navigate these conflicts, understanding that in democracy, disagreement is not failure – it's part of the process.

Despite the students' engagement, not every session was without difficulties. Some local children, initially unfamiliar with democratic decision-making in action, struggled with compromising. Refugee students, on the other hand, sometimes hesitated to speak up, fearing their ideas would be dismissed. Facilitators noted these challenges and introduced structured activities to address them. In a reflective storytelling exercise, students shared personal experiences of fairness and unfairness in their lives. For many refugee children, this was an opportunity to voice struggles they had faced in adjusting to a new school system. Their stories revealed both moments of exclusion and small acts of kindness that had helped them feel included. Through these exchanges, students began to see each other not as "locals" or "refugees" but as individuals with unique experiences. Teachers, too, observed a shift – classroom discussions became more balanced, with a greater willingness to hear opposing perspectives.

Figure 17 - Workshop with PAR2 participants prior to the theatre performance where youth were asked to draw their point of view of a fair society

As the sessions progressed, students took ownership of their learning. They brainstormed ideas for making their school environment more inclusive. Some suggested a buddy system, pairing local and refugee students to foster friendship. Others proposed a school assembly where students could voice concerns and propose changes. One of the most inspiring moments came during a session where students reflected on what democracy meant to them personally. Using art and storytelling, they depicted images of fairness, cooperation, and shared responsibility. Some drew their dream classrooms, where all students had equal say; others crafted stories of imaginary worlds where different cultures coexisted in harmony.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process. Interactive Theatre Play and Exploring Democracy Through Creative Workshops were repeated multiple times throughout the CCLAB.

Table 22 – Overview of methods used during Loutra lab

Process Step	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Focus Group	This activity brings together parents, teachers, and community members to explore democratic values, identify barriers to inclusion, and co-create solutions through discussions, interactive sessions, and feedback.
Question	Scenario-based Role Playing	This role-playing activity immersed students in democratic principles by assigning diverse perspectives, facilitating interactive scenarios, encouraging critical thinking and collaboration, and concluding with reflective discussions on fairness, inclusion, and real-life applications.
Envision & Examine	Interactive Theatre Play	This interactive theatre activity uses Animal Farm to engage students in democratic principles, power dynamics, and social justice by allowing them to influence the storyline through voting, role-playing, and discussions, fostering critical thinking, empathy, and real-world connections.
Act	Exploring Democracy Through	This interactive workshop involves group discussions, role-playing, and artistic activities, helping children explore

	Creative Workshops: Building Empathy and Inclusion	power, justice, and inclusion while applying democratic values to real-life situations.
Reflect	Evaluation and Feedback Sessions	These sessions allow participants (students, teachers, parents) to share insights gained from the activities, assess how the experience changed their perspectives, and provide feedback on the democratic values they engaged with throughout the process.

Impact and Key Learnings

By the end of the project, elements of transformation were beginning to emerge. Parents noticed changes in their children’s attitudes, with many becoming more empathetic and open to different perspectives. Teachers reported improved classroom interactions, with students more willing to collaborate and resolve conflicts constructively. LATRA and local educators continue to explore ways to sustain this participatory model, integrating democratic learning into everyday schooling.

The lab revealed several critical insights about democratic education. First, active participation is key to understanding democratic values. The use of theatre and role-playing engaged students in a way that traditional lectures could not, making abstract concepts tangible and relatable.

Second, inclusivity requires ongoing effort. Simply bringing students from different backgrounds together is not enough; structured activities must facilitate meaningful interactions and mutual understanding. Ensuring that all voices are heard, particularly those of quieter or marginalized students, was a key takeaway for educators.

Third, democracy is a continuous process. The children learned that fairness is complex, and that decision-making often involves compromise. By practicing these skills in a safe learning environment, they became better equipped to apply them in real-world situations.

Finally, fostering a democratic mindset goes beyond the classroom. Parents, teachers, and the broader community play a vital role in shaping children’s perceptions of fairness, justice, and inclusion. Strengthening partnerships between schools and local organizations will be essential for sustaining these lessons over time.

Figure 18 - Workshop with PAR2 participants following the theatre performance where students drew about injustice and solutions

3.4.2 LATRA Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged by LATRA. LATRA was unique in that parents of local and refugee children participated in the lab as well; they are listed separately as adult participants.

Table 23 - LATRA’s KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	394
Adult participants in PAR cycle	153
Participants from underrepresented groups	394
Adult participants from underrepresented groups	153

Educators	51
Other stakeholders	44
Researchers-facilitators	3
Number of participants (in final focus group)	7
Number of educators (in final interview)	1
Number of CSOs	14
Number of formal education organizations	5
Number of non-formal education organizations	1

3.5 Institute for Social Research (Croatia)

The Institute for Social Research hosted three different ChangeLabs in three student dormitories named Dora Pejačević (UDDP), Novi Zagreb (UDNZ) and Marija Jambrišak (UDMJ). A summary of each is described below.

3.5.1 UDDP

Table 24 - Details of UDDP lab

Geographical location	Zagreb, Croatia
Demographic characteristics of participants	Participants were high school students living in a girls' student dorm "Dora Pejačević" in Zagreb/ They are students from other parts of Croatia that enrolled in high schools in Zagreb. All students are female, from first to fourth grade (15-18 years old.).
Number of sessions	7
What is the topic of the cycle?	Mental health of youth in education and its relation to educational inequalities. The topic explored the educational inequalities that stem from students' differences in their mental health. It was stated that students with mental health issues could be in less favourable position in the educational settings, since the educational system in Croatia mostly does not address the mental health issues of the students.

The Critical ChangeLab at the student dormitory Dora Pejačević in Zagreb, Croatia, brought together a group of high school girls to explore educational inequalities, particularly those rooted in mental health. The lab spanned seven sessions. The students, aged 15 to 18, were residents of the dormitory, attending various secondary schools in Zagreb while coming from different regions of Croatia. Although they varied in age and academic focus, a shared openness and willingness to explore complex topics served as a foundation for group cohesion. Educators noted that while older girls tended to be more active and confident, younger ones were increasingly drawn into the dynamic group environment, benefiting from peer support and guidance.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

The first session introduced key themes and encouraged students to reflect on their personal experiences with educational inequality. The *Walking Debate* allowed participants to physically and verbally express their positions on statements related to support systems in education. A notable moment came when several students shifted their stance after hearing others' perspectives, especially regarding whether students in dormitories receive more support than local peers.

Figure 19 - UDDP group during the 'Walking debate' activity

As the sessions progressed, methods like *Idea Mapping*, *Walk of Privilege*, and *5 Whys?* helped the students narrow down their interest to a central theme: the intersection between mental health and educational inequality. This topic resonated deeply, as many had witnessed or experienced stress and anxiety related to academic expectations. Through group discussions, they identified systemic pressures – such as grade inflation, lack of mental health resources in schools, and societal expectations – that contribute to mental health struggles for youth.

The mid-cycle sessions emphasized both reflection and research. Activities like *Life in Years*, *Photovoice*, and *Critical Cartography* allowed participants to map personal and social events that shaped their understanding of mental health. These exercises revealed how individual experiences intersect with broader educational and cultural dynamics. The students shared images and personal

stories that exposed risk factors (such as isolation and pressure) and protective factors (like support from educators or peer solidarity). One significant insight emerged during the *Life in Years* timeline: students recognized how recent global and national events, including the pandemic, had intensified mental health challenges in academic settings.

The imaginative power of the participants was seen during the *Future Scenarios* session. Divided into small groups, the girls created optimistic, pessimistic, and realistic narratives about the future of mental health in education. Using collages, clay models, and drawings, they illustrated potential changes such as increased mental health support in schools or, conversely, deepening inequality if mental well-being continued to be neglected. These scenarios highlighted a strong desire for transformation and offered creative pathways for envisioning systemic change.

In the penultimate session, students synthesized their insights into concrete actions through the creation of zines. Each zine combined personal reflections, creative expression, and advocacy for systemic improvements. The students explored different perspectives - from the roles of teachers and parents to policymakers - and proposed practical solutions such as more school psychologists, reduced emphasis on grades, and peer support programs.

The final session took place at the University Counseling Center, where students engaged with psychologists, and learned to use tools like associative cards to recognize signs of distress in others. This visit helped to bridge the gap between theoretical discussion and real-world resources.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 25 - Overview of methods used during UDDP lab

Process Step	Activity Method or	Description
Onboard	Walking debate	Participants position themselves along a continuum from "Completely disagree" to "Completely agree" in response to statements about educational

		inequalities, then discuss their reasoning in a guided conversation.
Onboarding	Idea Mapping	Participants collaboratively identify, discuss, and prioritize topics related to educational inequalities.
Questioning	Walk of privilege	Through role-playing and observation, participants experience and reflect on how social identities impact opportunities and outcomes, fostering awareness of systemic inequalities and society's role in addressing them.
Questioning/Analysing	5 whys?	Participants use the "5 Whys" method in groups to analyse the root causes of educational inequalities for students with mental health issues, identifying key symptoms and underlying factors.
Analysing	Life in years	Participants create a collective timeline of personal and societal events related to mental health in education, fostering reflection on how historical experiences shape attitudes and perspectives.
Envision/Examine	Photovoice	Participants share and discuss photographs they took or found that represent mental health in education, using visual storytelling to explore personal perspectives and experiences.
Envision/Examine	Critical Cartography	Participants enhance their research skills and critical thinking by analysing articles on mental health in education and related inequalities.
Envision/Examine	Future scenarios	Participants work in small groups to create and present optimistic, pessimistic, and realistic scenarios about educational inequalities related to mental health, using creative materials to visualize future outcomes and encourage discussion.
Act/Reflect	Fanzine (Zine)	Participants create and present a zine on mental health in education, using text and visuals to propose improvements, raise awareness, and engage different stakeholders.
Act	Visit to the University Counselling Centre for Students	Participants visit the University Counselling Centre for Students, where they gain a deeper understanding of mental health in education, real-life examples and are encouraged to engage in self-reflection.

Reflect	Dynamic chain reflection	Participants engage in a dynamic chain reflection by building on or challenging each other's statements about their experience, fostering collective insight and discussion.
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Impact and Key Learnings

Key learnings from the lab included the realization that mental health is deeply intertwined with educational equity. Participants gained new understanding of how structural factors like access to support, societal expectations, and geographical background shape educational experiences. Through democratic methods and creative tools, they practiced empathy, reflection, and agency. The lab also demonstrated the importance of creating safe, inclusive spaces where young people can examine societal issues, propose solutions, and feel empowered to act.

Additionally, the lab showed how creative expression - whether through zines, photography, or scenario-building - can deepen engagement and support critical thinking. It enforced the importance of bridging discussion with real-world experiences, such as the visit to the Counseling Center. Perhaps most significantly, it highlighted the value of peer connection and the capacity of young people to not only understand complex social challenges but also to articulate meaningful, imaginative solutions.

3.5.2 UDNZ

Table 26 - Details of UDNZ lab

Geographical location	Zagreb, Croatia
Demographic characteristics of participants	Participants were upper secondary school students living in a student dorm Novi Zagreb. 5 males and 9 females, aged 15-18 were regular at sessions. The participants are students coming from various smaller towns/ rural areas across Croatia, attending various upper secondary schools in Zagreb. Educational programmes in which they are enrolled ranged from general programmes (gymnasiums) to various vocational programmes (technical, tourism and restaurant services). Although all participants live in the

	same institution, not all students knew each other before participating in the lab.
Number of sessions	8
What is the topic of the cycle?	Students living in student dormitories often experience negative reactions from people they encounter in schools (other students and teachers) and local community, as there is a faulty perception of students in dormitories as problematic youth or youth living in homes for abandoned children or youth correctional facilities. Teachers sometimes are not sensitive to the needs of students living in student dormitories and react overly strictly and unreasonable. In addition, dormitories as institutions often suffer from the problem of social invisibility, as the hard work, effort and achievements of educators and students are often being overlooked.

At Student Dormitory Novi Zagreb, a group of upper secondary school students participated in a Critical ChangeLab aimed at exploring gender inequalities in education. Facilitated by the Institute for Social Research (ISRZ), the lab provided a space for students to critically examine social issues through interactive methods and discussions. Over the course of eight sessions, students engaged in structured debates, role-playing activities, creative exercises, and research-based methods that encouraged critical thinking and self-reflection.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

The first session introduced the lab and its objectives, with an initial *Walking Debate* that encouraged students to express their views on statements related to educational inequalities. This activity facilitated discussion and allowed students to explore perspectives within the group. Another early activity, *Mapping of the Topics*, enabled students to collectively identify key themes they wanted to investigate. Through small-group discussions and voting, they selected “Gender Inequalities in Education” as the focus of the lab.

Figure 20 - Outcome of the 'Mapping Differences' Activity conducted in UDNZ

A key component of the lab involved structured role-playing and reflection exercises. In *Mapping of Gender Differences*, students worked in small groups to categorize various educational traits and behaviours as more typical of boys or girls. Using pre-written statements such as “They regularly do their homework” and “They are under a lot of stress because of school,” students placed responses into gender categories and discussed their reasoning. This led to deeper conversations about gender stereotypes and expectations in education. Facilitators noted that participants became more aware of how social norms shape perceptions of academic performance and behaviour.

Another exercise, *Privilege Walk*, encouraged students to reflect on how social identity influences educational opportunities. Each student assumed a different

role – such as a male student in a vocational school or a female student interested in a traditionally male-dominated field – and responded to prompts about access to resources and support. The activity illustrated how gender and other social factors shape educational experiences, with students recognizing disparities they had not previously considered.

The *5 Whys* method was used to help students critically analyse the root causes of gender inequalities in education. In small groups, participants identified and discussed symptoms of inequality, tracing them back to underlying causes such as societal expectations, family influences, and institutional policies. This activity helped students recognize the interconnected nature of social structures and individual experiences, deepening their understanding of systemic gender disparities. Students also engaged in *Photo Voice*, a visual storytelling method where they collected images representing how gender roles in education have evolved over time. These images became the foundation for discussions on generational changes, social expectations, and the persistence of gender-based barriers in education.

Figure 21 – UDNZ subgroup discussing their chosen photographs during *Photovoice*

To envision possible futures, students participated in a *Future Scenarios* exercise. They developed optimistic, pessimistic, and realistic predictions about gender equality in education, considering factors such as technological advancements, policy changes, and shifting social norms. Most participants expressed hope for

continued progress toward equality, though some acknowledged potential challenges in sustaining change.

As the lab neared its conclusion, students worked in groups to develop initiatives addressing gender inequality. They planned a public forum featuring professionals in non-traditional gender roles, created short videos documenting their experiences in the project, and designed a survey to assess gender perceptions among their peers. These activities allowed students to translate their learning into actions that could raise awareness and promote discussion beyond the CCLAB.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 27 – Methods used during UDNZ lab

Process Step	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Walking debate	Participants position themselves along a continuum from "Completely disagree" to "Completely agree" in response to statements about educational inequalities, then discuss their reasoning in a guided conversation.
Onboard	Mapping of the topics	Participants collaborate in small groups to identify and vote on topics related to educational inequalities that are most relevant and interesting to them.
Question	Mapping of gender differences	Participants reflect on and discuss gender differences in education by sorting stereotype-based statements, adding their own perspectives, and engaging in group discussions to analyse biases and experiences.
Question	Sharing of personal perspectives	Participants reflect on and discuss gender differences in education by sharing personal experiences, identifying dominant perspectives in small groups, and presenting key insights to the larger group.
Analyse	Walk of privilege	Participants engage in a role-playing activity to experience how social identities impact educational and life opportunities, fostering awareness and discussion on privilege and inequality.
Analyse	5 whys?	Participants use the "5 Whys" method in small groups to analyse the root causes of gender inequalities in

		education, mapping and discussing symptoms and underlying factors.
Analyse	Performance of theatrical play "Shoe Tongue at the Zagreb Youth Theatre"	Participants attended and engaged with a theatrical performance exploring the pressures of professional sports, dehumanization, and gender roles, using artistic expression to critically examine societal expectations and inequalities.
Examine / Envision	Photovoice	Participants use the photovoice method to visually reflect on changes in life, education, and gender inequalities over time.
Examine / Envision	Future scenarios	Participants analyse current trends and develop pessimistic, optimistic, and realistic future scenarios for gender equality in education.
Act	Sharing of responsibilities	Participants collaboratively plan and take real-world action to address gender inequalities by organizing a public forum, creating videos, and conducting a survey.
Act	Working in groups	Participants worked in small groups to design a survey, prepare questions for a public forum, and plan video content, collaboratively refining their projects through group presentations and discussions.
Evaluation and Reflection	Overview and discussion	Participants shared updates on their tasks, discussed challenges, and collaborated on refining the details of their upcoming event through group feedback and problem-solving.
Evaluation and Reflection	Reflection and closing debate	Participants reflected on their overall experience, sharing insights, challenges, and suggestions for improvement while practicing constructive feedback in group discussion.
Act	Panel Discussion	Participants organized a panel discussion featuring professionals working in non-traditional gender roles, gaining insights into gender-based workplace challenges and using the discussion to create educational videos.

Impact and Key Learnings

Throughout the lab, students demonstrated growth in their ability to critically examine gender inequalities. Many initially viewed disparities as individual challenges rather than systemic issues, but by the final sessions, they recognized

the broader social structures influencing educational experiences. Participants also developed greater openness to different perspectives, particularly through exercises that encouraged them to inhabit alternative viewpoints.

One of the most significant learning moments occurred during the *Privilege Walk*, where students realized how societal structures create different opportunities and limitations. Some expressed surprise at the disadvantages faced by individuals who do not conform to traditional gender expectations, leading to deeper discussions on inclusivity and representation. Students also became more engaged in self-reflection. Activities such as *5 Whys* and *Photo Voice* prompted them to examine their own biases and assumptions about gender roles in education. Many participants reported increased awareness of how societal expectations had influenced their own academic and career choices.

Moving forward, the lab’s outcomes – such as the student-led public forum and video documentation – have the potential to influence broader discussions within the school and dormitory communities. Facilitators observed that the participatory approach encouraged students to take ownership of their learning and to see themselves as active contributors to social change.

While the lab revealed significant progress in students’ understanding of gender issues, it also highlighted areas for further exploration. Some participants expressed interest in continuing discussions on related topics, such as economic inequalities and the intersection of gender with other social factors. Future initiatives could build on this momentum by incorporating interdisciplinary approaches and engaging a wider range of stakeholders.

3.5.3 UDMJ

Table 28 – Details of UDMJ lab

Geographical location	Zagreb, Croatia
Demographic characteristics of participants	A total of 15 female participants, aged 17 to 19, took part in the PAR cycle at the student dormitory “Marija Jambrišak.” The participants were enrolled in various upper secondary educational programs, including

	nursing school, health college, and gymnasium. Most came from smaller towns and villages in continental Croatia. The main reasons for their residence in the student dormitory were the lack of specific upper-secondary programs in their original communities, the pursuit of sports careers tied to opportunities in Zagreb, or aspirations to continue their education in Zagreb.
Number of sessions	8
What is the topic of the cycle?	Do enrolment policies in the transition between lower secondary and upper secondary education ensure equality of opportunity? At the outset of the CCLab, participants expressed concerns that the current enrolment policies were unjust, providing unfair advantages to certain groups of students. However, over the course of the PAR Cycle, most participants shifted their perspectives on the issue.

At the Student Dormitory Marija Jambrišak, 15 girls from various upper secondary programs explored the fairness of current enrolment practices between lower and upper secondary education in Croatia. This transition is particularly significant for students and their families, as it marks the first point of educational differentiation within the system. At the age of 15, students enrol in 3-year, 4-year, or 5-year vocational education and training (VET) programs or gymnasiums. Enrolment procedures are primarily based on achievements from lower secondary education. However, some groups of students receive additional points due to their academic success, sports achievements, socio-economic circumstances, health conditions, or minority status. Most participants, approaching the topic from an individualistic perspective, considered these policy solutions unfair, arguing they increase educational inequalities. Over the course of eight sessions, students engaged in structured debates, role-playing activities, creative exercises, and analyses of educational policies. The lab at SDMJ was also distinguished by participants' engagement with community actors. Ultimately, participants created and organized a small theatre play. All activities fostered critical thinking and self-reflection among the participants.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

Work in this lab started with the presentation of the project and mutual introductions. The working modalities and meeting dynamics were clearly defined. A broader topic of educational inequalities was preliminarily presented. The working part of the first meeting began with the *Walking Debate* method, where participants had the opportunity to express their views on the broader concept of educational inequalities. After that, they had the opportunity to explain their views. The active approach to work from the very beginning was extremely well-received by the participants, and they willingly embraced the *Idea Mapping* process. The work was organized in groups where they discussed various topics they wanted to explore during the lab, falling under the broader topic of educational inequalities. After identifying topics in each group, they submitted their proposals to a common space. At the end of the first round, three topics were identified: gender-based educational differences, differences among students based on their place of residence, and equality in enrolment to upper secondary education. In the second selection round, the participant groups were asked to rank these three topics by assigning the first rank to their top choice. All five groups gave their first rank to the issue of equality in enrolment to upper secondary education. In the discussion, most participants adopted a distinctly individualistic perspective, considering the possibility of granting additional points during enrolment to members of certain groups as unfair and a generator of inequalities. Participants did not adopt a perspective that considers the conditions in which an individual grows up and lives, or the difficulties they face during their education. After the meeting, educators expressed their surprise and even concern with some of the participants' views.

Figure 22 -UDMJ groups during the Onboarding session

The second session began with *Walk of Privileges*, for which roles were prepared in advance where some characters came from privileged environments while others came from more challenging backgrounds. During the exercise, led by the educators, it was clearly demonstrated to CCLab participants that not everyone is in the same position. This visual representation left a strong impression on the participants. In the discussion about the experience, the fact was particularly highlighted that “in real life” they had not had the opportunity to empathize with another’s position. During *Wall of Prejudices*, there was a clear reflection on attitudes and prejudices toward certain groups of students. During this exercise, a particularly negative attitude was expressed toward the Roma minority and children of war veterans (who do not receive additional points for enrolment). In the discussion, one of the educators shared her experience as a child whose father was a war invalid and the fact that her childhood and upbringing were not the same as other students in her generation. A critical moment occurred when some participants publicly stated that this fact should not have affected her education. Between the second and fourth meetings, participants had the task of studying the normative framework related to high school enrolment. Based on what they read, they were asked to design solutions they believe should be part of the legislative framework and prepare questions for a Q and A session with Iva Milardović Štimac, deputy Head of the Board of Education of the City of Zagreb.

The third meeting was organized outside the student dormitory. To gain a historical perspective related to the status of different groups of students in access to education, participants visited the Croatian School Museum and the exhibition “Lessons from the Past – (Re)forms of Education in Croatia from the Enlightenment to the Digital Age.” The visit was specially organized for the participants, and they were guided through the exhibition by its author, Štefka Batinić. Using historical lenses, participants asked questions about the present and the status of specific groups of students in the past. After the visit, a reflection was organized where participants shared their thoughts on the exhibition and changes in enrolment conditions over time.

The fourth meeting, particularly liked by the participants, was the Q and A session with Iva Milardović Štimac from the City of Zagreb Board of Education. In the open discussion, participants gained insights into the complexities of policy development and implementation. Participants posed questions about the possibilities of

changing educational policy at both city and national levels. The discussion soon became two-sided, with participants sharing their own experiences from the enrolment processes.

Figure 23 - UDMJ Q and A with high level representative from City of Zagreb

Between the fourth and fifth meetings, participants were given a task to create and present optimistic, pessimistic, and realistic scenarios about the possibilities of different education policies on transitions between educational levels. The fifth meeting began with a discussion about the scenarios created by the participants. After this task, different methods of action related to the lab topic were discussed. Some of the proposals included educational activities in elementary schools, a Tik-Tok campaign, and a public forum. Through democratic means, it was decided that a play related to the topic of (in)equality in enrolment to high school would be created for the final part of the work. During the discussion, it was suggested that the *Walk of Privilege* exercise be used as the basis for the play.

The sixth meeting was dedicated to creating the play. Each participant envisioned a character they wanted to be. They gave the character a name and personality. The next task was to individually write a text briefly describing the student and the

family and social environment from which they come. During this meeting, participants read their texts for the first time, acting out their imagined characters. Educators acted as judges in the play while some participants took on the roles of leaders. A short introductory video announcing the competition was also filmed for the play. Participants also planned for costumes best depicting their characters. The seventh meeting was dedicated to rehearsing for the final performance of the play. Details were refined during this meeting, and participants composed a text inviting viewers to reflect on whether everyone is equal in high school enrolment. Unlike their initial positions, the text used in the play advocated for granting additional points during enrolment to more groups. Participants designed posters for the play, which they posted around their dormitory.

The eighth meeting consisted of a public performance of the play "Are We All Equal?" and a forum on educational equality. The performance was attended by 30 viewers who responded positively to the play. In reflection on the entire process, almost all participants reported a complete change of attitudes. They particularly enjoyed the artistic activity they participated in.

Figure 24 - UDMJ Poster for the play "Are We All Equal?"

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 29 - Overview of methods used during UDMJ lab

Process Step	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Walking debate	Participants position themselves along a continuum from "Completely disagree" to "Completely agree" in response to statements about educational inequalities, followed by a guided discussion where they elaborate on their reasoning.
Onboard	Idea mapping	Participants collaboratively identify, discuss, and prioritize topics related to educational inequalities.
Question	Walk of privilege	Through role-playing and observation, participants explore and reflect on how social identities influence opportunities and outcomes, fostering greater awareness of systemic inequalities and society's role in addressing them.
Question	Wall of prejudice	In groups of 3 to 5, participants are invited to share positive and negative stereotypes and prejudices about specific groups of students and their relationship to enrolment policies. Participants then review the work of neighbouring groups. After the group work, participants reconvene to read aloud what has been written, followed by a guided discussion.
Analyse	Policy analyses	Participants were tasked with analysing enrolment policies at both the national level and the level of the City of Zagreb. They presented their views on these policies and proposed alternative policy options.
Analyse	Museum visit	The Croatian School Museum hosted a special session for CCLab participants as part of the exhibition "Lessons from the Past – (Re)forms of Education in Croatia from the Enlightenment to the Digital Age." During a guided tour, participants gained a historical perspective on enrolment policies and were encouraged to examine the topic through both

		present-day and historical lenses. Following the visit, a guided discussion took place, reflecting on the historical trajectories of enrolment policies.
Envision / Examine	Q and A with high official from City of Zagreb Board of Education	A Q and A session with a senior official from the City of Zagreb Board of Education was organized to provide participants with insight into the complexities of policy development and implementation. CCLab participants were encouraged to pose questions about the possibilities of changing educational policy at both the city and national levels.
Envision/ Examine	Policy development	Participants were assigned the task of creating and presenting optimistic, pessimistic, and realistic scenarios related to different education policies on transitions between educational levels.
Act	Theatre play	Participants developed and presented a short theatre play titled "Are We All Equal?" based on the "Walk of Privileges" exercise. They created characters, prepared video materials for the play, and performed it in front of their peers and teachers. After the play, they engaged in a discussion with the audience, reflecting on personal experiences during CCLab.
Reflect	Dynamic chain reflection	Participants participated in a dynamic chain reflection exercise, building on or challenging each other's statements about their experiences, fostering collective insight and discussion.

Impact and Key Learnings

The evaluation of participants and educators indicates that the CCLab conducted at UDMJ was entirely successful. The satisfaction curve of the participants was almost linear, and many expressed their desire to continue working on the topic of educational inequalities, particularly on enrolment into upper secondary education. This outcome was not entirely expected, given the start of the process.

The primary reason for choosing the topic was the perception of inequalities from an individualistic perspective. Nearly all participants initially wanted to abolish additional points for certain groups of students in disadvantaged positions or those who had achieved specific successes. By the end of the cycle, all participants

shifted to a completely opposite stance, advocating for expanding the number of groups eligible for additional points during enrolment in secondary schools.

A standout feature of CCLab was the opportunity for participants to influence the choice of the topic they worked on. This fact, which significantly differed from their school and dormitory practices, formed the foundation of their initial motivation to engage and participate. The use of active methods, especially at the beginning, further motivated the participants and made the activity fresh and appealing.

Another distinctive element of this CCLab was the involvement of community stakeholders. The museum visit was well received, with minor reservations about the use of historical perspectives. Direct dialogue with a person responsible for enrolment policies was one of the highlights of the collective work. The fact that someone listened to them was particularly important for the participants. Overall, the CCLab methodology can be significantly enriched by organizing activities within the community.

The final part of the work on the play represented a completely new experience for the students, which had the greatest impact on changing their attitudes. Immersing themselves in characters they had designed themselves demonstrated the power of artistic methods of expression. The fact that they prepared and presented their work to their peers and dormitory staff within a short timeframe filled them with pride. Overall, this represents a highly positive example of using the CCLab methodology.

3.5.4 Institute for Social Research Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged cumulatively by the Institute for Social Research.

Table 30 - Institute for Social Research's KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	45
Participants from underrepresented groups	45
Educators	9
Other stakeholders	10
Researchers-facilitators	8

Number of participants (in final focus group)	36
Number of educators (in final interview)	2
Number of CSOs	0
Number of formal education organizations	0
Number of non-formal education organizations	0

3.6 Ars Electronica (Austria)

Ars Electronica facilitated two labs during PAR Cycle 2 - one titled Open Lab and the other HTL Spengergasse. Reports on both are described below.

3.6.1 Open Lab - create your world

Table 31 - Details of create your world lab

Geographical location	Linz, Austria
Demographic characteristics of participants	12 youth (3 female, 9 male), aged between 14 and 18, coming from diverse backgrounds
Number of sessions	6
What is the topic of the cycle?	The topic of "Envisioning Futures" was already set before talking to the stakeholder. Within this frame they especially pointed to the importance of social impact of technology as well as mental health among youth and how these topics can be imagined differently / critically in the future.

As part of the Ars Electronica Festival 2024 in Linz, Austria, Ars Electronica facilitated a five-day Open Lab for twelve youth participants aged 14 to 18. This lab, connected to the broader festival theme "Hope: Who Will Turn the Tide?", focused on envisioning futures through creative engagement with technology, media, and societal issues. Participants were recruited through the Jugendbegegnungsprojekt, a youth exchange program that invited young people from different cultural institutions across Europe, alongside previous participants of create your world, an existing Ars Electronica youth initiative. The group was diverse in background and experience, with some having prior exposure to the Ars Electronica Festival and others engaging for the first time.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

The Open Lab provided structured sessions where participants explored the intersection of technology, democracy, and media production. An onboarding session introduced the participants to the lab and each other, using the icebreaker *Two Truths - One Lie*. While this activity aimed to establish a comfortable

environment, facilitators observed that some participants were hesitant to share, indicating the need for additional community-building exercises.

Once on-site at the festival, the participants engaged in hands-on workshops and discussions. A technical introduction to podcast recording was led by FM4, a national youth radio station, where students familiarized themselves with recording equipment and editing software. This session was particularly effective in increasing engagement, as participants actively tested the tools and conducted initial recordings. Later, a podcast producer guided them through a Q&A session, where they discussed storytelling techniques and the role of media in shaping public discourse.

A guided tour through the Ars Electronica Center, known as the "Museum of the Future," exposed participants to exhibits on AI, food production, and material sciences. This visit prompted discussions about global inequalities and technological ethics, with some participants questioning who has access to emerging technologies and how they shape future societies. A second guided tour through the festival's main venue, Postcity, focused on the theme "Hope: Who Will Turn the Tide?" and further encouraged participants to reflect on the intersection of activism and artistic expression.

Throughout the lab, facilitators observed that while the group was generally open to discussing new ideas, they struggled with certain aspects of self-reflection and abstract thinking. During a *Yes/No Icebreaker* activity, which asked participants to physically position themselves in the room according to their stance on various social questions, some individuals were hesitant to take strong positions. Differences in language proficiency also played a role, as English was the working language of the program, and not all participants were equally confident in expressing their thoughts outside of their native language.

Despite these challenges, critical moments of engagement emerged. During the *Future Exhibition* session, participants examined artistic depictions of future societies from different historical periods. As they categorized ideas into themes like nature, education, and governance, some noted the lack of diverse perspectives in these imagined futures. This helped students reflect on the role of dominant cultural narratives in shaping visions of progress.

Figure 25 - Youth at the Future Exhibition

In the final days of the Open Lab, youth worked independently or in small groups to develop their own podcast episodes. They conducted interviews with festival visitors, artists, and each other, exploring topics related to future technologies, societal challenges, and personal reflections on the festival's themes. Some experimented with creative audio techniques, such as soundscapes and AI-generated content, to enhance their storytelling.

Figure 26 - Podcast recording

Although energy levels waned by the fourth day, most participants remained committed to completing their projects. Some questioned the potential impact of their work, wondering how widely their podcasts would be heard. This led to a discussion about media accessibility and the challenges of amplifying youth voices in broader public discourse. Ultimately, the podcasts were uploaded to the [Frischer Wind channel](#), a platform created by previous PAR cycle participants, ensuring their work would have a digital presence beyond the festival.

Impact and Key Learnings

The Open Lab demonstrated how participatory media production can be a tool for critical engagement, enabling youth to explore emerging technologies while reflecting on issues of access, agency, and representation. Through guided tours and workshops, participants engaged in conversations about global inequalities in technological development and how cultural perspectives influence visions of the future.

However, challenges such as language barriers and varying levels of confidence limited deeper discussion and self-reflection. While participants showed interest in speculative futures, they often needed prompting to critically analyse dominant narratives. Facilitators noted that future iterations could benefit from more structured reflection to support critical inquiry.

Despite these hurdles, the lab had a meaningful impact. It created a space for creative experimentation and dialogue, empowering young people to not only imagine alternative futures but also recognize themselves as active contributors to shaping them.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 32 - Overview of methods used during create your world lab

Process Step	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Two Truths, One Lie	The "Two Truths and a Lie" icebreaker activity encourages participants to share three personal

		statements about themselves – two true and one false – while others try to identify the false statement, helping people get to know each other.
Onboard	Competencies - Open discussion	In an online onboarding session, participants were introduced to competencies through a presentation, voted on which they considered most important via chat, and engaged in a self-assessment discussion, though some found the abstract nature of the competencies and lack of objective measurement criteria challenging.
Onboard	Peer-Mentoring	A participant from a previous cycle demonstrated the post-production software Descript through a brief presentation and Q&A session, aiming to familiarize others with the tool and share insights about the podcasting process.
Onboard	Workshop: Technical intro to recording equipment and intro to Descript by radio station FM4	In this hands-on technical workshop, participants learned to use recording equipment and audio software through practical exercises including test interviews and sound recording at a festival, under the guidance of a radio station facilitator.
Question	Q&A: Intro to Podcasting by Podcast Producer	A podcast producer led an interactive session combining open discussion about participants' podcast experiences with professional insights and practical planning tools to help them understand and prepare for creating their own podcasts.
Question / Analyse	Guided Tour through Ars Electronica Center	An educational tour through the Ars Electronica Center exposed participants to futuristic exhibits on food, music, materials, and AI/robotics to encourage creative thinking about societal changes.
Question	Yes/No Icebreaker	In this physical positioning activity, participants respond to questions about democracy and social issues by moving to designated "yes" or "no" areas of the room, followed by group discussion of their choices.
Envision	Future Exhibition	Through analysing historical artistic depictions of the future, participants identify and reflect on past predictions, societal concerns, and underlying biases

		while clustering common themes to better understand how different eras envisioned change.
Question / Analyse	Guided Tour through the AE Festival 24	A guided tour through the festival venue explores the connection between artistic expression and activism, highlighting how art and technology can influence society.
Analyse	Recording Icebreaker	A multilingual exercise where participants share, translate, and record tongue twisters to become more comfortable with recording equipment and explore different languages.
Act	Open Podcastlab	A self-directed group activity where participants apply research, creativity, and critical understanding to develop podcast episodes, fostering openness to diverse perspectives with facilitator support as needed.
Act	Recording & editing podcasts / Open Lab	A collaborative podcast development session where participants independently form groups, research topics, and apply creativity, critical thinking, and openness to diverse perspectives, with facilitator support.
Act	Publishing Podcasts	A hands-on activity where participants take ownership of their work by independently uploading their podcast episodes to a shared Spotify channel.

3.6.2 HTL Spengergasse

Table 33 - Details of HTL Spengergasse lab

Geographical location	Vienna, Austria
Demographic characteristics of participants	29 participants; 10 male, 19 female; aged 17 – 18; from diverse backgrounds
Number of sessions	5
What is the topic of the cycle?	The most relevant topics identified by the group through a pre-workshop online survey (via Google Forms) were human rights and discrimination as well as climate change.

At HTL Spengergasse in Vienna, Austria, a group of 29 students participated in a Critical ChangeLab as part of their media projects curriculum. The lab centred on the theme of *Envisioning Futures* and encouraged students to explore how their voices could influence societal change. Over the course of five sessions, students engaged in discussions, interviews, and creative exercises that culminated in the production of podcasts addressing topics of personal and social significance.

The lab aimed to integrate democratic principles, research skills, and creative expression. While attendance was mandatory, students appeared interested in social issues, particularly human rights and climate change, as indicated in a pre-workshop survey. The group had prior experience working collaboratively on socially engaged projects, including a partnership with an NGO focused on homelessness awareness. This background contributed to a strong foundation for their engagement in the research process.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

The first session introduced the CCLAB methodology and the principles of Participatory Action Research. Facilitators explained the collaborative approach of research, highlighting how it allows young people to investigate issues relevant to their lives. A Mentimeter survey engaged students in identifying personal frustrations and aspirations, shaping the focus of their research.

However, participation was initially limited. Facilitators noted that students remained largely silent during discussions, despite efforts to encourage engagement. While some students demonstrated interest, overall interaction was minimal.

A significant turning point in the project came with the *Archive of Voices* activity, where students conducted interviews with strangers on Vienna's streets. Equipped with recording tools, they posed questions about societal challenges, democracy, and the future. This real-world engagement dramatically increased participation and motivation.

Figure 27 - A word cloud from the Archive of Voices activity

Students spoke with people with diverse perspectives, with notable interviews including a university student discussing the pressures of academic life and a woman in a mechanical workshop sharing her experiences of workplace sexism. These encounters prompted deep discussions in class, particularly regarding gender inequality and mental health in education.

Following the interviews, students engaged in a *Future Exhibition* exercise, where they examined historical depictions of the future and reflected on how societal visions have evolved. They categorized their findings into key themes such as technology, governance, and social justice. While students were highly engaged in identifying societal challenges, they struggled to propose concrete solutions. Many framed problems—such as human rights violations and government control—as issues happening outside Europe, reflecting a Eurocentric perspective. Facilitators encouraged broader critical reflection, but this remained a challenge throughout the sessions.

In the *Femplak* exercise, inspired by a feminist activist initiative, students created slogans summarizing their research themes. These included phrases such as “Human Rights, Human Wrong” and were later displayed around the school. The creative process engaged students deeply, reinforcing the connection between research and advocacy.

Figure 28 - The Femplak activity

In the final sessions, students worked in groups to develop podcast episodes based on their research. Topics included AI in social media, gender and ability, domestic violence, and systemic issues. While the students were confident in using recording equipment, some hesitated to express personal views publicly. One group working on a human rights episode initially refused to have their podcast played in class, though they later agreed to share it but chose to leave the room during playback. Their episode discussed fears within the LGBTQ+ community regarding the rise of the far-right FPÖ party, illustrating the personal and sometimes vulnerable nature of the topics explored.

The *Yes/No Icebreaker* was particularly effective in prompting debate about democracy, voting rights, and civic responsibility. Some students physically switched sides mid-discussion, reconsidering their perspectives as they listened to

classmates' arguments. This moment shows the potential of structured debate in fostering critical engagement with societal issues.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 34 - Overview of methods used during HTL Spengergasse lab

Process Step	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Introduction to the Critical Change Lab	This activity introduces participants to the concept of a CCLAB, familiarizes them with the methodology of Participatory Action Research, and engages them in discussions by presenting key concepts, survey insights, and collaborative problem-solving approaches.
Question	Initial Survey via Mentimeter	This activity uses Mentimeter to engage participants in sharing their everyday concerns and future visions, shaping workshop discussions based on their input.
Question	Archive of Voices: Field Recordings	This activity immerses students in real-world learning by conducting street interviews, fostering critical thinking, communication skills, and engagement with diverse perspectives on societal issues.
Analyse	Reflection on the Voice Archive Recordings	This activity encourages students to reflect on their street interviews, analyse response patterns using word clouds, and engage in a discussion about the insights and impact of their interactions.
Envision	Envision Futures - Future Exhibition	This activity engages students in reflecting on historical visions of the future, organizing their thoughts into thematic groups, and selecting topics for their upcoming podcast project.
Envision	Femplak	This activity allows students to translate their abstract ideas into activist messages by creating and displaying slogans related to their podcast themes.
Analyse	Yes/No Icebreaker	In this physical positioning activity, participants respond to questions about democracy and social issues by moving to designated "yes" or "no" areas of the room, followed by group discussion on their choices.

Act	Coming up with a concept (with peer support)	This activity encourages students to express their opinions creatively, identify societal tensions affecting their daily lives, and collaboratively explore potential solutions with peer support.
Act	Recording	This activity allows students to publicly express their opinions and creatively explore solutions to societal issues by recording their ideas.
Act	Podcast Recording and Postproduction	This activity enhances collaboration, critical thinking, and creativity as students finalize their podcasts through recording, editing, and designing cover graphics
Reflect	Podcast Listening and Reflection	This activity promotes self-awareness, openness to diverse perspectives, and transformative agency by having students listen to their recorded podcasts, reflect on their experiences, and engage in peer discussions on socio-political themes.

Impact and Key Learnings

The lab offered valuable insights into both the potential and the challenges of fostering research-based inquiry and creative expression among students. One key learning was the importance of built-in flexibility: time constraints initially hindered students' ability to refine their podcasts, prompting facilitators to extend the submission deadline. This underscored the need to anticipate the iterative nature of creative work in future planning. Another important takeaway was the necessity of supporting collaborative decision-making. Some groups struggled with reaching consensus quickly, revealing a need for more structured guidance on teamwork dynamics and time management.

The lab also highlighted the significance of creating safe spaces for sensitive conversations. While some students critically engaged with difficult topics, others were less open, with one dismissing a peer's podcast as "too emotional." This pointed to the need for more explicit teaching around empathy, respectful dialogue, and engaging with marginalized perspectives.

Ultimately, the lab demonstrated that with the right scaffolding, students can thoughtfully navigate complex societal issues and express their insights through media. Their podcast episodes - showcased at the Oulu Loves Me exhibition - not

only amplified their voices but also displayed youth potential in shaping public discourse and practicing digital citizenship.

3.6.3 Ars Electronica Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged cumulatively between Ars Electronica’s CCLABs.

Table 35 – Ars Electronica’s KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	41
Participants from underrepresented groups	26
Educators	3
Other stakeholders	6
Researchers-facilitators	3
Number of participants (in final focus group)	27
Number of educators (in final interview)	1
Number of CSOs	2
Number of formal education organizations	1
Number of non-formal education organizations	1

3.7 Kersnikova (Slovenia)

3.7.1 Center Rog

Table 36 - Details of Center Rog lab

Geographical location	Ljubljana, Slovenia
Demographic characteristics of participants	31 students; 80% male; aged 11-15
Number of sessions	8
What is the topic of the cycle?	Humanist topics related to STEAM – technological literacy, digital governance, democratic decision making and civic engagement

In Ljubljana, at the community hub Center Rog, a group of students gathered every Friday evening for an eight-week CCLAB. Designed by Zavod Kersnikova in collaboration with Društvo Rampa, this lab aimed to explore the intersections of democracy and technology. The participants were a mix of boys and girls aged 11 to 15; the majority came from well-educated or middle-class backgrounds, with some participants from underrepresented groups, yet many had never deeply considered how technology shapes governance and civic engagement. Over two months, they engaged in hands-on learning, debates, and creative problem-solving, discovering new ways to approach democratic decision-making and technological literacy.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

At Center Rog, participants engaged in democratic processes by collectively selecting a topic, building a server to explore digital infrastructure, and envisioning its community applications. They further developed their understanding through practical engagement with open-source principles and a simulation-based exercise in urban planning and decision-making. The lab began with introductory exercises where participants shared their interests and experiences. This helped facilitators tailor the sessions to the group’s needs and created an open space for discussion. The early sessions focused on defining democracy and its role in

everyday life, encouraging participants to reflect on decision-making and fairness in both digital and real-world contexts. Activities such as structured debates allowed participants to express opinions on digital governance and regulation. Using the *Row of Opinion* method, they positioned themselves physically in the space to represent their stance on topics related to technology's role in governance and everyday decision-making.

The program introduced participants to open-source technologies, alternative digital systems, and discussions on civic technology. Through interactive demonstrations, students explored different operating systems and considered the implications of digital autonomy. In one interactive activity they turned an old computer into a server and used it to collaborate on a graphic design. They also examined how technology can facilitate or hinder democratic engagement.

One of the interactive elements involved a simulation game where participants experimented with managing public infrastructure. The activity highlighted challenges in governance, decision-making, and the balance between efficiency and accessibility in public services.

Figure 29 - Participants engaging in the simulation game (left) and live data from the server (right)

In the final sessions, participants reflected on their learning through creative storytelling and discussions. They revisited key themes, such as the intersection of technology and governance, and shared their perspectives on how digital tools can shape democratic participation.

Figure 30 – The *Interactive Debate Machine* where participants vote for topics and opinions event

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 37 – Overview of methods used during Center Rog lab

Process Step	Activity or Method	Description
Onboarding	Present Your Passion	This method helps participants develop public speaking skills by having them draw and present something they're passionate about, followed by exchanging and discussing their passions with others.
Onboarding	Field Visit - Center Rog makerspace	In this activity, participants and mentors visited the Center Rog makerspace where they were encouraged to engage with the makerspace manager about interesting equipment and possibilities.
Onboarding	Talking About Talking	In this activity the participants were asked to share how they felt when talking about the things they are passionate about and compare this to other experiences of talking in public. This activity prepared the group for

		further discussions by providing a safe environment for sharing opinion.
Question	'What Bothers Me The Most' Brainstorm	This activity encourages participants to examine and document their dissatisfactions with various aspects of life, from school to global issues, helping them identify areas for potential change or improvement.
Question	'Why Does This Bother Me And What About The Others?'	This activity encourages participants to reflect on their choices and better understand the problem by looking at it from other angles. By asking themselves 'What about the others?' participants begin to develop a sense of community in relation to the individual.
Analyse	Finding the Common Issue	Through group collaboration, participants identify common challenges among their individual concerns and democratically select the top problem their openlab will address.
Envision / Examine	Use of open-source graphical design tools	This activity introduces participants to basic graphic design software through demonstration and hands-on practice of creating their own designs.
Envision / Examine	Command Line Intro	This activity introduces participants to essential command line navigation through hands-on practice with basic terminal commands.
Envision / Examine	SFTP (Secure File Transfer Protocol) Intro	This activity teaches participants how to securely transfer files between computers by demonstrating and practicing the SFTP command to upload their pictures to a server.
Envision / Examine	Row of Opinion	This method helps participants form and adjust their opinions by discussing a statement with others and physically moving to show their level of agreement, repeating the process until everyone settles into their final positions.
Envision / Examine	Dabbling with Linux Distros	This activity introduces participants to Linux, guiding them to explore its features, install apps, and consider how it can benefit people with limited access to expensive technology.
Envision / Examine	Installing Packages on Linux	This activity teaches participants basic command usage by having them install a package via the Linux terminal.

Envision / Examine	Installing and Using XPIPE	This activity familiarizes participants with using a graphical SFTP application by connecting to a server and downloading images they edited in a previous workshop.
Act	OpenTTD	This activity introduces participants to the basics of designing a transportation system by showing them a gameplay video, followed by hands-on experience with the game on their computers.
Act	Interactive Debate Machine	This method enhances participants' discussion skills and willingness to challenge their opinions through an interactive quiz/debate format, where they select topics and use RFID-tagged sticks to vote on questions presented for discussion.
Act	Role Play as Technological Company	In this activity, participants collaborate in groups to create and present their ideas for imaginary revolutionary technologies that could change the world, fostering creativity and critical thinking.
Act	Final Event Brainstorm	In this activity, participants brainstorm and discuss ways to create engaging presentations for a closing event where they will share their work with parents and other workshop participants.
Reflect	Presentation Mapping	In this activity, participants were asked to draw maps of what they did in the workshops and to think about what, if any, changes in their view on the topic occurred.
Reflect	Role Play as Presenters	In this activity, participants explore creative ways to present their workshop experiences to their parents, challenging traditional school methods and addressing the concept of adult centrism.

Impact and Key Learnings

The CCLAB underscored the importance of structured debate, hands-on learning, and critical engagement with digital systems. Facilitators noted that fostering discussion in an open, participatory manner helped participants become more confident in expressing their views and considering different perspectives.

Future iterations could build on this approach by integrating more opportunities for hands-on experimentation, deeper discussions on digital literacy, and extended collaboration between participants and facilitators. In addition, some of the planned activities took longer than expected, leading facilitators to adjust the

programming on the spot. This was at times a result of the technological literacy of the students; some of the activities were perhaps too advanced for their level and thus took longer to complete. The level of student technological literacy needs to be considered and understood to appropriately map activities for the lab.

3.7.2 Kersnikova Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged by Kersnikova.

Table 38 – Kersnikova’s KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	40
Participants from underrepresented groups	20
Educators	4
Other stakeholders	2
Researchers-facilitators	4
Number of participants (in final focus group)	0
Number of educators (in final interview)	0
Number of CSOs	1
Number of formal education organizations	1
Number of non-formal education organizations	2

3.8 Waag Futurelab (Netherlands)

3.8.1 Corderius College

Table 39 - Details of Corderius College lab

Geographical location	Amersfoort, Netherlands
Demographic characteristics of participants	100 participants in total All between 15 and 17 years old All VMBO level, pre-vocational secondary education Diverse backgrounds
Number of sessions	3
What is the topic of the cycle?	Identity, relations, and racism

At Corderius College in Amersfoort, a group of around 70 pre-vocational secondary education (VMBO) students participated in a Critical ChangeLab facilitated by Waag Futurelab. The project was embedded within their final exam year as part of a newly introduced course that integrates cultural, philosophical, and societal learning objectives. Over a series of sessions, the students engaged with topics related to identity, democracy, and creative expression, using interactive methods to provoke discussion and reflection. While the students were not volunteers - participation was mandatory - stakeholders, including philosophy teachers and external facilitators, aimed to foster engagement by incorporating creative and discussion-based activities.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

The lab began with a focus on identity, guided by the Hannah Arendt quote: “We are not born equal, but equality we must organize together”. This statement provided a foundation for discussions on democratic principles and social inclusion. Early activities were intended to provoke thought and elicit personal responses from the students.

One such activity, *Grouppicture to Provoke*, required students to pose for a group photo without explanation. While they initially complied, resistance emerged when the facilitator announced that the photo would be used without their explicit

consent (NB: this was for activity purposes only; the photo was indeed not used without their consent). This led to debates about consent, privacy, and personal agency, reinforcing the connection between individual rights and democratic decision-making. When students were given the opportunity to negotiate, they proposed a solution: they would allow the use of the photo in exchange for payment. This unexpected turn highlighted their intuitive understanding of bargaining power and collective decision-making.

As the sessions progressed, students engaged with [Exactitudes](#), a visual analysis exercise where they examined and categorized street photography. Initially, students struggled to see themselves represented in the images, finding it difficult to associate personal identity with external appearances. Informal conversations emerged, touching on topics such as subcultures, self-expression, and stereotypes. Some comments reflected rigid group distinctions, such as "that one is really gay," while others expressed uncertainty about belonging: "I don't fit in anywhere". The exercise provided a space for students to question and critique social categorization while recognizing the fluidity of identity.

The *Theses* method further challenged students by presenting statements about social issues, including one that read, "Racism is something that is part of it, you can't do anything about it". Unlike earlier discussions where students hesitated to share their thoughts, this statement created an unusual moment of silence in the class. The stillness suggested that the topic resonated deeply, marking an instance of collective reflection. Facilitators noted that while students often struggled with articulating abstract concepts, direct engagement with real-world injustices prompted more meaningful contemplation.

The latter sessions emphasized participatory creation, using artistic and design-based methods to explore identity and democracy. The *Moodboards* activity allowed students to visually represent aspects of their identity through collage, drawing, and mixed media. Unlike previous discussions where participation varied, this exercise saw high engagement, as students expressed themselves through imagery and personal symbolism.

Building on this, the *Making the Costume* session encouraged students to translate abstract ideas into physical form. Working in teams, they designed and constructed

costumes representing social or political statements. Initially, some students resisted the group structure, arguing for the freedom to choose their collaborators. The facilitator responded by asking them to justify their position, prompting students to articulate why group autonomy mattered. They cited increased motivation and the ability to utilize diverse skill sets as key reasons. By negotiating the terms of their participation, students demonstrated an emergent understanding of democratic agency.

Figure 31 - A costume designed by students during the lab

The final presentation of costumes required students to articulate both their creative process and the meaning behind their designs. This exercise encouraged honesty about collaboration, as students reflected on both the successes and difficulties of working together. Some admitted that achieving equal participation had been challenging, while others recognized the value of compromise in shared decision-making.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 40 - Overview of methods used during Corderius College lab

Process Step	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Group picture to provoke	This activity uses a group photo setup to provoke students into recognizing their role in a group, challenging their comfort zones, and leading them to negotiate ownership, consent, and democratic decision-making through collective rulemaking and voting.
Analyse/ Question	Exactitudes	This activity engages students in analysing 'Exactitudes' photos, prompting them to reflect on visual identity, stereotypes, and group belonging while informally discussing social categorization and personal recognition.
Analyse/ Question	Theses	This activity encourages students to analyse and discuss global issues from multiple perspectives by engaging with thought-statements.
Analyse/ Question	Statement examples	This activity engages students in discussing well-known statements from public figures or groups to deepen their understanding of democratic principles, encouraging participation, inclusivity, and respect for diverse opinions.
Envision/Act	Moodboards	This activity encourages students to engage in self-reflection by visualizing their identity through various artistic techniques, helping them assess how their personal experiences shape their worldview and interactions with others.

Analyse/ Question	Statement worksheet	This activity guides students in analysing well-known statements on themes like privacy, equity, racism, and women's rights.
Envision/Act	Get Inspired	This activity encourages students to think creatively and reimagine concepts by creating a Pinterest board with visual inspirations related to a self-generated statement, helping them transform abstract ideas into tangible expressions.
Reflect	Rapid Choices	This activity challenges students to collaboratively design a costume under time constraints while integrating democratic principles into their decision-making process.
Reflect	Critically Reflect	This activity encourages students to reflect on Hannah Arendt's quote about equality, linking their collaborative experiences to democratic principles through discussion and the application of fair decision-making processes.
Envision/Act	Making the Costume	This activity engages students in a collaborative costume design process where they apply democratic principles, express societal or political statements through visual elements, and reflect on group dynamics while using various creative techniques.
Reflect	Presenting the Costume	This activity requires students to present their costume while reflecting honestly on their collaborative process, highlighting both challenges and successes in teamwork and decision-making.

Impact and Key Learnings

Throughout the sessions, the process revealed both challenges and moments of transformation. Many students entered the program viewing school assignments as requirements rather than opportunities for exploration. The facilitators observed that abstract concepts like democracy and agency often felt disconnected from the students' lived experiences. However, when presented with tangible dilemmas – such as negotiating the use of their group photo or deciding on team structures – students demonstrated an understanding of collective action and decision-making.

Despite initial resistance to discussions on identity and belief systems, students displayed curiosity when these themes were tied to personal expression. The visual

and hands-on activities, such as moodboarding and costume-making, generated higher levels of engagement than discussion-based methods. This suggests that creative expression provided an alternative entry point for students who struggled with verbalizing complex ideas. One of the most striking observations came when a discussion on activism unexpectedly resonated with the group. A trainer shared a personal experience of attending a protest, prompting a response from students who had previously remained silent.

Ultimately, the lab displayed the importance of creating spaces where students can negotiate their own participation. By allowing moments of agency - whether through debating group structures or defining the meaning of their own creations - students engaged more authentically with the material.

3.8.2 Waag Futurelab Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged by Waag Futurelab.

Table 41 - Waag Futurelab's KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	74
Participants from underrepresented groups	74
Educators	7
Other stakeholders	2
Researchers-facilitators	1
Number of participants (in final focus group)	3
Number of educators (in final interview)	2
Number of CSOs	2
Number of formal education organizations	1
Number of non-formal education organizations	1

3.9 University of Barcelona (Spain)

The University of Barcelona completed three labs during PAR Cycle 2 – BAU, CAN FABRA, and Vapor Moli. Reports on each lab are described below.

3.9.1 BAU

Table 42 – Details of BAU lab

Geographical location	Barcelona, Spain
Demographic characteristics of participants	26 undergraduate students of the first year of the Grade in Design; 4 boys and 22 girls of 17-18 years old.
Number of sessions	7
What is the topic of the cycle?	The lack of affective responsibility in society. The topic was defined collectively by the group of participants, using vote and debate.

At the BAU College of Arts and Design in Barcelona, a group of first-year undergraduate design students engaged in a Critical ChangeLab to explore the theme of affective responsibility in society. Facilitated as part of their coursework, this lab aimed to foster critical reflection, creativity, and democratic engagement. Over six sessions, participants worked through a series of interactive methods designed to deepen their understanding of the chosen topic while developing key competences in research, critical thinking, and creative expression.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

The lab started with an Ecosocial Issues Cartography exercise, where students responded to the question, "What are you fed up with?". Using sticky notes, they mapped personal and societal concerns, which were then categorized into thematic clusters. Among the dominant themes were sexism, emotional responsibility, misinformation, and climate change. Through a democratic process combining voting and deliberation, the group ultimately chose affective responsibility as their central focus, incorporating elements of gender dynamics, emotional awareness, and societal care structures.

Although sexism received the highest votes initially, the group engaged in open dialogue to reconsider their decision. Many felt that affective responsibility was a lesser-explored yet impactful issue. This moment was significant - not only did it establish their research direction, but it also demonstrated the value of collective reasoning over majority rule. Affective responsibility within the lab was thought of as being aware of the impact of our actions and words on others, assuming that these cause emotions and feelings in the people we relate to. The notion became popular in recent years due to the challenges posed by new forms of social networking.

With the topic set, the next phase focused on collecting and interpreting personal experiences related to affective responsibility. *Dear Data* required students to document emotional interactions throughout the week, which they later translated into visual representations. These data-driven artworks became conversation starters, revealing patterns in emotional expression and social expectations.

Building on these insights, students participated in *Cultural Probe Prototype*, designing interactive research kits to gather further perspectives from their communities. These kits included prompts, observational exercises, and reflective tools aimed at investigating affective responsibility in real-life settings. The responses helped students refine their research focus and recognize how emotional responsibility plays out in different social contexts.

Figure 32 - Prototype of materials to support affective responsibility

As students transitioned from research to creative expression, they faced both conceptual and practical challenges. A pivotal moment occurred during the *Tridimensional Artefact Production* session, where teams worked to materialize their findings through artistic installations. One group, initially planning to use staged photography to depict emotional responsibility, found that their approach felt forced and artificial. After re-evaluating their project, they shifted towards analysing personal photographs that evoked genuine emotions, leading to a richer and more meaningful representation.

Another challenge emerged in group dynamics. Some students struggled with uneven participation, where a few took on more responsibilities while others remained disengaged. This tension led to a discussion about collaborative work ethics, pushing students to navigate conflict resolution and ensure equal

contribution. The facilitators played a key role in guiding these conversations, emphasizing the importance of democratic participation and shared accountability.

In the final stages, students translated their research into tangible interventions. Their projects ranged from interactive installations to community-driven initiatives aimed at raising awareness of emotional responsibility. Some explored the role of digital spaces, proposing online platforms for collective storytelling, while others focused on educational campaigns promoting emotional literacy among younger audiences.

A particularly impactful session involved speculative design. Through guided visualization exercises, students imagined a society where affective responsibility was a core value, reflecting on what systemic changes would be needed to achieve such a future. These reflections informed their final projects, which integrated elements of advocacy, artistic expression, and participatory design.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 43 - Overview of methods used during BAU lab

Process Step	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Ecosocial issues cartography	This activity engages participants in a collaborative brainstorming process where they identify shared concerns, categorize them, and collectively decide on a focal topic for discussion using sticky notes and group voting.
Question / Analyse	Dear Data	This activity involves collecting personal experiences related to the lack of emotional responsibility over a week and transforming the data into a visual pattern through graphic representation.
Question / Analyse	Cultural Probe Prototype	This activity guides teams through a collaborative process of sharing personal data, mapping insights, and designing a participatory research kit to explore a specific issue for their design project.

Question / Analyse	Tridimensional artefact production based on the cultural probe design	This activity involves teams creating a three-dimensional artifact using collected materials to explore their research focus in a multimodal way, translating experiences into a tangible, non-verbal representation.
Envision / Act	Creation of a symbolic territory of creative projects	This activity involves teams exploring an archive of social and creative projects related to affective responsibility, mapping connections to their own work, and investigating local initiatives to foster collaboration and deepen understanding.
Envision and Act	Guided visualisation	The activity focuses on envisioning a society with greater emotional responsibility and identifying the effective changes needed to achieve it through guided visualization and group collaboration.
Reflect	Creation of Voices of Youths Videos	Participants were encouraged to create a 1-minute video for social media sharing their experience during the CCLAB in a free format, using their own mobile phones.

Impact and Key Learnings

The research process showed how affective responsibility extends beyond individual interactions and into broader social structures. Students began recognizing that emotional responsibility is not just about interpersonal relationships but also about societal systems that encourage or hinder care and accountability. Many reflected on their personal biases and assumptions, realizing how deeply ingrained cultural norms shape expectations of emotional labour and responsibility.

The process of democratic decision-making was another important learning. The shift from simple voting to consensus-building demonstrated that collective reasoning encourages richer, more inclusive discussions. However, it also presented challenges, as not all participants initially felt comfortable voicing their opinions. Over time, they gained confidence in navigating disagreements and finding common ground, a skill that will serve them in future collaborative work.

Creativity emerged as a powerful tool for inquiry, allowing students to engage with abstract concepts in an accessible and personal way. While some initially struggled with the ambiguity of the process, they ultimately embraced the iterative nature of research. This shift in mindset was particularly evident in their final projects, which reflected deep engagement with the subject matter rather than a focus on polished outcomes. The experience also highlighted the difficulties of group work. Some students found it challenging to balance responsibilities and ensure equal participation, leading to moments of frustration. However, these difficulties prompted discussions about accountability and teamwork.

As the lab concluded, students expressed a desire to extend their findings beyond the classroom. Some proposed community-based initiatives, while others saw potential for integrating affective responsibility principles into their future design work. This project not only deepened their understanding of emotional responsibility but also provided them with tools to critically engage with social issues through design and research.

3.9.2 Vapor Moli

Table 44 - Details of Vapor Moli lab

Geographical location	Barcelona, Spain
Demographic characteristics of participants	25 secondary students aged 15, with mostly equal gender distribution. All students speak Catalan and Spanish fluently. The majority of them seem to have local (Catalan) family backgrounds but there are some with migrant family backgrounds.
Number of sessions	7
What is the topic of the cycle?	The group was divided into 7 groups; each group defined a different topic: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Animal welfare • Rising rent prices • Racism • Safety in the Barcelona Metro (especially for women)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dirt on the streets of Barcelona • The spatial distribution of their classroom • A school methodologic-program on basic everyday knowledge.
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This lab took place at the Institut Escola Vapor i Molí, a public primary and secondary school located in the district of Sant Andreu, Barcelona. A total of 25 pupils in the fourth year of secondary education aged participated in the lab. This group was selected by three of the school's teachers, who identified the need to implement the CCLAB because the students had not achieved the objectives of a previous activity. In this previous activity, they had to identify an eco-social issue, relate it to an SDG and develop a proposal for transformation (very similar to a CCLAB).

For the choice of theme, the students were organised into seven teams, a division proposed by the teachers. Each team defined its own theme based on their shared concerns and frustrations. The topics selected were the following: animal abuse, rising rents in Barcelona, racism, safety in the Barcelona Metro (with special attention to women), street cleaning, redistribution of space in the classroom and the need to incorporate into the school a programme of everyday-life practical skills (such as first aid, sew and DIY).

Critical ChangeLab Summary

During the first session, the researchers proposed to start using creative practices to connect with the topics to be explored in the lab. Based on the question “What are you fed up with?” the participants constructed an *Ecosocial Mapping*, revealing shared concerns. Then, those were transformed into poems, which in turn served to define the research themes for each group. Although some students showed signs of tiredness, others were actively involved, responding to the tasks with quality.

After the selection of the topic by groups, in the third session the researchers tried to encourage creativity as well as facilitate the planning of the project by making it easier for the students to identify the key research needs, questions and answers. The artistic strategy of creating a *3D Collage* was used to create a more practical visualisation of the research process. The outside of the box visually represented the topic, concepts and other relevant elements, while the inside detailed the

methodologies and techniques to be used. However, some students faced difficulties in reflecting on and analysing their projects, suggesting a limited understanding of research as a tool for transformation. This resistance generated tensions, highlighting the need for clearer and more effective communication between facilitators and participants within the framework of participatory action research.

Figure 33 - 3D Collage from the lab

During the fourth session the researchers introduced the *PechaKucha* format to the participants, providing them guidance for the final presentations. From this point on, the facilitators provided individual guidance and feedback to each group. Throughout the sessions, there were significant divisions within the groups, with one or two participants taking on most of the work, while the rest showed little commitment. This situation improved slightly in the last two sessions. In addition, during two sessions, one group moved to another classroom without informing the

facilitators, which impeded the monitoring and guidance of the project. There was also widespread frustration with institutional constraints, such as restricted working space and access to resources such as the 3D printer.

The fifth and sixth sessions were devoted to shaping and materialising the proposals, exploring the intervention spaces, testing the prototypes and preparing the final presentations. Overall, these practical phases were characterised by a significant increase in student participation, engagement and motivation.

The fifth and sixth sessions were used to shape the proposals, materialise them, get to know the intervention spaces, test the prototypes and prepare the final presentation. In general, during these more practical phases there was a greater increase in participation showing increased commitment and motivation

The following table details the types of activities and methods used during the CCLAB sessions, indicating how they align with the stages of the Critical ChangeLab process.

Table 45 - Overview of methods used during Vapor Moli lab

Process Step	Activity or method	Description
Onboarding / Question	Ecosocial cartography	Participants used sticky notes to express their frustrations, grouped similar responses into themes, collaboratively named the topics, and explored possible solutions through discussion and evaluation.
Onboarding / Question	Poem	Participants engaged in creative exercises, using the "exquisite corpse" technique and poetry to transform their notes into thematic narratives, forming an initial picture of their PAR focus, which would guide the next session's inquiry development.
Question / Analyse	3D collage design: the box as a conceptual creation tool	Participants used a cardboard box as a visual tool to represent their research, illustrating key topics and concepts on the outside while detailing methodologies and techniques inside.

Envision	Envision and act. Development of action	Participants engaged in group discussions and oral presentations to share their research progress, refine their problematization, and receive feedback to enhance their work and apply their ideas in practical ways.
Reflect	Reflect – PechaKucha	Participants delivered PechaKucha-style presentations to enhance communication skills, foster collaboration, evaluate project progress, identify improvements, and encourage critical reflection.

Impact and Key Learnings

One key learning from the lab was that initial resistance among participants – stemming from past frustrations, group reshuffling, and a sense of repetition – can be transformed. While the early sessions were marked by disorganisation and low motivation, the lab’s pace, clarity, and action-oriented structure helped shift participants’ perspectives, even if some feelings of helplessness remained.

The emphasis on practical application over long research phases was particularly effective. Participants responded positively to the freedom to choose their own topics and to the question “What are you fed up with?”, which helped ground their work in personal relevance and gave direction to their projects.

Despite this engagement, many participants showed a clear aversion to planning, research, and critical self-reflection – stages they also identified as underdeveloped in their school experience. Their preference for creative and implementation-focused sessions highlighted a disconnect between preferred activities and essential learning processes. Throughout the project, certain structural limits became evident. A lack of material and digital resources, along with unequal task distribution – where women often took on more responsibility – impacted group dynamics and the quality of outcomes. Time constraints were a consistent challenge for all involved.

Nevertheless, participants’ understanding of the social issues they tackled deepened considerably. They developed a greater appreciation for the complexity of these issues and for the role of creative, artistic strategies in exploring and

expressing them. At the same time, the process revealed an ongoing need to strengthen skills in planning, research, collaboration, and communication.

From an educational standpoint, teachers recognised both the strengths and the challenges in the process. While they noted students’ difficulties with reflection and analysis, they valued the creative strategies used and the meaningful exchanges between researchers and participants. They also pointed to the importance of building stronger connections with external organisations and providing more time for group feedback.

3.9.3 CAN FABRA

Table 46 - Details of CAN FABRA lab

Geographical location	Barcelona, Spain
Demographic characteristics of participants	9 participants between 12 and 14 years old who signed up for a maker space activity
Number of sessions	9
What is the topic of the cycle?	The topic of the PAR cycle focused on the lack of interest that people show toward others (humans and non-humans).

The CAN FABRA lab took place as an extracurricular activity in the maker space of the Biblioteca Can Fabra - Ignasi Iglesias, a public library in Barcelona. A total of 9 participants between 12 and 14 years old signed up for the maker space activity; only between 4 and 6 of them regularly attended the CCLAB. The topic of the lab was defined based on the concerns and frustrations expressed by the participants. While discussing what they dislike about the world, several themes emerged, including pollution, injustice, political issues, education, and wasted time. A recurring theme among these concerns was a general lack of interest- - whether in learning, the environment, or others (both human and non-human). This observation led to the definition of the cycle’s central focus: the lack of interest that people show toward others.

This topic includes issues like political negligence, disregard for education, environmental indifference, and social apathy, which were repeatedly mentioned in different forms by the participants.

Critical ChangeLab Summary

In the first session, the facilitators introduced the *Ecosocial Issues Cartography* as a tool to define the topic of the lab. Using the question, “What do you dislike about the world you live in?”, participants generated numerous ideas, writing them individually on post its. However, they struggled to define thematic focuses that were neither too specific (e.g., issues affecting a single individual) nor too broad (e.g., world peace). Ultimately, they decided that the CCLAB would focus on the lack of interest people show toward others, both human and non-human.

Figure 34 - Ecosystem mapping during the lab

To refine and specify this focus, participants were provided with field-diaries and were asked to observe this phenomenon in their daily lives and document their observations in the diary. In the second session, they shared their notes and explored the theme further through image theatre.

Each person selected a scene from their notes and recreated it using the bodies of others as a static image, without speaking. The group then guessed and analysed the scenes, identifying common themes and connections. These ideas were mapped on kraft paper, revealing common concerns related to power structures, abuse of power, disrespect in conversations, prejudice, lack of concentration, phone addiction, avoidance of problems, conformity and the belief that “if everyone does it, my actions don’t matter”. Following this, participants were paired based on thematic affinity.

To further sharpen their research focus, participants engaged in a monster-design activity. Each pair choose a topic and was instructed to imagine a monster that depicted this topic. Specifically, the following topics were selected: lack of concentration, social disengagement and conformity. After a brief introduction to the concept of monsters, they used a template to define their creature’s physical appearance, history, habits, behaviour, activation triggers, ideals, and relationships.

This creative process sparked a debate about agency, particularly the idea that “if everyone does it wrong, nothing changes if you do it right”. The group reflected on how this mindset is common in daily life and discussed its impact. This perception showed the role of conformity and group dynamics in either enabling or blocking social change. It also highlighted a sense of individual powerlessness – the belief that personal efforts cannot bring real change within a complex system. One participant captured this sentiment, stating “one person alone cannot change things”.

During the third session, participants translated their monster designs into 3D models. To prepare for the next session, they were then asked to document instances in which their monster appeared in everyday life over the course of a week. In the fourth session, they shared these notes and were invited to work on collaboratively defining the design of an art intervention aimed at making their identified problem more visible.

These brainstorming sessions proved particularly difficult. Participants struggled to define the problem systemically and to think through its implications and interrelationships. Even more challenging was translating their reflections into

concrete and creative ideas. They found it difficult to imagine solutions beyond the inspirations provided by educators. Many expressed a strong preference for simply executing tasks rather than engaging in critical thinking - one participant even expected to be given specific instructions, such as “build a car that follows a line or avoids obstacles”.

These difficulties persisted into the fifth session, which was also dedicated to defining the project design. Decision-making remained a challenge, as no one wanted to express their opinions. Instead, choices were made through voting without discussion or justification. Moreover, the need to agree on a shared design led to tensions in collaborative work. Each participant remained fixated on their own idea, making it difficult to co-create a unified concept.

To support students in the creative process, educators introduced a more technical, hands-on approach. The following sessions focused on developing technical skills in Arduino and Tinkercad to deepen their common design. This shift significantly increased student engagement, as they expressed a clear preference for making rather than thinking. Currently, students continue working on their project alongside makerspace educators.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with stages of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 47 - Overview of methods used during CAN FABRA lab

Process Step	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard / Question	Ecosocial cartography	Participants wrote their frustrations on sticky notes and placed them on kraft paper. They then grouped similar topics and named them with researchers. Using marks, they indicated their preferred topics, and the final topic was chosen through discussion of the pros and cons of the most marked topics.

Question / Analyse	Field Diaries	Participants document their observations of a chosen phenomenon over one week, using field diaries to collect real-life examples and reflections.
Question / Analyse	Image Theatre	Participants bring their observations to life by recreating selected scenes using their peers' bodies as static images, without speaking. The group then guesses and analyses the scenes, mapping key themes and connections on kraft paper.
Envision	Monster Lab	Participants design a monster that represents their chosen focus. Using a structured template, they define its physical appearance, history, habits, behaviour, activation triggers, ideals, and relationships.
Envision	Monster Evidence Collection	Participants spend a week identifying and documenting real-life instances of their monster, collecting evidence of its presence in their daily experiences.
Envision	Co-Design	Participants collaborate to design an artistic intervention aimed at raising awareness about their chosen social issue, brainstorming and refining ideas collectively.
Act	Construction and Technology Learning	Participants are introduced to various technologies, exploring how they function and how they can be integrated into their project to bring their ideas to life.

Impact and Key Learnings

The CCLAB provided a valuable space for participants to explore the concept of agency and engage in reflecting about social issues. One of the most noticeable impacts was a shift in the way participants interacted with one another. Over time, they collaborated more, showed greater respect for each other, and became more open to listening to and building upon others' ideas. While at the beginning they struggled with teamwork, preferring to work individually and defend their own perspectives, by the end of the process, small but meaningful changes in their group dynamics and communication were evident.

In terms of their understanding of the social issue they explored, there were also subtle yet significant changes. Grounding the topic in their own daily experiences

helped make it more tangible and meaningful to them. This shift allowed participants to relate abstract social problems to their personal realities, fostering a deeper level of engagement.

From an educational perspective, educators from the maker space recognized that although guiding these reflections was challenging, it was both valuable and necessary. Many students initially resisted engaging in critical thinking and discussion, preferring to focus on execution rather than reflection. However, the process reaffirmed the importance of creating spaces for reflection, even when students do not actively seek them.

3.9.4 University of Barcelona Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged by the University of Barcelona across all labs.

Table 48 - University of Barcelona's KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	57
Participants from underrepresented groups	33
Educators	10
Other stakeholders	0
Researchers-facilitators	5
Number of participants (in final focus group)	50
Number of educators (in final interview)	3
Number of CSOs	2
Number of formal education organizations	2
Number of non-formal education organizations	1

3.10 Tactical Tech (Germany, Labs in multiple countries)

Tactical Tech's report follows a different structure as, instead of conducting a Critical ChangeLab themselves, they coordinated labs with nine different external partners. As such, this chapter reflects how partners were onboarded, describes each external lab, and provides cumulative KPIs for the external labs.

External Partner Onboarding

Tactical Tech's onboarding process for external partners was designed to provide clarity and structure for planning and executing ChangeLabs within each external partner's local context. The process began with an onboarding session with representatives from all external labs partners to introduce them to the Critical ChangeLab pedagogical framework, key partnership expectations namely concerning topics, methods and to foster collaboration among partners; following this session, open houses were scheduled, allowing partners to further familiarize themselves with the project framework and seek support from Tactical Tech.

To formalize the partnership, several documents had to be submitted before and after project implementation. These included a detailed sessions timetable outlining planned activities, locations, and participant numbers. A Code of Conduct had to be read and signed before the project began, ensuring alignment with Tactical Tech's ethical and operational standards. Upon completion, partners were required to submit a final report detailing project outcomes.

Partners were responsible for implementing three workshop sessions with a group of young participants aged 11 to 18. These sessions also involved external stakeholders, including four educators and two representatives from civil society organizations. These stakeholders, who could be school administrators, youth centre managers, or representatives from local organizations, contributed to the discussions and helped guide participants. While Tactical Tech provided suggested structures for these sessions, partners were encouraged to adapt and innovate to best suit their local contexts.

To support partners in delivering these sessions, Tactical Tech provided a range of learning resources. A series of recorded videos covered essential topics such as privacy, risk assessment, safeguarding, and impact measurement. These resources helped partners develop a strong foundation in Tactical Tech's approach to digital

literacy and responsible technology use. Partners were expected to review these materials before beginning their sessions to ensure alignment with best practices.

In addition to pedagogical resources, Tactical Tech offered communication and branding materials to maintain consistency across the project. Partners received communication and social media guidelines, branding assets, and recommendations for tracking and monitoring their lab's impact. Logos and other visual materials were provided to ensure clear and professional representation in external communications.

At the end of PAR Cycle 2, Tactical Tech hosted a debrief session with all partners where each had the chance to share the main outcomes of their local lab and provide key insights on changes in perspectives, behaviours and attitudes in their group. In this debrief session partner representatives reflected on methodology, learning and participation levels as well as impact.

Throughout the partnership, Tactical Tech provided ongoing support. Each partner had a primary contact for direct assistance, and additional support was available via dedicated email contacts. Tactical Tech also upheld a strong commitment to data privacy and transparency, and partners were encouraged to review the organization's Data Use Policy for a better understanding of its approach to information security.

External partners were also given a document with workshop structures for their Critical ChangeLabs. While the structures were detailed, external partners were encouraged to adjust and adapt the workshops to best fit their local context. This also includes the methods across external partners within their labs. This document can be found in Annex 2.

3.10.1 External Partner Labs

In this PAR Cycle, nine external partner labs focused on the topic of Influence, Participation, and Technology. The chart below details each lab, followed by a brief overview of how each lab engaged with and adjust the topic based on student input.

Table 49 - Overview of Tactical Tech's external labs

Partner Name	Location	Type of Institution	Number of Youth	Participant Demographics
Sofia Professional School "Knyaginia Evdokia"	Sofia, Bulgaria	Formal education	24	Students aged 14–16, mostly girls, from diverse backgrounds studying for vocational certificates
2nd Farnham Scout	Farnham, Surrey, UK	Non-formal (Scouts, youth org.)	25	10 girls and 15 boys aged 11–14; all attend co-ed secondary schools and are registered scouts.
105 VIERTEL HAMBURG GmbH	Hamburg, Germany	Formal education (school)	23	Grade 8 students (17 boys, 6 girls), mostly from migrant backgrounds, living in socio-economically disadvantaged area.
Televele Media Education Association	Budakeszi, Hungary	Non-formal (scout group)	25	Youth aged 15–17 (18 boys, 7 girls), all scouts; mix of patrol leaders and members, offering peer-led mentorship experiences.
LINKS Foundation	Verzuolo, Cuneo, Italy	Formal education (VET school)	Up to 16/session	14–16-year-olds, 60% male; many from agri-food sector families, some with special educational needs; rural context.
Ciência Viva	Lisbon, Portugal	Formal & informal (school + org)	30	16 girls and 14 boys, aged 12–14; participants from a priority education area; sessions at school and a science centre.
Colegiul Național Costache Negruzzi	Iași, Romania	Formal/public education	30	Aged 15–17; 25 girls, 5 boys; humanities focus; prior engagement in human rights, EU policy, and media literacy.

Faculty of Philosophy, Univ. of Belgrade	Belgrade, Serbia	Formal education	25	17 girls and 8 boys; mix from traffic-technical and law/business schools; aged teens to early 20s.
Teyit	Ankara, Turkey	Non-formal education	21 (average between 3 sessions)	Equal mix of male and female students; aged 15-17

Sofia Professional School "Knyaginia Evdokia" (Bulgaria)

The Critical ChangeLab explored influence and technology with students aged 14-16, analysing influencers, debating influence vs. information, and discussing AI in education, climate change, and social engagement. Students expressed frustrations like, "I am fed up with seeing so many people give up on their dreams." The final advocacy session showcased critical thinking, though some struggled to develop concrete solutions, highlighting the need for continued exploration of citizenship and digital literacy.

2nd Farnham Scouts (England)

This lab examined digital influence, online behaviour, and societal participation with Scouts aged 11-14. Discussions covered invisible influencers, addictive design, and online scams, with participants recognizing social media's impact. An algorithmic storytelling game engaged them, leading to discussions on climate change, cost-of-living, and school stress. The final activities emphasized critical thinking, with observers noting the need for clearer terminology for younger audiences. The project has potential for integration into the Scouts' Digital Citizenship badge.

105 VIERTEL (Germany)

Held at Stadtteilschule Mümmelmannsberg in Hamburg, this lab focused on media influence, disinformation, and social media manipulation. Students analysed tabloid vs. serious journalism, TikTok videos, and emotional triggers in online behaviour. They explored trolls, disinformation campaigns, and scepticism toward mainstream news while trusting YouTubers more. While engagement varied, students acknowledged a heightened awareness of media influence. Educators gained insight into students' challenges, deepening their understanding of structural issues in the school system.

Televéle Media Education Association (Hungary)

Facilitated in Budakeszi, Hungary, this lab addressed media influence, algorithms, and societal participation. Initially hesitant, students became more engaged, reflecting on how algorithms shape content consumption. One remarked, “It’s scary how it keeps showing you stuff you like, but then you lose track of time.” Advocacy projects included a StopSmog campaign and a public transport app. While real-world implementation was challenging, participants recognized their role in shaping society and appreciated working on meaningful tasks.

LINKS Foundation (Italy)

At I.I.S. Umberto I in Verzuolo, Italy, students explored social media influence, activism, and misinformation. They debated digital influence, AI’s role in judgment, and social pressure. The advocacy phase led to symbolic representations of societal issues like war and online hate. Students appreciated being heard as active participants, while facilitators observed increased engagement and critical thinking in discussions about digital citizenship and democracy.

Ciência Viva (Portugal)

This lab engaged students aged 12-14 in discussions on technology’s impact on opinions. They debated influence, noting racism and economic bias as harmful, while a dance challenge promoting COVID-19 precautions was beneficial. Advocacy projects tackled pollution, bullying, and school hygiene, with proposals like a recycling incentive system and a student suggestion box. Educators observed growing confidence in discussing democracy, school rights, and political awareness.

Colegiul Național Costache Negruzzi (Romania)

Students in Iași, Romania, explored influence, misinformation, and civic participation, defining influence as “the ability to shape thoughts, behaviours, and outcomes.” Discussions covered social media algorithms, TikTok, AI, and manipulation. Advocacy efforts targeted misinformation, climate change, and online trends, with students urging society to “research topics before judging.” While confidence in issue analysis grew, translating ideas into actions remained a challenge. The lab concluded with public presentations and school initiatives.

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Figure 35 – Poster produced by students in Romania

Center for Teacher Education and Institute for Pedagogy and Andragogy (Serbia)
 This Belgrade-based lab engaged vocational school students in discussions on influence, digital footprints, and privacy. A lecture on data collection sparked interest, and students debated the dual impact of influence, noting that promoting skincare products “can be good but also harmful.” Topics included discrimination, bullying, and youth participation, leading to advocacy projects like online awareness platforms. While collaboration improved, facilitators recommended smaller groups for future sessions.

Teyit (Turkey)

The Ankara-based lab explored influence, participation, and technology, with students associating influence with manipulation, content creation, and advertising. Algorithmic bias encouraged debate, with differing views on whether AI can be biased. Discussions on civic participation raised concerns about slacktivism. Advocacy projects tackled digital influence, gender inequality, and social intolerance, with one group launching a “Stop Violence, Give Women a Voice”

campaign. Post-session reflections showed increased confidence in collaboration and action.

Figure 36 - Poster produced by teens at Teyit

Key Learnings

While each external partner had specific key takeaways related to their local context, there were shared learnings across the partners. These shared learnings include:

- *Relevance increases engagement and reflection.* When topics were closely tied to students' lives - like peer pressure, TikTok, or disinformation - engagement increased significantly. Real-world connections made abstract ideas more tangible and prompted personal insight, helping students question both what influences them and how they influence others.
- *Participation grows through ownership, not instruction.* Young people were most engaged when they were treated as collaborators and creators, not passive learners. Giving them space to choose topics or shape activities led to deeper investment, greater confidence, and a stronger sense of agency.
- *Influence is easy to understand, participation is more difficult to define.* While students easily understood personal influence, they often struggled to define

what participation in society means. This gap created an opportunity to explore civic roles and link personal actions to broader social impact.

- *Hands-on, low-tech activities increase participation more than digital tools.* Despite the digital nature of the topic, simple tools like pens, post its, and drawing activities proved more engaging than screens. These tactile methods encouraged collaboration, made abstract ideas visual, and worked especially well in varied learning environments.
- *Group size, structure, and environment are critical.* Small, well-facilitated groups created safer spaces for dialogue, creativity, and participation. Large group sessions often led to logistical challenges and less meaningful engagement, especially without enough time or support.
- *Confidence in change-making Increases with practice.* Many students began the process unsure of their ability to make change but ended with a stronger belief in their potential - especially through teamwork. Collective effort helped shift their mindset from passive observation to active problem-solving.

3.10.2 Tactical Tech Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged cumulatively by the external labs coordinated by Tactical Tech.

Table 50 - Tactical Tech's KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	226
Participants from underrepresented groups	107
Educators	39
Other stakeholders	30
Researchers-facilitators	15
Number of participants (in final focus group)	0
Number of educators (in final interview)	0
Number of CSOs	0
Number of formal education organizations	5
Number of non-formal education organizations	4

4. Key Learnings

Many learnings emerged during PAR Cycle 2; this section contains an overview of these learnings both related to establishing and maintaining a Community of Practice as well as the implementation of the PAR Cycle. A full and detailed exploration and analysis of learnings from PAR Cycle 2 is provided in Deliverable 3.1.

4.1 Key Learnings – PAR Cycle Implementation

While each PAR Cycle partner had key learnings specific to their local context, five key learnings emerged from PAR Cycle 2 across partners. These learnings are:

- 1. Young people feel disconnected from democracy and lack a sense of agency**
 Democracy was often seen as remote, limited to voting or political structures, with little relevance to daily life. Group decision-making in schools often felt inequitable, and many young people doubted their power to effect change. This sense of disempowerment discouraged civic engagement and reinforced feelings of futility in the face of large-scale societal problems.
- 2. Education systems rarely provide empowering democratic experiences**
 In educational systems, students encountered few real opportunities to make decisions or influence outcomes. When responsibility was offered, it was often met with low motivation – stemming from scepticism about whether their input truly mattered. Many preferred action over reflection, resisted open-ended thinking, and sought clarity over ambiguity, revealing a need for more supportive structures for democratic learning.
- 3. Imagining alternative futures is difficult but essential**
 A key challenge was the limited capacity of participants to envision transformative solutions beyond their lived experience. While many could critique existing systems, few could articulate meaningful alternatives. There was a strong tendency to stay grounded in immediate, concrete issues, rather than exploring broader or more radical possibilities – indicating the need to cultivate imagination and visioning skills.
- 4. Engagement is strongest when rooted in local and hands-on experiences**
 Students responded more positively to local, tangible issues like pollution or community safety. Abstract or global problems felt too distant, and doom-laden

narratives were demotivating. In contrast, solution-oriented and hopeful messaging fostered a sense of purpose and agency. Participatory fieldwork and observation further deepened connection and understanding.

5. Creative, collaborative methods foster deeper learning and inclusivity

The shift from individual work to collaborative approaches led to greater respect and cooperation. Creative tools – such as zines, podcasts, and hands-on fieldwork – made complex topics more accessible and engaging. These methods supported differing learning styles, encouraged critical reflection, and helped participants better understand power dynamics and inequality in society.

These key learnings are critical to the next iteration of participatory action research and will be built upon during the next cycle, PAR Cycle 3.

4.2 Key Learnings – Community of Practice

The Community of Practice was a critical foundation for the planning, implementation of, and reflection on the Critical ChangeLabs. It served as a space for knowledge exchange, learning, and feedback. As such, it is important for WP2 leaders to continue to reflect upon and improve the CoP as partners move into PAR Cycle 3. Three primary key learnings emerged related to facilitating the CoP, relating to engagement of members and the content of CoP meetings.

1. Active engagement of participants

The first key learning was that engagement from partners is necessary for the CoP to serve its function. In the initial CoP meetings, engagement, dialogue and feedback was low. To increase participation and engagement, a focus was placed on strengthening the relationships of members of the CoP through interactive activities (as opposed to simply presentations) and small group conversations that mixed the members around. Asking more explicit questions, or providing actionable assignments, worked to increase engagement. In addition, WP leaders made it a point to check in with quieter participants, asking if they wanted to contribute to the conversation. These tactics proved successful, and the CoP became more engaged and interactive.

2. Gathering feedback

The second key learning relates to the content of the CoP meetings. The first few meetings, due to the timing of the CoP start and needs of other WP leads, often consisted of presentations from WP leads and a request for feedback. While this is valuable, and the CoP can serve as a space for engagement between PAR Cycle partners and WP leaders, it was observed that a presentation and then request for feedback often did not solicit enough feedback or input. As a result, the format of requests for feedback and input was adjusted, creating exercises and workshops to solicit input and feedback from partners.

An example of this relates to the Critical ChangeLab Educators Handbook, which will be delivered later in the project. To ensure that partner input, ideas, and perspectives are included, WP2 leads briefly presented a proposed structure for the handbook, and then instead of asking for feedback, conducted an interactive workshop on Miro where partners worked in small groups to provide feedback on the proposed structure as well as generate ideas for two key components of the handbook - tailoring activities to local context and conflict resolution strategies. As a result of the interactive nature, and the small group environment, the meeting was productive and generative as well as allowed partners to have a strong voice in shaping the handbook.

Figure 37 - Miro board exercise on the Critical ChangeLab Educators Handbook

3. Sharing and detailing of methods

Finally, it was important that the content of the CoP served the needs of the partners. A section was added to the shared partner Miro board where partners can request meeting topics, or list areas where they might need help or feedback. One example of this related to methods; there was a desire among partners to learn more about methods used in the ChangeLab - what methods work well and why (and conversely, what may have not worked so well). As a result of this request, an interactive methods workshop was conducted, focused on the sharing and detailing of methods that can be implemented within the ChangeLabs.

The CoP was not without its challenges. It was difficult for external stakeholders to attend these meetings, and they were very rarely present; logistic scheduling is always challenging within both formal and informal environments. It is therefore critical as the project moves into its final PAR Cycle to consider how the CoP might be reconfigured beyond the time limits of the project. Furthermore, the CoP will be examining how the learnings of the CoP, including the opportunities and challenges of implementing and facilitating labs, can be not only documented, but can shape the approach of and feed into project outputs like the MOOC (Massive Open Online Course) and the CCL Educator's Handbook.

Overall, the CoP serves as a strong foundation for knowledge sharing and learning among partners. By focusing on small improvements related to engaging members in meetings and ensuring that content is well structured to support partners, the CoP will continue to serve as a critical space for growth in the project as partners moved into PAR Cycle 3.

5. Conclusion

PAR Cycle 2 has provided valuable insights into the practical application of participatory action research in fostering democratic engagement through creative and narrative practices. The implementation of Critical ChangeLabs in varying local contexts has highlighted both the strengths and challenges of engaging young people in democratic processes. By refining methodologies and constructing a Community of Practice, this cycle has strengthened the foundation for meaningful participation and co-creation in democratic education.

A key takeaway from this cycle is the importance of adaptability in implementing the Critical ChangeLab framework across diverse educational and social contexts, including both formal and informal settings. The findings suggest that young people often view democracy as distant and inaccessible, yet when democratic principles are applied to local and personally relevant issues, engagement significantly increases. Participatory research and creative methodologies, such as role-playing, storytelling, speculative design, and interactive theatre, have proven to be effective in shifting perceptions and generating a sense of agency among participants.

Furthermore, the Community of Practice has played a crucial role in supporting partners through workshops, knowledge-sharing, and iterative feedback touchpoints. The evolution of the CoP demonstrates that ongoing dialogue and collective problem-solving are essential for refining approaches to democratic education. The participatory structure of the CoP has allowed partners to share best practices, address implementation challenges, and co-develop strategies that enhance the sustainability and impact of the Critical ChangeLabs.

PAR Cycle 2 has also shown the importance of addressing systemic barriers to democratic engagement. Several key challenges emerged, including the hesitancy of young participants to feel agency within democratic processes, difficulties in translating abstract discussions into tangible action, and disparities in access to resources and institutional support. However, the iterative nature of the Critical ChangeLab process has enabled partners to identify solutions and adjustments that will be integrated into the upcoming PAR Cycle 3.

Looking ahead, the insights gained from this cycle will inform refinements to methodologies, further the capacity of the CoP, and strengthen partnerships with educators, civic organizations, and policymakers. By maintaining a commitment to adaptability, co-creation, and critical reflection, the Critical ChangeLab project will continue to work toward resilient and participatory democratic processes, ensuring that young people are not just passive recipients of democratic education but active contributors to its transformation.

Annex 1 – Critical ChangeLab PAR Cycle 2 Partner Plans

This annex contains the PAR Cycle 2 plans developed by each partner. Tactical Tech’s plan is different from the other partners as they coordinated efforts of external partners that were conducting CCLABs.

Trinity College Dublin PAR Cycle 2 Plan

Cross Care

Researchers at Trinity College Dublin will work with youth workers in an Irish charity, CrossCare, to deliver a Critical ChangeLab with one of their youth groups. The CCLABs will take place over September–October 2024 and will focus on climate change, sustainability, and their local community.

PAR Cycle Background and Introduction

Trinity College Dublin

The Critical ChangeLab Ireland, led by Trinity College Dublin, is undertaken by the School of Education’s Science & Society Research Group and the Trinity Long Room Hub’s Democracy Forum. The research team brings expertise in education, science, arts and the humanities to this project, and promotes interdisciplinarity in its implementation. Through Critical ChangeLab Ireland, we are interested in creating spaces to partner with youth to imagine futures, explore new technologies, foster creative expression, and reinvigorate democracy.

CrossCare Ireland – partner organisation and local context

Crosscare is a prominent provider of youth services within the Archdiocese of Dublin, directly supporting youth work across 10 local services and aiding voluntary efforts in Dublin City and County, County Wicklow, and parts of County Kildare. Its mission focuses on fostering a compassionate and Christian approach to youth work, encouraging young people to engage fully in society and the church. Guided by its core values of Love, Respect, and Excellence, Crosscare emphasises personal

responsibility in upholding these principles. With a legacy spanning over 80 years, Crosscare is committed to adapting to evolving social and economic challenges, ensuring support for those most in need in the community.

The TCD team are working with a youth group based in Arklow in county Wicklow, a coastal town in the Greater Dublin Area. The youth group are interested in climate change and sustainability and have completed projects on local marine ecosystems and climate change in the past. This programme, working towards the Youth Assembly on Climate Change in October.

Theme of CCLAB/CrossCare programme

The focus of this Critical ChangeLab/CrossCare programme is on environmental or climate change issues in their local area. The group are organising a Youth Assembly on Climate Change for youth groups in their region in October 2024, so the Critical ChangeLab programme will work towards that action in their area. Using creative and narrative methods to interrogate their topic the programme will work towards the aims outlined below.

Aims of CCLAB

This Critical ChangeLab aims to:

1. To support young people to act on local issues that matter to them.
2. To implement a YPAR Cycle that encourages youth to generate and use research in their own analysis through quantitative surveys.
3. Strengthen democratic systems through civic participation.

Research Questions

Our research questions for this Critical ChangeLab are

1. How do Wicklow youth respond to/engage with local climate policies?
2. Is the Critical ChangeLab method successful in promoting/fostering democratic competences/active participation?
3. How do youth display the development of critical literacies throughout the programme?
4. Is there evidence of using the past to envision the future or inform the present?

Stakeholders & target audiences

This is an overview of the general stakeholders that are to be involved over the course of the project. The stakeholders that are made **bold** are also considered the target audience for the main objectives of the PAR Cycle.

- Stakeholder 1: **youth (aged 11-18) who avail of CrossCare youth services**
- Stakeholder 2: youth workers employed by CrossCare (1-2 x educators, 1 x CSO)
- Stakeholder 3: local guest speaker (TBC) (1 x educator, possibly 1 x CSO)
- Stakeholder 4: Science & Society Research group, Trinity College Dublin (approx. 6 x educators)
- Stakeholder 5: NYCI (1 x CSO, feeding into NYCI One World Week)
- Stakeholder 6: scientist/researcher (water quality, 1 x educator)

PAR Cycle Objectives

Key Concepts

Democratic practice & citizenship (understanding)

Challenge

The challenge in engaging with ideas and issues around democratic practice and citizenship is to help participants to move beyond thinking about 'democracy' solely in terms of governance, voting, and the judiciary.

PAR Cycle Mission

To foster meaningful discussion and action on the links between democratic practice, citizenship, and participation, and how everyone can engage in reinvigorating democracy through their everyday actions.

Recognizing conflict & contradictions in democratic systems (identifying)

Challenge

To identify a local issue (linked to a larger global issue) over which the participants can exert meaningful influence and to clearly identify the links between that issue and contradictions in democratic systems.

PAR Cycle Mission

To encourage participants to identify a range of issues, on local, national, and global levels, and to facilitate activities that will enable them to work together to identify a local issue that they can act on which interests them and to articulate the contradictions in democratic systems that feed into that issue.

Interrogating cultural construction, social, political context and societal transformation (deconstructing)

Challenge

To challenge traditional assumptions and normative expectations with participants through engaging in difficult discussions and giving space to perspectives and opinions that might differ from their own. Another major challenge here is to meaningfully engage with discussions of socio-political issues and power structures in the limited time we have.

PAR Cycle Mission

To design activities and lesson plans that are layered, complex, and engaging. By encouraging participants to consider these issues throughout the programme the discussion and activities at this stage should already be informed by their analysis and some reflection.

Alternative futures (activating change)

Challenge

To affect meaningful action and envision alternative futures with participants in a creative and innovative way in a limited amount of time.

PAR Cycle Mission

To implement a programme of activities which will empower participants to meaningfully envision alternative futures for their community and to act towards their implementation. The action may be big or small, but it's important that participants feel as though their action had impact.

Please rate the importance of each concept within your PAR Cycle, marking one value per row (1 is lowest, 5 is highest)

	1	2	3	4	5
<i>Democratic practice & citizenship</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

<i>Recognizing conflict & contradictions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Interrogating constructions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Alternative futures</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Outcomes

Outcome 1: Youth Assembly on Climate Change.

A Youth Assembly on Climate Change for CCLAB participants and invited members of other local youth clubs in Co Wicklow. The Youth Assembly will take place on the last week of October, and the form will be defined by the CCLAB participants. This event will be the first such event that this youth group have organised and will produce a response from a varied group of Wicklow Youth to local policies and inform future youth climate action projects in the local area. A Youth Assembly is a platform for young people to raise issues, discuss solutions and oversee projects that will create positive change for the wider community.

Outcome 2: Wicklow Youth Response to Climate Change Policies.

A collective response from the youth of CrossCare Wicklow, YOUTH GROUP 2, YOUTH GROUP 3, ETC., will be produced from the Youth Assembly. This might take the form of a manifesto, a pact, a letter to local authorities, etc. The form of the response will be determined by the youth. The priorities set out in their response will inform the youth work and youth climate action projects undertaken by the participating organisations in the next 12 months and a letter or petition may be prepared to be presented to the local authorities.

Outcome 3: Students engage in and apply democratic principles in the decision-making and organisation processes around the intended outputs. Their actions will be examples of everyday democracy and will strengthen their participation in their local communities. This will be tracked through observational field notes and the rubric provided by the team at University of Barcelona, and will be an aspect that will be considered when evaluating the programme as a whole.

Plan and Activities

Action plan

In this PAR Cycle we will engage participants in a five-session Critical ChangeLab programme between 26 August and 29 October, and a follow-up reflection session on 23 November. We will work with the youth to research issues related to climate action, climate justice, and social justice in their local area and foster critical literacies through artistic methods. We will work with the youth towards a Youth Assembly on Climate Change that they will organise and host for youth from their own town and neighbouring towns in Co Wicklow. From this Youth Assembly we will produce a collective response to local plans and policies from the youth and submit or present this to local authorities.

Activities

Activity 1: Consultation with youth worker

We will meet with the youth worker educator who works with the young people to introduce the Critical ChangeLab project, its aims, objectives, and parameters. We will discuss previous work with youth groups, the work already done by this youth group, and their interests. We decide on a general topic to focus on (Climate Action) and which to work on with the young people.

Activity 2: Onboarding and identifying an issue

We meet with the young people to explain our Critical ChangeLab project and our aims. We talk to them about issues that matter to them and why. We invite them to discuss these questions in groups, to decide on group values, and (informed by the issues and values) to decide on a specific challenge to take action on.

Activity 3: Learning more about the issue

We use this activity to ensure that the entire group have knowledge about the issue being focused on, and invite external facilitators to come and do a walking tour or a workshop with the group to introduce expertise and diverse perspectives on a topic.

Activity 4: Incorporating learnings into Youth Assembly organisation

This activity focuses on the young people applying what they've learned to the organisation of their Youth Assembly event in Wicklow. Reflecting on their learning and incorporating the vision of the future that they desire, they will decide on topics, guests to invite, and the schedule for the day.

Activity 5: Host a Youth Assembly on Climate Action

The young people will host their planned Youth Assembly on Climate Action, which will focus on issues that matter to them and incorporate aspects of the Critical ChangeLab process, the research that the participants undertook, and the visions of the future that they imagined. The Youth Assembly, through its nature and by inviting youth from neighbouring areas, is a decisive community action led by the young people that will have wider impact in their local area and result in a consultation document to inform the focus of future projects.

Table 3 – Activity Planning

	Aug 2024	Sep 2024	Oct 2024	Nov 2024	Dec 2024	Jan 2025
Act 1	X					
Act 2		X				
Act 3		X	X			
Act 4				X		
Act 5				X		

Obstacles and mitigation

Table 4 – Obstacles and mitigation

Description	Probability	Impact	Mitigation Measure
Students not engaging or participating fully	M	H	Create engaging activities and ensure inclusive facilitation, being open to adapting learning plan as the programme progresses
Limited understanding of democratic practices and principles	M	M	Provide clear definitions and explanations, and devise appropriate prompts for reflexive discussion
Conflict within groups affecting progress	S	M	Facilitate conflict resolution techniques and support
Time constraints in completing the project	M	H	Manage time effectively and provide additional support for TCD CCLAB team staff in the form of a Research Assistant.
Technical difficulties with materials or equipment	S	L	Have backup materials and plan for contingencies
Balancing artistic and educational objectives	M	H	Align activities with both artistic and educational goals

Design Your Future/Academy of the Near Future

PAR Cycle Background and Introduction

Trinity College Dublin

The Critical ChangeLab Ireland, led by Trinity College Dublin, is undertaken by the School of Education’s Science & Society Research Group and the Trinity Long Room Hub’s Democracy Forum. The research team brings expertise in education, science, arts and the humanities to this project, and promotes interdisciplinarity in its implementation. Through Critical ChangeLab Ireland, we are interested in creating spaces to partner with youth to imagine futures, explore new technologies, foster creative expression, and reinvigorate democracy.

Academy of the Near Future

Academy of the Near Future is a smart city education programme in partnership with CONNECT and Dublin City Council. They exist to accelerate sustainable and inclusive smart city development through awareness, skills, and confidence-building. Academy of the Near Future programmes are a combination of interactive workshops, online learning and “hands on” activities with sensor kits that provide learners with an understanding of how technologies such as the Internet of Things and Big Data can help cities deal with traffic congestion, air pollution, extreme weather events, and more.

Committed to demystifying smart cities to groups who are underserved in STEM, 50% of their workshops take place in DEIS (“disadvantaged”) schools with 50% female participation. In doing so, the Academy of the Near Future equips change makers to tackle 21st-century city challenges, and work towards a world where smart city technology improves the sustainability and liveability of cities across the world.

The TCD team are working with the Academy of the Near Future on their ‘Design Your Future City’ programme aimed at young people in Transition Year (approximately 15–16 years old) attending school in Dublin city. The ‘Design Your Future City’ programme is a well-established outreach programme, but this year will be following a Critical ChangeLab methodology for its structure. Ideas will be presented to a representative of Dublin City Council at the end of the week.

Theme of the CCLAB/Academy of the Near Future programme

The focus will be on designing an intervention for the future smart city, based around the theme of sustainability as it takes place during Trinity College Dublin's Climate Action Week. The youth will envision sustainable cities and propose an idea to implement in Dublin to improve sustainability in the city.

Aims of CCLAB

This Critical ChangeLab aims to:

1. To support the Academy of the Near Future to integrate a Critical ChangeLab methodology into their programme.
2. To implement a YPAR Cycle that encourages youth to generate and use research in their own analysis.
3. Strengthen democratic systems through civic participation.

Research Questions

Our research questions for this Critical ChangeLab are

1. Is the Critical ChangeLab method successful in promoting/fostering democratic competences/active participation?
2. How do youth display the development of critical literacies throughout the programme?
3. Is there evidence of using the past to envision the future or inform the present?
4. Can the Critical ChangeLab method be successfully integrated into a pre-existing programme?

Stakeholders & target audiences

This is an overview of the general stakeholders that are to be involved over the course of the project. The stakeholders that are made **bold** are also considered the target audience for the main objectives of the PAR Cycle.

- Stakeholder 1: **youth (aged approximately 15-16) who are accepted onto the 'Design Your Future City' programme**
- Stakeholder 2: The Academy of the Near Future team (1-2 x educators, 1 x educational institution)

- Stakeholder 3: Dublin City Council (partners with the Academy of the Near Future, 1 x CSO)
- Stakeholder 4: local guest speaker (TBC) (possibly 1-2 x CSO/educators)
- Stakeholder 5: Science & Society Research group, Trinity College Dublin (approx. 6 x educators)

PAR Cycle Objectives

Key Concepts

For each of the below concepts, identify the main related challenges and the local missions to combat these challenges within the scope of the PAR Cycle. Each segment should be around 50 -100 words.

Democratic practice & citizenship (understanding)

Challenge

The challenge in engaging with ideas and issues around democratic practice and citizenship is to help participants to move beyond thinking about 'democracy' solely in terms of governance, voting, and the judiciary.

PAR Cycle Mission

To foster meaningful discussion and action on the links between democratic practice, citizenship, and participation, and how everyone can engage in reinvigorating democracy through their everyday actions.

Recognizing conflict & contradictions in democratic systems (identifying)

Challenge

To make a meaningful connection between the engagement programme and their visions for the future and the conflict and contradictions in democratic systems in the limited time that we have with them.

PAR Cycle Mission

To collaborate with local authority stakeholders to engage the young people with discussions around questions about the democratic system and sustainability issues, national and local policies, and climate action targets.

Interrogating cultural construction, social, political context and societal transformation (deconstructing)

Challenge

To challenge traditional assumptions and normative expectations with participants through engaging in difficult discussions and giving space to perspectives and opinions that might differ from their own. Another major challenge here is to meaningfully engage with discussions of socio-political issues and power structures in the limited time we have.

PAR Cycle Mission

To design activities and lesson plans that are layered, complex, and engaging. By encouraging participants to consider these issues throughout the programme the discussion and activities at this stage should already be informed by their analysis and some reflection.

Alternative futures (activating change)

Challenge

To affect meaningful action and envision alternative futures with participants in a creative and innovative way in a limited amount of time.

PAR Cycle Mission

To implement a programme of activities which will empower participants to meaningfully envision alternative futures for their community and to act towards their implementation. The action may be big or small, but it's important that participants feel as though their action had impact.

Please rate the importance of each concept within your PAR Cycle, marking one value per row (1 is lowest, 5 is highest)

	1	2	3	4	5
<i>Democratic practice & citizenship</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Recognizing conflict & contradictions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Interrogating constructions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Alternative futures</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Outcomes

Outcome 1: Presenting an idea and/or prototype of an invention that addresses the issue of sustainability in future Dublin city. Participants will envision alternative, sustainable futures for Dublin city and present ideas and prototypes of inventions that they will work together to create. These prototypes will address specific challenges that Dublin faces in being a completely sustainable city. They will be presented to a guest panel of reviewers, which will include a member of Dublin City Council.

Outcome 2: Students enhance their knowledge on issues of sustainability and the challenges of climate action in Dublin city. Students will enhance their knowledge of sustainability issues within Dublin city through actions taken in our Participatory Action Research project. Students, using research methodologies, will investigate issues such as water quality or measuring heat zones. Their knowledge of the challenges in addressing sustainability issues and the tensions that can arise will also be enhanced.

Outcome 3: Increased participation in society through engagement with the Critical ChangeLab. Students will envision alternative futures for their city and take individual and small group action towards creating something to address the challenges they face. This will increase their participation in society.

Plan and Activities

Action plan

In this PAR Cycle we will collaborate with the Academy of the Near Future to incorporate a Critical ChangeLab methodology into their 'Design Your Future City' programme. It will take place between 14–18 October (inclusive) at Trinity College Dublin. We will work with the youth to research sustainability, climate change, and climate action challenges in Dublin city and envision alternative futures.

Activities

Activity 1: Consultation with educator

We will meet with the educator who works with the young people (on the Academy of the Near Future team) to introduce the Critical ChangeLab project, its aims, objectives, and parameters. We will discuss previous work with the Design Your Future City programme, the potential for integrating the Critical ChangeLab

methodology, and the challenges the educator hopes to address. We decide on a general topic to focus on (Climate Action and Biodiversity) and which to work on with the young people.

Activity 2: Onboarding and identifying an issue

We meet with the young people to explain our Critical ChangeLab project and our aims. We talk to them about issues that matter to them and why. We invite them to discuss these questions in groups, to decide on group values, and (informed by the issues and values) to decide on a specific challenge to take action on.

Activity 3: Workshops

The young people take part in a series of themed workshops, all related to ‘Climate Action and Biodiversity’ which will aim to expand their knowledge on a range of issues and challenges related to the topic. The workshops will offer them different perspectives and expertise.

Activity 4: Prototyping a solution

Based on the work they will have done, students will generate ideas for challenges related to Climate Action and Biodiversity in the city of Dublin in the future. In groups they will generate solutions to these challenges, and decide on which solution to prototype and pitch to a judging panel.

Activity 5: Pitching

Participants will pitch their solutions (which must be focused on technology) for the future city of Dublin. They will creatively pitch their solutions and answer questions on its design, their rationale, and potential audiences. The students will aim to convince the judging panel that their prototype is worthy of being elevated to the next stage of development.

Table 3 – Activity Planning

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Table 4 – Obstacles and mitigation

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Technical difficulties with materials or equipment	S	L	Have backup materials and plan for contingencies
Balancing artistic and educational objectives	M	H	Align activities with both artistic and educational goals

LATRA PAR Cycle 2 Plan

LATRA's PAR Cycle will involve collaboration with diverse stakeholders to adapt George Orwell's *Animal Farm* into a theatre play and workshops designed for children. Through this creative and interactive approach, LATRA aims to explore how schoolchildren understand and embody democratic values in the context of their lived experiences with the refugee crisis. The play and workshops will serve as tools to provoke reflection and dialogue on themes such as power, equality, and justice.

PAR Cycle Background and Introduction

Information about local context: LATRA will be conducting its PAR Cycle in Lesvos, Greece, a location that has faced tremendous challenges since 2015 due to the ongoing refugee crisis. Over the years, the island has been at the forefront of Europe's migration crisis, with thousands of refugees arriving from conflict zones such as Syria, Afghanistan, and beyond. This influx of refugees has placed Lesvos under immense social, political, and economic strain, exacerbating tensions both within the local community as well as on a national level. The refugee crisis has deeply divided the island's residents, creating polarized opinions on how to address the humanitarian situation. While many have shown compassion, providing aid and support to those fleeing violence, others have expressed frustration over the impact the refugee population has had on local resources, infrastructure, and daily life. This division extends beyond Lesvos to the national political landscape, where the refugee crisis remains a contentious issue.

Information about organisation: LATRA is an organisation based in Lesvos-Greece conducting state-of-the-art research and innovation at the frontlines of 21st Century European challenges that respond to the most pressing needs and challenges faced by European citizens. LATRA ensures that all citizens, including those in geographically-remote regions, and socio-economically disadvantaged communities, are equitably included in all aspects of European society. Specifically, we work with NEETs, early school leavers, refugees and unaccompanied minors and people with disabilities. In addition, we take affirmative action in producing gender-balanced activities that are designed to address the barriers faced by women and those belonging to the LGBTQIA+ community. Our goal is to build a society free from exclusion due to race, gender identity, age, disability, immigration status, or other

factors. Through our programs, we aim to enhance their abilities, elevate their confidence, and ensure they have equal chances for growth in both personal and professional spheres. We engage in initiatives across policy domains of the New European Bauhaus in collaboration with a wide array of partners. We leverage lifelong learning and behavioural changes to enable communities to have a tangible and significant influence on Europe's journey. That is achieved by emphasising the advancement of digital skills, the cultivation of digital citizenship, the encouragement of digital-minded thinking, and the application of online and remote learning techniques.

PAR Cycle aims to research: Throughout primary education in Greece, children are taught about their country's historical legacy in the European Union as the birthplace of democracy. LATRA's second PAR cycle will explore how these educational messages resonate with 11-year-old schoolchildren on the island of Lesbos, especially in the context of the ongoing refugee crisis. The research aims to investigate how the values of democracy—such as equality, inclusion, and participation—are understood, internalised, and reflected in the daily lives of these children.

This inquiry is particularly relevant in Lesbos, where for the past five years, classrooms have been integrating both local and refugee children. These students, coming from vastly different backgrounds, have had to share not only physical space but also learning experiences, social interactions, and playtime. This unique co-existence presents an important lens through which to study how democratic values are being put into practice in everyday life for children. At the same time, local children have been exposed to a variety of conflicting messages about the refugee crisis from their parents, who may hold diverse views based on their own experiences and perspectives on the crisis. Some parents may express empathy and solidarity with the refugees, while others may communicate frustration or resentment due to the social, economic, and political strains the crisis has placed on the island. LATRA's research will focus on how these different influences—school teachings about democracy and parental attitudes toward refugees—shape the way children think about and enact democratic principles such as fairness, inclusion, and cooperation. By examining the children's reflections, interactions, and behaviours, the research will provide insights into the extent to which they are able to embody democratic values in their day-to-day lives. LATRA hopes to uncover

whether these values are being reinforced or undermined by the combination of school education and the varied messages children receive at home. The findings will contribute to understanding how young minds are navigating complex social realities, and may also offer valuable lessons for educators, policymakers, and communities about fostering democratic culture and social cohesion among the next generation, even in challenging environments like Lesvos.

Stakeholders & target audiences

This is an overview of the general stakeholders that are to be involved over the course of the project. The stakeholders that are made **bold** are also considered the target audience for the main objectives of the PAR Cycle.

1. **Local Schoolchildren (11-year-olds)** – These children are the primary target audience of the research, as the project focuses on understanding how democratic values resonate with them. Expected reach: 75-100.
2. **Refugee Schoolchildren (11-year-olds)** – These students are also a key target audience, as their experiences and interactions within local classrooms are central to the study's objectives. Their number is far smaller than group (1). Expected reach: 10-20.
3. Parents of Local Schoolchildren – Their attitudes and messages regarding the refugee crisis are crucial for understanding how children's perceptions of democratic values are shaped. Expected reach: 25-35.
4. Parents of Refugee Schoolchildren – Their experiences and views could also offer insight into how integration and co-learning impact the refugee children's development and social integration. Expected reach: 5-10.
5. Teachers and School Administrators – As they facilitate the integration and co-existence of local and refugee children, their perspectives on education, inclusion, and democratic values will be essential for understanding the school environment. Expected reach: 15-25.
6. Local Community Members – Broader community sentiment plays a role in shaping the environment that children are growing up in, influencing their views on democracy and inclusion. Expected reach: 5-10.
7. Refugee Support Organizations – NGOs and other groups providing services to refugee families may offer insights into how integration is working and how schoolchildren are impacted by the crisis. Expected reach: 2-3.

8. Academics and Researchers – Researchers in fields such as education, social cohesion, and migration studies may contribute to or benefit from the findings of the PAR Cycle. Expected reach: 2–3.
9. Creative Organisations – These are organisations who will assist LATRA in producing non-formal educational activities that will spur the debate and research. Expected reach: 2–3.

PAR Cycle Objectives

Key Concepts

Democratic practice & citizenship (understanding)

Challenge: The main challenge lies in how schoolchildren grasp and apply democratic values such as participation, equality, and inclusion, especially in a context marked by the refugee crisis. Conflicting messages from schools promoting democratic ideals and parents or community members expressing frustration over the crisis can create confusion for children. This leads to gaps in their understanding of citizenship and the principles of democracy.

PAR Cycle Mission: The PAR Cycle aims to bridge this gap by engaging children through interactive theatre and workshops based on *Animal Farm*, encouraging them to reflect on their roles as active citizens. The mission is to help students better understand and practice democratic values, by exploring these concepts in a safe, creative environment where they can express their thoughts, share experiences, and consider the complexities of equality and power in their daily lives.

Recognizing conflict & contradictions in democratic systems (identifying)

Challenge: One of the major challenges is helping children recognize the inherent conflicts and contradictions within democratic systems, particularly when ideals such as equality and inclusion clash with the realities of social and political issues like the refugee crisis. Children may struggle to reconcile the values of democracy taught in school with the exclusion or negative attitudes they witness toward refugees in their communities or families.

PAR Cycle Mission: The PAR Cycle aims to create a space where children can safely explore and identify these contradictions through the lens of *Animal Farm* and the

workshops. By encouraging critical thinking and open discussions, the mission is to help them recognize where democratic systems fall short or conflict with lived experiences, and to foster an understanding of the complexities of democracy in real-world contexts. This process empowers children to question and critically engage with the democratic values they are taught.

Interrogating cultural construction, social, political context and societal transformation (deconstructing)

Challenge: A key challenge is helping children deconstruct the cultural, social, and political narratives surrounding the refugee crisis and societal transformation. Young students may have difficulty understanding how cultural biases, media portrayals, and political discourse shape their perceptions of refugees and influence societal divisions. Additionally, they might struggle to grasp how these forces contribute to broader societal changes and how their own beliefs are formed within this context.

PAR Cycle Mission: The PAR Cycle seeks to guide children in critically deconstructing these narratives by using the allegorical themes in *Animal Farm* as a framework. Through the play and workshops, children will explore how societal structures, power dynamics, and cultural biases affect their understanding of social and political issues. The mission is to foster critical thinking and awareness of how these forces shape their worldview, empowering them to engage more thoughtfully in societal transformation and democratic practice.

Alternative futures (activating change)

Challenge: The main challenge in envisioning alternative futures is helping children move beyond passive acceptance of current societal conditions and encouraging them to see themselves as active agents of change. In a context dominated by the refugee crisis and social divisions, children may feel powerless or believe that the status quo is unchangeable. Encouraging them to imagine and work toward more inclusive and just futures is a significant hurdle.

PAR Cycle Mission: The PAR Cycle aims to inspire children to envision alternative futures by exploring themes of power, equality, and justice through *Animal Farm*. The mission is to activate a sense of agency in young minds, encouraging them to think critically about their role in creating change. Through interactive theatre and

workshops, children will be empowered to imagine new possibilities for their communities, fostering a mindset that they can contribute to more democratic, inclusive futures.

Please rate the importance of each concept within your PAR Cycle, marking one value per row (1 is lowest, 5 is highest)

	1	2	3	4	5
<i>Democratic practice & citizenship</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	X	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Recognizing conflict & contradictions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	X
<i>Interrogating constructions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	X	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Alternative futures</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	X	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Outcomes

Outcome 1: At the conclusion of the PAR Cycle, we hope to achieve an enhanced understanding of democratic values—such as equality, participation, and inclusion—among local and refugee schoolchildren. Through their engagement with *Animal Farm* and the accompanying workshops, children will have the opportunity to explore complex democratic ideals in a tangible and relatable way. By portraying the dynamics of power, authority, and justice in the play, the aim is to help children internalize these values and reflect on how they apply in their own lives. This enhanced understanding should manifest in their ability to recognize democratic practices in daily interactions, not only in their schools but also within their families and communities. The project aims for the children to have a clearer sense of what it means to be an active citizen, with a foundational understanding of democracy that empowers them to practice fairness, cooperation, and inclusion.

Success criteria for outcome 1:

Observational reports: Facilitators will assess children’s behaviour during workshops, noting instances of democratic practices (e.g., fairness in group activities, active participation in discussions).

Reflections and feedback: Children will participate in reflective activities, such as group discussions and drawn reflections, where they articulate how they see democratic values applied in their school and community life.

Outcome 2: The second outcome is for participants to develop a heightened awareness of the contradictions and conflicts inherent in democratic systems, especially in relation to the refugee crisis. By the end of the PAR Cycle, children will be better equipped to identify and question the dissonance between democratic ideals and the real-world experiences of marginalized groups, such as refugees. Using *Animal Farm* as a tool for critical inquiry, the project will encourage children to reflect on the contradictions they observe in their own community—where democratic principles may be taught but not always practiced, especially regarding inclusion and equity for refugees. This outcome will promote critical thinking, enabling children to actively question and engage with societal norms, rather than passively accepting them. Ideally, this will contribute to a more reflective and open-minded younger generation, aware of the complexities of democracy.

Success criteria for outcome 2:

Focus group feedback: Feedback from teachers and parents will gauge whether children are questioning societal norms more critically and discussing these issues outside of the structured activities.

Interactive participation: Children’s engagement during the *Animal Farm* play and related activities (e.g., voting on character decisions, debating ethical choices) will be evaluated to see if they can identify and question inconsistencies in the story’s portrayal of democracy.

Outcome 3: A critical outcome of the PAR Cycle is fostering stronger social cohesion and empathy between local and refugee children. By having them co-participate in the theatre production and workshops, the project aims to bridge cultural and social divides, creating a shared space for dialogue, collaboration, and mutual understanding. Through role-playing and storytelling in *Animal Farm*, children will gain insight into different perspectives and experiences, building emotional intelligence and empathy. By the end of the cycle, we hope to observe a greater sense of solidarity and inclusiveness between the children, with both local and refugee students feeling more connected and valued within their classroom and community. This outcome is aimed at promoting social harmony and reducing the sense of "otherness" that often arises in contexts of cultural integration.

Success criteria for outcome 3:

Behavioural observations: Facilitators will monitor interactions between local and refugee children during workshops and the play, noting any positive changes in collaboration, mutual support, and inclusiveness.

Empathy assessment: Through storytelling activities and role-playing exercises, children's ability to understand and express empathy for different perspectives will be evaluated. This can be measured by their responses in group discussions and reflective exercises.

Plan and Activities

LATRA will engage key stakeholders, including teachers, school administrators, parents, and local NGOs working with refugees. Workshops will be designed to align with the goals of the cycle, focusing on *Animal Farm* as the primary educational tool. Local and refugee children will be selected for participation in the project, and preparatory sessions will introduce the themes of democracy, equality, and social justice. After the performances and workshops, data will be collected through observation, interviews, and group discussions to assess the impact of the cycle. LATRA will compile insights, focusing on how children's understanding of democratic values and social inclusion evolved, and present findings to stakeholders, schools, and the wider community.

Activities

Activity 1: Recruiting

The recruiting phase of the PAR Cycle will involve building a strong network of support by meeting with key stakeholders in the education and social sectors. LATRA will hold in-depth discussions with teachers, school administrators, NGO staff, CSO representatives, and researchers to present the objectives of the PAR Cycle and gain their support. These meetings will help establish partnerships, ensure the project aligns with local needs, and secure buy-in from those who directly influence children's education and well-being. During these interactions, LATRA will present the project's goals, highlighting the importance of fostering democratic values in children and addressing the refugee crisis in a sensitive and constructive way. Stakeholders will be invited to contribute their expertise, offer suggestions, and

collaborate on the logistics of the project. Materials used in this phase will include leaflets/presentations about CCLAB and detailed timelines of planned activities. These resources will provide stakeholders with a clear understanding of their roles and how they can contribute to the successful implementation of the PAR Cycle, creating a supportive and engaged ecosystem for the project.

Activity 2: Focus groups

Prior to involving children in the main activities of the PAR Cycle, focus groups will be conducted with key stakeholders such as parents, teachers, school administrators, researchers, and representatives from civil society organisations and NGOs. These sessions will serve two primary purposes: engaging the broader community and gathering insights on existing attitudes, concerns, and tendencies related to the refugee crisis and democratic values. During these focus groups, LATRA will facilitate discussions around the social, political, and educational contexts influencing children's perceptions of democracy and inclusion. The aim is to identify any potential challenges, such as community resistance or misconceptions, and gather ideas on how best to engage the children in meaningful activities. Materials distributed include consent forms, and anonymised feedback forms.

Activity 3: Talking about democracy in the classroom

In preparation for the PAR Cycle, LATRA will collaborate with teachers to streamline existing lesson plans on democracy based on their existing curriculum. This activity is designed to ensure that children have a foundational understanding of democratic concepts before participating in the *Animal Farm* play and workshops. Teachers will use existing educational materials and curriculum guides, adapting them to emphasise key democratic principles such as equality, justice, and participation, with connections to current events like the refugee crisis. LATRA will support teachers in creating engaging classroom discussions and activities around these topics. The lesson plan will focus on making abstract democratic ideals relatable to the children's everyday experiences, such as fairness in decision-making, inclusion in group activities, and respecting different viewpoints. Materials used will include textbooks, multimedia resources (videos, presentations), and interactive classroom exercises such as debates, role-playing scenarios, or group discussions. This preparation phase will ensure students are familiar with key

concepts of democracy and ready to engage more deeply with the themes explored in the *Animal Farm* production and the broader PAR Cycle activities.

Activity 4: Theatre play

LATRA will collaborate with a theatre production company to adapt *Animal Farm* into a play specifically designed for children. This adaptation will focus on making the themes of power, equality, and democracy accessible and engaging for young audiences. The play will include interactive components, where children can participate directly in the performance, such as voting on key decisions made by the characters. The interactive nature of the play is intended to deepen the children's understanding of democratic values by allowing them to actively experience concepts such as participation and fairness. Children will attend the performance with their parents and teachers, creating a shared learning experience that fosters dialogue both in and outside the theatre. Materials used will include customized scripts designed for young audiences, props, multimedia elements to enhance visual engagement, and tools for interactive participation, such as voting cards or on-stage participation opportunities. This immersive experience will serve as a foundation for the workshops that follow, where children will further explore the lessons learned from the play in more depth.

Activity 5: Workshops

Following the interactive *Animal Farm* performance, LATRA will conduct a series of workshops with participating children to deepen their understanding of the democratic values explored in the play. These workshops will be designed to encourage reflection on themes like power, justice, and inclusion, especially in relation to their lived experiences with the refugee crisis. Through creative activities such as role-playing, group discussions, and collaborative problem-solving tasks, children will explore how these democratic principles apply to their daily lives, both in school and in their communities. The workshops will be interactive and age-appropriate, using a combination of storytelling, visual aids, and hands-on activities to engage the children. Materials will include creative art supplies for drawing or expressing ideas visually. The workshops aim to reinforce the lessons learned in the play, encourage empathy between local and refugee children, and empower them to see themselves as active participants in a democratic society. The goal is to leave children with a stronger understanding of how they can practice

fairness, inclusion, and cooperation in their everyday lives. In total there will be 5 workshops.

Activity 6: Evaluating sessions

At the conclusion of the PAR Cycle, LATRA will hold evaluation sessions with all participating stakeholders, including teachers, parents, school administrators, CSO/NGO representatives, and the children themselves. The aim of these sessions is to assess the overall effectiveness of the PAR Cycle in achieving its objectives, particularly in promoting an understanding of democratic values and fostering social cohesion between local and refugee children. The evaluation sessions will be structured as open discussions and feedback forums, where participants can share their experiences, observations, and insights. Materials used will include surveys and questionnaires tailored to different stakeholder groups to gather quantitative and qualitative data on the impact of the activities. Focus group discussions will be held to allow deeper reflection on the play, workshops, and their effects on the children’s behaviour and attitudes. LATRA will also use observational reports from teachers and workshop facilitators, along with any feedback gathered during the project, to identify strengths and areas for improvement. The results of these evaluations will inform future cycles, ensuring that the program continues to evolve and effectively meet the needs of the children and broader community.

Table 3 – Activity Planning

	Aug 2024	Sep 2024	Oct 2024	Nov 2024	Dec 2024	Jan 2025
Act 1	X	X	X			
Act 2			X	X		
Act 3				X		
Act 4				X	X	
Act 5				X	X	
Act 6						X

Obstacles and mitigation

Table 4 – Obstacles and mitigation

Description	Probability	Impact	Mitigation Measure
Resistance from schools, parents, or community members	M	L	Engage parents and community members early in the process through informational sessions and open

			dialogue. Clearly communicate the goals of the PAR Cycle and the benefits of inclusion and empathy for all children involved.
Logistical challenges	M	M	Plan well in advance, securing venues, materials, and scheduling workshops to align with school and community availability. Develop a flexible timetable to adjust to any unforeseen logistical issues.
Limited engagement from schoolchildren in conversations around democracy	L	M	Use interactive and creative activities (e.g., role-playing, theatre) to keep children engaged. Regular check-ins with participants to ensure they feel involved and heard throughout the cycle.
Political or social tensions around the refugee crisis	M	L	Frame discussions around empathy and shared democratic values, rather than focusing on divisive political narratives. Ensure a neutral and safe environment for discussions, avoiding overly politicized conversations.

University of Oulu PAR Cycle 2 Plan

We plan to have 3 CCLABs during PAR 2 with 2 local school. Labs 1 and 2 are happening at the same school while Lab 3 is happening at School 2.

PAR Cycle Background and Introduction

This PAR cycle is conducted with two local schools, in both cases with 7th grade students (in one school two Labs were organised with two different classes, while in the other school only one class was involved). Total number of youths involved in these labs were 72 students (25+25+22), with 33 students from underrepresented groups (all participants were younger than 15 years old).

Researchers from University of Oulu: 4 Researchers from University of Oulu are involved in running the labs. Researchers are from INTERACT Research Unit that falls under the faculty of Information Technology and Electrical Engineering. The research background of the researchers varies, ranging from information systems, media, design, education and literature and they are from 3 different nationalities.

School 1 (period Oct–Nov 2024): Two labs were organised with two 7th grade classes taking the same course (with same teacher). Each session lasted 60 min. The Labs take place in the context of an ICT course that focuses on providing children with a chance to get familiar with technologies that they need for everyday schoolwork like Teams, Microsoft word, PowerPoint etc. While students were allowed to use their phones and some of the activities involved checking social media, in some respects the tools available to use during the sessions were restricted to services to which the school had agreements. Throughout the Lab, emphasis was made on children’s rights as data subjects (when going through the informed consent, making parallelisms with IT services personal data collection practices). Further discussion (through dedicated moments) about the democratic practices of IT companies was not possible, basically due to time limitations.

The Labs focused on social media and had as key objective triggering discussions on conflicts and tensions in social media in everyday lives of young people. The questions used to trigger discussion during the pitching session is “How is growing up with social media?” based on the comments and discussions, we would move towards shaping the concrete idea which the young people want to focus on during the coming sessions.

School 2 (period Dec. 2024 – Jan. 2025): the Lab was organised in the context of a transdisciplinary project-based course focused on UNESCO goals (with an emphasis on values such as tolerance, peace...). This Lab was also focused on social media. In terms of Lab design, most of the activities and methods were same as the ones used in school 1, with some adaptations as in this case there were a smaller number of sessions (although each session had a duration of 75 min.).

School 3 (pitch sessions organised on 10.09.2024): This school provides courses for students who need skills and guided support to move on to secondary education or vocational education so they can access further training before entering job market. Some of the students attending this school had dropped out from secondary education thus here they could gain supplementary courses to enrol in the mainstream education. The target group for this educational context are mostly students whose native language is not Finnish, Swedish or Sami you have completed basic education or equivalent education in a language other than Finnish, Swedish or Sami.

Stakeholders & target audiences

*This is an overview of the general stakeholders that are to be involved over the course of the project. The stakeholders that are made **bold** are also considered the target audience for the main objectives of the PAR Cycle.*

1. **Local Schools** (three schools located in Oulu were interested and a pitching session was organised in all of them. Three Labs were organised with two of them).
2. **Educators** (includes teachers, FABLAB Instructors/operators)
 - a. **School 1:** 1 educator (contacted us after meeting in a STEAM education event organised by the city), during planning phase 1 FabLab instructor was also contacted.
 - b. **School 2:** 2 educators (we had already worked with one of these educators during PAR 1)
 - c. **School 3** (these Labs did not finally happen due to lack of participants): 1 pedagogical coordinator, 1 educator, (contacts with 4 other educators).
3. **Students**

D2.1 Report: Critical ChangeLab cycle 2

- a. **School 1:** 2 classes of 7th graders from ICT course. Each class had 25 students aged 12–13.
 - b. **School 2:** 22 students aged 12–13, 7th grade taking a “MOK” course (multi-disciplinary learning modules). This school is university’s Teacher Training School and is located near the university. This area is mostly occupied by foreigners (university students, staff members) as there are a lot of student housing society buildings. The teacher mentioned that the selected class is composed mostly of foreigners.
 - c. **School 3** (only pitch session): 32 students aged 15–17, taking preparatory education for upper secondary education (“TUVA”) (two classes). These students had dropped out from compulsory secondary education.
4. **Civic Society Organisations:**
- a. **Multicultural Centre Villa Victor:** The City of Oulu Multicultural Centre Villa Victor is a low threshold meeting place open for everyone. They offer Finnish language teaching free of charge and organise multicultural events, information sessions, clubs and mentoring programs. It specialises in immigration work coordination and development. Their staff members work as specialists in different work and guidance groups related to immigration and multiculturalism. Anti-racism work and integration as a two-way process are their central goals. Villa Victor staff (three persons) participated in three Labs with school 1 and 2.
 - b. **Designing for Children’s Rights:** Designing for Children’s Rights (D4CR) is a global non-profit association, supporting the Designing for Children’s Rights Guide that integrates the U.N. rights of the child in design, business and development of products and services around the world. The association’s work seeks to create awareness about children’s rights when designing products and services. To this purpose, they have developed the Designing for Children’s Rights Guide, which instead of pointing out what is wrong, guides how to do things right.

PAR Cycle Objectives

Key Concepts

Democratic practice & citizenship (understanding)

Challenge: Fostering understanding of social media as a space where people relate and thus, is part of everyday democracy.

PAR Cycle Mission

Open a discussion regarding:

- How is it growing up with social media?
- How do participants view social media?
- What is needed to fully communicate/participate in these spaces?
- What type of experiences do participants get in social media and how much agency do they think they have in these spaces?

Participants were involved as researchers to record and explore significant instances from their interactions with social media.

Recognizing conflict & contradictions in democratic systems (identifying)

Challenge: Prompting participants to identify the range of experiences youth might have about social media going beyond their own individual experiences.

PAR Cycle Mission

Trigger discussion regarding following questions:

- Who is present or has the possibility to have presence?
- How does the system work: can anybody have a voice and visibility?

Interrogating cultural construction, social, political context and societal transformation (deconstructing)

Challenge: Supporting participants develop a critical and complex thinking about relations in social media. Encouraging them to deconstruct the conflicts happening in these spaces in their own terms

PAR Cycle Mission

Deconstructing experiences:

What does it look like for someone who experiences bullying, hate speech etc?

Multiple perspectives: mind-maps.

Alternative futures (activating change)

D2.1 Report: Critical ChangeLab cycle 2

Challenge: Helping participants go beyond stereotypes. Envision alternatives that matter to them.

PAR Cycle Mission

What do the young people want in social media apps that is not currently there?
Young people as “Ambassadors of change”: What would they suggest or advocate for based on their observations or research?
Ambassadors of change: campaigning/activism: Intervention in their own context (school, library etc) to open conversations and trigger awareness.

Please rate the importance of each concept within your PAR Cycle, marking one value per row (1 is lowest, 5 is highest)

	1	2	3	4	5
<i>Democratic practice & citizenship</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Recognizing conflict & contradictions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	x
<i>Interrogating constructions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	x
<i>Alternative futures</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	x

Outcomes

Outcome 1: Participant-led research on issues that are close to their everyday life

Outcome 2: Foster imagination and critical thinking among participants

Outcome 3: Advocacy through exhibition design. Encourage participants to envision ways they can make their voice heard.

The main focus of these outcomes is on building competences and the methods used to involve the children during the labs supported in building these competencies. Examples include reflective discussions during the focus group and the everyday activities taking place during the session. Students demonstrated certain competences like critical self-reflection by identify tensions based on their observations of social media (their own feeds in most cases). During the focus group students were able to link these competences to the activities and how the activities helped in practicing /acquiring certain competences. Furthermore, they were able to imagine and design alternative app designs for future social media apps and this led to discussion regarding the futures they want and how can they take action-oriented steps to bring the desired futures.

Plan and Activities

School 1

- 2 Labs ran simultaneously in School 1
- Eight sessions of 60 minutes each happening in the school classroom. For one session, we invited people from Villa Victor (Oulu Loves me) to brief students about different services provide by city for youth and the type of events they organize in which youth can participate as active members to make their voices heard. One such event would be Oulu Loves me(anti-racist) week and they gave students a task to make posters to make a campaign about their selected topics that is, “racism or prejudices or equality and diversity).

Activities School 1

Activity 1: Workshops

We ran 8 workshops with 2 different sections of 7th graders from school 1. Each session lasted 60 mins. The workshops consisted of hands-on activities where youth were active participants, and the researchers supported the activities by providing simple instructions. The description of session’s activities is given below:

Onboard: Mentimeter (open ended)

The participants are asked an open-ended question: What is Democracy? They wrote their answers individually on the mentimeter and this was followed by a short discussion and shedding light on democracy in everyday settings and lives.

This activity was followed by a second question: How is growing up with social media? Here we moved from words to ideas, discussing ideas with peers in pairs or small groups and sharing on mentimeter in the form of sentences.

This activity provided a chance to explore the words young people choose to talk about their social media interactions. There were many positive comments but also a few negative ones to help in triggering discussion and opening conversations about the fact that “experience is not the same for everyone”.

Onboard-Question: Storyboard for opening up discussion about emotions- Onboard

Instructions: Create a storyboard about a situation in which somebody gives a funny idea in a group in response to the starting statement. The other characters respond based on the role they got.

Starting statement: Somebody suggests “Let us come up with ideas for being safe online”.

- Participants choose 1 character and 1 emotion randomly.
- **Characters:** A cat, A Robot, A tree, A magical unicorn, A teenager
- **Emotions:** Supportive, funny, jealous, grumpy, happy

They thought about other 1-3 characters to be added in the story and created a visual story by thinking about:

- What funny idea the main character proposes?
- How would the selected characters respond to the comments?
- What would it make the other person feel?

Participants worked in groups to create visual stories on a storyboard template provided to them. Finally, they presented their stories leading to comments and discussion.

Onboard: Co-creating the code of conduct

Trigger questions:

- How do our comments/responses make others feel?
- How do we want to relate to one another?

Co-creating a code of conduct that would make everybody feel included, encouraged and safe to speak their mind even if their ideas are not perfect.

The storyboards resulted in talk about emotions. How our responses and attitudes give rise to different emotions and what rules we can make for ourselves to promote positivity. Each group suggested one rule to be observed during our interactions face to face and online.

On-board: Competences as Thinking hats

This activity was aimed at understanding competences and collective meaning making. The participants discussed in groups what they understood by certain competences and used the hat as a prop to put competence cards in it and wear as a personification of these competences they prioritized and want to focus on during the CCLAB sessions. We took pictures of what each group selected and put in the hat.

Question: Establishing a Researcher ID

The activity started with a question: Who is a researcher?

Followed by discussion based on the participants' answers. The students were encouraged to play the role of researchers throughout the Lab where they will collect data, analyse and finally look for solutions/answers.

We used the Motto: “All of us are researchers” and provided them with a Researcher tool kit (University logo bad, notebook, pens, stickers and an ID card) to support their role as researchers. Their role was to collect data for their research by looking for tensions/issues in their everyday social media interactions. They took screenshots and put them in the Teams folder dedicated for each group with small sticky notes detailing what is happening and why they think it is important to discuss. The participants were given 1 week to collect data for the research they are going to do. They could choose to use social media with their personal account or could create a new account just for this data collection activity.

The instructions for the task are given here:

- You just have to use social media as usual.
- For the same amount of time that you usually spend on social media.
- But be more perceptive and critical. Look at things from a researcher's perspective and collect data.

Data can be anything

- comments that you think are inappropriate (negative, bullying, demotivating).
- Videos that promote false idols (societal pressures)
- Pranks.
- Any other thing that you feel is annoying

How to collect data?

- Take screenshots and post them in your group space and add on sticky notes 1-2 sentences explaining
- What is happening in the screenshot? Why do you think this is relevant?

Question-Analyse: Thematic analysis of the screen shots

The researchers printed the photos and notes that the participants had collected in their Teams folder. The group members discussed what they shared and what it meant in the context of tensions in social media. Later, they looked at all the screenshots collected by the group and grouped them according to similar themes. They cut and pasted these photos and notes onto a big sheet of paper.

The participants looked at all the themes and from there they chose a main topic/theme that they would like to explore in detail. They looked at any sub-categories within the broader theme and tried to find connections.

Analyse: Mind Maps-Going deeper in the themes

Within the broader theme that each group had chosen, the participants analysed it further by focusing on what type of question they should be asking as a researcher and what is a good question.

Questions like

- What else is happening under the same theme? Discussing.
- Who are the actors/stakeholders, missing actors/stakeholder? Who has a voice?
- How are different actors connected/involved?

Envision & Examine: Future Apps designing

Trigger questions:

- What do we want our futures to look like? What do young people want that is not currently there?
- What features do you envision for future social media apps that could be the solution of existing problems that you identified.

The participants thought about features, wireframes and visuals of new social media apps.

Act: Creating Posters

Open (digital vs Physical posters):

Working on their designs for the posters or artefacts they want to create.

Designs included: Small Message, Design, visual logo etc

Activity 2: Participant led Interviews

Participants interviewed others in groups to know more about what other groups had been working on regarding the topics and mind-maps. The purpose was to allow them to have a varied perspective on what other groups had been discussing about the same topic. This allowed them to have an active role and gain deeper insights by asking questions, listening and recording the whole process.

Activity 3: Small presentation by Villa Viktor team

An Info session was held with the organizers from Villa Viktor where they presented What they have been doing regarding youth work and activities? They shared examples from the past about how they have worked previously with children and provided prompts for future interventions and actions for the students regarding How can students make their voices heard.

Activity 4: Students’ work Presentations for Villa Viktor team

The participants presented their posters that they created to be displayed in Oulu Loves me week along with the supporting materials created throughout the labs (mind maps, app designs) to organizers from Villa Viktor, this was followed by discussion and feedback from them regarding their work.

Activity 5: Exhibition

Students work would be displayed in the Oulu Loves Me Week exhibition to be held in March 2025 in the Cultural centre Valve.

Table 2 – Activity Planning School 1

	Aug 2024	Sep 2024	Oct 2024	Nov 2024	Dec 2024- Feb 2025	March 2025
Act 1						
Act 2						
Act 3						
Act 4						

Act 5						
Act 6						
Act 7						
Act 8						
Act 9						
Act 10						

School 2

Six sessions of 75 minutes each. Session 1 happened at the school while the remaining 5 sessions would take place in the University of Oulu premises. For one session, we would invite people from Villa Victor (Oulu Loves me) to brief students about different services provide by city for youth and the type of events they organize in which youth can participate as active members to make their voices heard. One such event would be Oulu Loves me(anti-racist) week and they gave students a task to make posters to make a campaign about their selected topics that is, “racism or prejudices or equality and diversity).

Activities School 2

Activity 1 Workshops

6 workshops would be held, and the activities are similar to the ones already described in the context of Lab 1.

Activity 2: Participant led Interviews

Participants would interview other groups to explore the chosen topic in detail and know more about what had been discussed in other groups.

Activity 3: Visitors from Civil Service organizations

The participants would present what they have been doing to the people from Villa Viktor and there is a possibility that we would invite a team from D4CR for their insights into designing for children rights.

Activity 4: Exhibition

The students work (posters, future app designs) would be exhibited in school and also in the Anti Racist week (Oulu Loves Me) in Cultural Center Valve.

	December	January	February	March		
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	2024	2025	2025	2025		
Act 1						
Act 2						
Act 3						
Act 4						

Obstacles and mitigation

Table 4 – Obstacles and mitigation

Please list any potential obstacles to the success of your PAR Cycle, the probability and impact (S, M, or L), and mitigation measures your PAR Cycle will take. List a minimum of three obstacles and maximum of 6.

Description	Probability	Impact	Mitigation Measure
Engaging participants, getting them to lead the lab	L	L	Close communication with the teacher, give visibility to their work outside the school, plan revision based on each session development
Arranging collaboration with stakeholders	S	M	Flexibility with the scheduling, Limiting collaboration to specific moments

European Alternatives PAR Cycle 2 Plan

Researchers at Alternatives Européennes will work with youth groups in the Greater Paris area and the city of Marseille. We will be engaging in discussions on the subject of ‘rights’; notably around how rights (and the associated democratic process of establishing and recognising rights) can be scaled to a given context (school, family, workplace, youth association, etc.) – this is a continuation of the themes explored in PAR Cycle 1. We will approach the ‘rights workshop’ from a creative–speculative, socio–political point of view.

PAR Cycle Background and Introduction

Alternatives Européennes will run ChangeLabs in two urban contexts, those of Greater Paris and Marseille. The organisations involved will be diverse, including participants from formal education contexts (a local high school), as well as from non–formal and informal education contexts including youth organisations and sports associations. Building upon the experience of the PAR Cycle 1, we will engage with questions of everyday democracy, such as how rights are expressed, and the scale of impact that can be had through enacting change in localised contexts.

Our organisation works to promote democracy, equality and culture beyond the nation–state and imagine, demand and enact alternatives for a viable future. Thus, we seek to translate this aspect of our work into the ChangeLab context, engaging participants in questioning current practices and seeking alternatives to present–day problems. The wider activity of Alternatives Européennes is often involved in democratic assemblies, co–creating spaces of reflection and activism towards transversal possibilities of change.

By engaging with youth participants, we intend on transforming our political activist expertise into youth–led discussion, context–relevant exercises and solution–driven processes throughout the labs. Involving primarily youth from underrepresented communities, we seek to underline the importance of making space for diverse voices and embodied experiences.

We have chosen to centre our ChangeLab process on the question of rights. Our understanding of rights is that there is an overlapping distinction between “Rights” (as a political entity) and “rights” as a social contract. Evidently, there are well–established notions of Rights as political devices for structuring society, this

includes human rights, recognised as moral principles in support of living standards in various societies internationally. They are prescribed and protected by municipal, national and international laws. Whilst these rights may be felt in daily life, they remain relatively abstract. Thus, our approach seeks to highlight alternative expressions of rights that are experienced on a day-to-day basis – notably the (often unspoken) rights that exist within the framework of school, the workplace, and the family. Rights are not just words on a paper. They are performed and negotiated through lived experience and social practice and can vary greatly according to the context. Our reflection includes recognising the different ways in which rights take shape – how they have evolved and may evolve further, as well as their precariousness. In-line with the Critical ChangeLab Critical Literacies Framework, we will also engage with rights beyond ‘human-human’ relations, including ‘human-nature’ and ‘human-technology’; these are necessary elements of a discussion of rights in modern society. In our ChangeLab, we hope to encourage participants to see rights as active, not passive, social as well as political, and subject to changing socio-political climates, for better or worse.

Stakeholders & target audiences

This is an overview of the general stakeholders that are to be involved over the course of the project. The stakeholders that are made bold are also considered the target audience for the main objectives of the PAR Cycle.

- **Youth (14-18) belonging to youth organisations:** 20
- **Youth (11-18) in a formal education environment (school students):** 20
- Youth workers: 4
- CSO representatives: 2
- Educators (formal and non-formal educational contexts): 4

PAR Cycle Objectives

Key Concepts

Democratic practice & citizenship (UNDERSTANDING)

Challenge

Given that the labs take place in parallel to the youth participants’ secondary education, our objective of suggesting alternative approaches to democratic practice and citizenship will be competing with the traditional approaches they are currently being taught. The challenge will be to distance these more well-

established notions from the creative and speculative discussions intended in the labs.

PAR Cycle Mission

Thus, our mission is to keep our approach as concrete as possible when discussing the notions of democratic processes and rights, by citing real-life examples and eliciting their lived experience of these examples.

Recognizing conflict & contradictions in democratic systems (IDENTIFYING)

Challenge

The challenge of identifying conflict and contradictions entails the challenge of realising what exactly can be considered a conflict in a given context, as well as identifying it as something that may be resolved by a collective response.

PAR Cycle Mission

Our mission is to approach the question of conflict in a way that centres day-to-day experiences, including situations that involve lived experience of “large-scale” problems (such as addiction to social media, disinterest in politics, climate change) as well as “small-scale”-but no less important-problems (within the context of family, school, community, etc.).

Interrogating cultural construction, social, political context and societal transformation (DECONSTRUCTING)

Challenge

The challenge is to deconstruct a well-known, well-established notion that is both abstract (what is a “right” if not words on paper) yet “materially” present (we may be aware of our rights on a daily basis, especially when infringement occurs). Moving from Rights to rights, we seek to change perspectives on how this aspect of political societies come to be, as well as their scalability.

PAR Cycle Mission

By asking participants to look at areas in life where rights (prescribed or otherwise) exist and how they take different forms, we hope to encourage an alternative approach to democratic practices rooted in lived experience and tangible changes. For example, how do rights exist in the family sphere? Are they unspoken, innate, do they evolve or disappear when we get older? In any case, they differ

greatly to those Rights we associate with democracy, political inscription and socio-political struggle – or do they?

Alternative futures (ACTIVATING CHANGE)

Challenge

Questioning the idea that change is brought about only by mass social movements, elections and policy making, instead suggesting a focus on localised, small-scale activism, behavioural change at an individual and collective level and decision-making processes. By providing collective skills, competences and practices to re-conceive problems and imagine and activate alternative futures, the CCLAB enlarges the repertoire of political action for young people, providing them with ways of doing politics that can be used throughout their lives and imagined in a wide variety of contexts.

PAR Cycle Mission

Our mission is to take a playful, speculative approach to alternative futures, both as a means of engaging students in creative-critical thinking and also encouraging them to realise the impact of which they are capable within their local contexts. We will also guide discussion towards real-life exercises that they can implement in their own democratic endeavours.

Please rate the importance of each concept within your PAR Cycle, marking one value per row (1 is lowest, 5 is highest)

	1	2	3	4	5
<i>Democratic practice & citizenship</i>				X	
<i>Recognizing conflict & contradictions</i>					X
<i>Interrogating constructions</i>					X
<i>Alternative futures</i>			X		

Outcomes

Outcome 1: “Whose rights are they anyway?”

The principle intended outcome for AlterEuro’s PAR2 labs is to approach the subject of “rights” in a way that distances the established notion of human rights (as seen in large-scale political spheres, national and international policy), towards rights in less-formal and informal contexts (school, workplace, home, youth organisations, etc.) as well as alternative contexts (human-nature relations, human-technology

relations). In a process of questioning to whom these rights belong, we seek to shift perceptions from rights as an entirely political notion (“Rights”) towards a more intersectional approach of rights as different according to context (e.g., historical, socio-political, ecological). In doing so, participants may discover alternative perspectives that are underrepresented, disregarded or hitherto unvoiced.

Outcome 2: Scales of democracy

The second outcome of EuroAlter’s PAR2 labs is to creatively approach the “scalability” of democracy. This includes critical analysis of Democracy on a large scale (typically associated with political superstructures), and scaling down to micro-democratic contexts, processes and spaces where decisions are made democratically but without necessarily being named so. When negotiating decisions in informal contexts, we may undergo certain democratic exercises such as debating, seeking compromise and voting – this is hopefully something that participants have already experienced throughout their lives (even and especially prior to being able to vote in elections). For example, it may be suggested that the smallest scale democracy is a decision made between two people – such as choosing a restaurant for dinner or which film to watch. Moving “upwards” on the scale, we can recreate and analyse the various democratic processes in which we take part on a more daily basis.

Outcome 3: Degrees of influence

The third outcome is a recognition of the potential for activating change through influence in localised democratic practices. For example, if a youth group (e.g., girls’ football club) is able to effect change in their context, how can they share, sustain and support this change – extending it beyond their immediate context. To do this, we seek to question what can be done by young people to influence their surroundings and to engage in local, “small-scale” activism. Then, if successful, how can they share these successes with their peers (both intra-communal and outside of their circles).

Measuring success of outcomes

These outcomes will be measured by a) beginning the sessions with an oral, written and/or embodied survey of their current (initial) perspectives on the above subjects, then b) reviewing the survey at the final stage, in order to measure change

with regards to their perspectives and opinions of the subject matter, as well as their experiences of the lab itself.

The success criteria, in this case, rely on the participants' expression of an evolution in their thinking or a change in their position regarding the initial phase – the outcomes survey will be designed in a way that still allows the researchers to measure the participants' perspectives even if they don't report any evolution therein, e.g., "did you think differently about the topic but come to the same conclusion?".

Plan and Activities

The plan is to take an alternative, creative approach to the democratic notion of "rights". This will be done by questioning the scalability of "rights", seeking to recognise the power (influence) of small-scale activism and engagement with democratic processes. We expect each lab to take place in different contexts, so the material outcome will be diverse, but a priori we hope to create a text that represents the culmination of our discussion throughout the labs. An example of this is the Chart of Rights and Duties (which could be implemented in the classroom, in the youth club, in a friend group, or more widely).

Phases:

Phase 1: Needs assessment (90 minutes)

In the initial phase of the lab, the researchers will conduct a needs assessment with the stakeholder(s) and participants, in order to better understand their current perspectives and expectations prior to the initial session.

Phase 2: Onboarding and initial session (90 minutes)

This phase is concerned with the introduction to the structure of the labs, as well as to the subject matter, including a survey of the participants current perspectives. Beginning with icebreaker activities, the flow of the session will be driven by participant engagement with the topic. To conclude this phase, the researcher will scaffold the next sessions' activities with the participants.

Phase 3: Core sessions (180 minutes)

The central elements of the Critical Literacy Framework will be applied here, lasting 2-3 sessions (60-90 minutes each); here is where the bulk of the activities (see below) will be implemented.

Phase 4: Final session (90 minutes)

Here participants and stakeholder(s) will engage with the 'activating change' element of the lab process, focusing on the production of a (multimedia) text and discussing its implementation in a real-life context (relevant to participants' situation).

Phase 5: Feedback and reflection (90 minutes)

In the final session of the lab we will conduct a feedback discussion where participants will share their experiences. This includes a return to the survey implemented in the onboarding session. This will not only be verbal but also include creative approaches to giving feedback, such as embodied, movement-based or arts-based responses (moving from point X to point Y to represent a feeling; drawing an image to associate with a particular aspect of the lab).

Activities:

Here is a list of activities to be implemented throughout the Phases, including a brief description of their method and intention.

Activity 1: Alternative Uses

This icebreaker activity seeks to engage participants in a creative approach to the "embracing multiple perspectives" aspect of the Critical Literacies Framework. Participants are asked to think of alternative uses (in a wide sense of the term) for a given object within the context of the lab (e.g., a phone, a pen, a piece of paper, a water bottle, a hairclip). The goal is to invent as many alternative uses as possible, including a description of how this "use" could be enacted.

Activity 2: Perspective-Play

A secondary icebreaker activity, not unlike the 'Alternative Uses' game, where participants will come up with an example situation (e.g., building social housing, starting a band, eating at a restaurant) and try to find as many perspectives (roles) as possible within this context. The objective being an engagement with multiple

perspectives as well as impact (human-human, human-nature, human-technology). For example, a tree is to be chopped down in the local park – what is the impact of this action? What entities will be affected, how and when? Role-playing the tree, the living organisms for whom it is home, the local residents, the municipal politicians, etc.

Activity 3: Pass the problem

Write a problem statement on a piece of paper and pass it to a neighbour. The second person reads the problem and either adds a solution or a secondary, related problem. The goal is to have an asynchronous discussion that engages with multiple perspectives on how a problem exists, evolves and may be solved.

Activity 4: What if...?

This activity is a thought-experiment based on positioning ourselves in the past and imagining what the future might look like (for example, what would 2025 look like from the perspective of those living in 1925). This engages participants with relative, contextualised points of view (those of the past) but encourages reflection of alternative versions of our present day (at the same time alternative futures and alternative presents).

Activity 5: Creation of a Chart of Rights and Duties

The creation of this text will also be context-dependent, but the process is similar in any case. The objective is to consider current problems and the behaviours that cause them to persist. How can these be addressed in a democratic way? To do so we suggest the co-creation (through a writing exercise) of a chart of rights and duties for the given context. For example: participants find that there are too many distractions in the classroom, so they discuss what the principal causes are and seek a possible solution to be enacted as a “right” or “duty” in that context.

Activity 6: What then? What now? What next?

This activity is deployed as a summative assessment of the lab as well as a wrap-up discussion. We will ask what brought us to this topic (context dependent), both from the perspective of the participants (why this choice?) and from a socio-historical perspective (how did this situation arise?). Then, we review what the current situation is, as discussed throughout the lab. Finally, we ask what can be

done moving forward, which will include feasible actions and activities for the participants to undertake post-lab.

Table 3 – Phase Planning

	Oct 2024	Nov 2024	Dec 2024	Jan 2025	Feb 2025
Phase 1					
Phase 2					
Phase 3					
Phase 4					
Phase 5					

Obstacles and mitigation

Table 4 – Obstacles and mitigation

Description	Probability	Impact	Mitigation Measure
<i>Disinterest in the subject</i>	S	S	The labs will be tailored to the interests, problems and immediate contexts (however not necessarily small-scale) that concern the youth participants. Other stakeholders will be encouraged to tailor their input to the topics voiced by the participants.
<i>Lack of pertinence</i>	M	M	Similar to the above, the relevance of the topics will be linked to the choices made by participants, rather than pre-selected or generic topics. Ideally, the chosen subject will be dynamic and flexible throughout the sessions.
<i>Attention span</i>	L	M	To reduce the impact of participants being bored or losing their attention, we will include dynamic, playful activities in each session, tailored to the content and the context.
<i>Abstract concepts</i>	S	S	To avoid the difficulty of abstract concepts such as “rights”, we will

D2.1 Report: Critical ChangeLab cycle 2

			establish our own, free-of-consequence definitions and notions that will be discussed and used throughout the labs.
<i>Power imbalance</i>	M	M	To avoid imbalance in our discussions as well as the wider socio-spatial dynamic of the labs, we will encourage all present (youth, educators, researchers, etc.) to engage equally with the content and activities. This should mitigate the impression of whose voice is more or less important, and distance the lab from the top-down classroom experience.

Institute for Social Research PAR Cycle 2 Plan

We plan to form three groups of young participants for the PAR Cycle, all groups formed from the high school student dormitory youth. Our primary focus will be on educational inequalities, encompassing issues such as gender disparities, inequities based on school program type, student body composition, minority identity, and school location.

PAR Cycle Background and Introduction

We are planning to establish three distinct groups of young participants for the upcoming PAR Cycle, residing in three different high school dormitories in the city of Zagreb.

Our PAR Cycle will primarily address the issue of educational inequalities, a topic of significant concern in Croatia, as well as in many other countries. We aim to explore a broad spectrum of disparities that affect students' educational experiences and outcomes. These include, but are not limited to, gender inequalities that might influence access to certain fields of study or opportunities within the school system. We will also investigate inequities that arise from the type of school program students are enrolled in, as the curriculum and resources available in gymnasiums and VET schools can vary significantly, along with school culture.

Additionally, our PAR Cycle will consider the impact of student body composition, examining how factors like socioeconomic background and the presence of minority groups within a school influence educational outcomes. We will also address the implications of minority identity on a student's educational journey, looking into how cultural, ethnic, or linguistic minority status might contribute to unequal educational opportunities. Lastly, the location of the school, whether urban or rural, and its access to resources, will be another critical focus of our study.

Through this approach, participants will investigate the multifaceted nature of educational inequalities and contribute to the ongoing dialogue on how to create a more equitable educational environment for all students.

We plan to conduct six structured meetings with the participants in the PAR Cycle2. The first meeting will serve as an onboarding session, where we will introduce the participants to the project, outline its objectives, and agree on the key topic (theme)

we will explore throughout the cycle. Participants independently choose the theme on which they want to work on in the PAR Cycle, facilitated by educators. Through the PAR cycle, they will deepen their understanding of educational inequalities and gain a solid foundation for further engagement with the topic.

The second meeting will consist of the Question phase. During this session, participants will collaboratively identify the critical questions related to educational inequalities and prepare for the analyses of the data and experiences that inform these issues.

In the third meeting the participants will work on the Analyse phase, analysing different approaches to selected topic and data and insights about the selected issue.

In the fourth meeting, the participants go through the Envision and Examine phases. This session will focus on envisioning possible solutions or interventions, examining their feasibility, and start to develop concrete steps that can be implemented to address the identified inequalities or their causes.

The fifth meeting will comprise of Act phase, where participants will be encouraged to creatively express their ideas for action, change and solving educational inequalities on the selected topic.

The final, sixth, meeting will be dedicated to reflection. Participants will have the opportunity to reflect on the entire process, discuss the insights they have gained, and evaluate their participation. This reflective session is crucial for consolidating their learning and considering how they might apply their new understanding to future initiatives.

Stakeholders & target audiences

This is an overview of the general stakeholders that are to be involved over the course of the project. The stakeholders that are made **bold** are also considered the target audience for the main objectives of the PAR Cycle.

- representatives from **civil society organizations**, such as Forum for Freedom in Education, Academy for Political Development, Network of Educational

Policy Centers, etc. – their involvement will help ensure that our project aligns with broader community needs

- **Artistic groups** – will contribute to a creative dimension of the project, helping to engage participants in innovative ways and bringing attention to the issues of educational inequality through various forms of artistic expression
- **High school student dormitories** are very important to us, as they directly affect the participants who are included in this PAR Cycle. These institutions will provide a critical context for our PAR Cycle, and their cooperation will be essential in facilitating participation and implementing any actions that arise from our findings
- **Local government** representatives will play an instrumental role in supporting the project's objectives at a policy level. Their involvement might help, as the outcomes of our PAR Cycle might stimulate policies and initiatives that address educational inequalities on a broader scale.

Stakeholders will be involved in various ways, depending on their profile. Some will share their expertise during certain meetings (e.g., representatives of civil society organizations), offer new ways of addressing educational inequality issues through creative activities (artistic groups), or listen to the solutions participants develop and discuss with them the possibilities and methods for implementing these solutions (local government representatives).

PAR Cycle Objectives

Key Concepts

Democratic practice & citizenship (understanding)

Challenge

Key challenges include ensuring participant motivation, managing their attrition, and securing educators' willingness and readiness to facilitate the process. Maintaining participant engagement is vital, as low motivation and high attrition can undermine the democratic principles of the project. Educators may need support and training to confidently adopt the PAR methodology. Additionally, integrating the PAR Cycle into the participants' dormitory schedule is another

challenge, due to time constraints in dormitories and participants' school schedules, requiring a flexible approach to ensure it complements, rather than disrupts, their daily life and schedule.

PAR Cycle Mission

Our mission here is to cultivate an inclusive and democratic educational environment by fostering participant motivation and sustained engagement in the PAR Cycle. We aim to support educators with the necessary training and resources to facilitate this process, ensuring that they can effectively guide participants in exploring and addressing critical issues. We are committed to integrating the PAR Cycle into the student dormitory schedule in a flexible manner. Some of the educators who will carry out the activities have already been the collaborators of the Institute for Social Research in Zagreb, and some of them are new to the project. However, prior to the implementation of PAR activities, meetings will be organized to discuss the methods and dynamics of implementation. During these meetings, a needs assessment related to support for preparation of meetings and detailed introduction with work methods will also be conducted. Based on this, the educators will be able to propose methods they consider more suitable, as well as to get instructions related to the implementation of methods planned by the ISRZ team.

Recognizing conflict & contradictions in democratic systems (identifying)

Challenge

Participants often perceive contradictions in power dynamics, whether at the micro-level or within broader society, as 'natural.' This perception can make it difficult for them to recognize and critically engage with conflicts related to power relations, such as those between youth and adults or within school settings.

PAR Cycle Mission

Our mission is to raise awareness of social inequalities, contradictions, and their roots, fostering the development of critical thinking. By encouraging participants to explore power relations in everyday life and at a societal level, we aim to empower them to recognize and challenge these dynamics.

Interrogating cultural construction, social, political context and societal transformation (deconstructing)

Challenge

Participants may struggle to critically examine the deeply embedded cultural, social, and political constructs that shape their perceptions and behaviours. This can be compounded by a lack of understanding of how these constructs influence societal transformations, making it difficult for them to question and deconstruct these norms within their own contexts. Additionally, confronting these issues might provoke resistance or discomfort, as it challenges established beliefs and values present in their cultural and social environments.

PAR Cycle Mission

Our mission is to empower participants to critically interrogate the cultural, social, and political constructs that shape their worldviews. We aim to provide them with the tools and knowledge to understand how these constructs influence societal transformations. By fostering a safe and reflective environment, we seek to encourage participants to challenge and deconstruct established norms, enabling them to actively participate in shaping a more equitable and inclusive society.

Alternative futures (activating change)

PAR Cycle Mission

Same as above.

Please rate the importance of each concept within your PAR Cycle, marking one value per row (1 is lowest, 5 is highest)

	1	2	3	4	5
<i>Democratic practice & citizenship</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Recognizing conflict & contradictions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Interrogating constructions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Alternative futures</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Outcomes

Outcomes

Outcome 1: Knowledge and critical understanding of the world

We aim at raising awareness and developing competencies for critical thinking, be it critical self-reflection or critical understanding of the society (world), based on

some basic knowledge that we aim to provide participants about social and educational inequalities, and the relation with their own life.

Outcome 2: Transformative agency

On the basis of Outcome 1, we aim to empower participants to think outside the usual thinking path and challenge them to envision some possibilities for change and transformation. The transformative role can encompass individual level, mezzo level (e.g. school setting, local government) and macro level (state level). We aim at encouraging participants to transform old patterns into new ones, based on desired outcome (educational or societal).

Outcome 3: Creative competences

In line with the previous, we decided to stress creativity and creative competences as our important outcomes. We understand creativity not only in the manner of creative outputs (artefacts), but also as a creativity in the way of thinking and creativity of cognitive processes, combined with affective moment which activates the imagination and emotions related to possible change.

Plan and Activities

Activities

Activity 1: Title

Life in years exercise – Aimed at getting to know one another. In a box there are folded paper pieces with different years written on them. Participants take turn picking a paper and everybody shares one thing related to what happened in their life in that year, what were they doing (achievements, milestones, important events etc.). Materials used: paper pieces, box/bowl to place the pieces.

Activity 2: Title

Futures triangle: PUSH OF THE PRESENT – Discussions based on the mirror material, with some guiding questions related to the chosen theme. Documenting initial thoughts and ideas. Questions to consider: Where is the world now heading and how can we make a difference? What processes of change are underway? What is currently pushing us to change ourselves or to change things around us? These include trends and other changes in society and people's lives. Materials used: mirror material, post its and pens, futures triangle print.

Activity 3: Title

Futures triangle: WEIGHT OF THE PAST – Connecting the tensions to societal level, historically developed contradictions. Questions to consider: What kinds of limitations and obstacles does past impose on us? What prevents us from moving forward? These may include different commitments, persistent beliefs and unsustainable worldviews, values or ways of thinking. Materials used: Futures triangle, suggestions of websites and other material, post its, pens.

Activity 4: Title

Futures triangle: PULL OF THE FUTURE – Discussions Imagining possible futures. What are our images of the future? What is the best thing that could happen? We can consider different dreams, plans, visions and their feasibility. Can continue with other activities, for example making. Materials used: futures triangle, post its, pens material for making.

Activity 5: Title

Speculative Design – Participants are encouraged to envision their preferred future (e.g., where there is no certain issue or problem) through two processes: exploration and visualisation. During the exploration process, participants engage in an investigation of potential innovative approaches for designing the solution to the problem (e.g., the use of VR, AI, or other uses of digital technology). In the next step, using the form of expression chosen by the participants themselves, participants visualise and create their solution/preferred future. Materials used: tools and materials needed as a chosen form of expression.

Table 3 – Activity Planning

	Aug 2024	Sep 2024	Oct 2024	Nov 2024	Dec 2024	Jan 2025
Act 1					x	
Act 2					x	
Act 3					x	
Act 4						x
Act 5						x

Obstacles and mitigation

Table 4 – Obstacles and mitigation

Description	Probability	Impact	Mitigation Measure
Participant motivation	S	S	Incorporate dynamic and interactive activities linked to real-life situations that are both useful and entertaining; Organize outdoor activities such as fieldwork, visits to institutions, exhibitions, or other engaging events to make the process more stimulating
Participants' attrition	S	S	We planned for a surplus of participants to account for possible attrition due to illness or other unforeseen reasons
Educators' readiness for the PAR Cycle and their competences to facilitate the process	M	M	We planned additional support and training for educators prior to every meeting with participants so they might confidently adopt the PAR methodology and ideas; we provide backup for educators in every PAR session if needed (consultation during sessions, joined activities..)

Ars Electronica PAR Cycle 2 Plan

Open Lab

PAR Cycle 2 at Ars Electronica will take form as a Podcast Open Lab where tools and methods already used on PAR Cycle 1 will be reinvented to reach a more creative outcome and engage participants with the whole process.

PAR Cycle Background and Introduction

The Ars Electronica Festival (Linz, Upper Austria, 4 – 8 September) will host PAR Cycle 2 of the Critical ChangeLab. Build upon the experience of the first iteration, the second one will repeat some of the tools and methods but will be more flexible in terms of session structure and will give more protagonism to art and the creative process.

Thus, Ars Electronica will set up an OpenLab in which participants will be invited through different stations to design, write and produce a podcast about a speculative future imagined by themselves. It is worth noting that this year's festival theme *HOPE – who will turn the tide*, provides a fantastic context for participants to draw inspiration from and reflect on speculative futures.

To this end, 10–15 young people from 5 different countries will be the core participants, while Upper Austrian associations will invite their networks to participate in a more flexible way.

In addition, further synergies with local actors will be developed, as a collaboration with the student's union of one of the local universities, the Johannes Kepler University Linz, and the national youth radio station FM4 is planned.

Stakeholders & target audiences

This is an overview of the general stakeholders that are to be involved over the course of the project. The stakeholders that are made **bold** are also considered the target audience for the main objectives of the PAR Cycle.

- For this second iteration **create your world** will be again one of the stakeholders, as the CCLAB activities will be framed within its program at Ars Electronica Festival 2024.

- **Jugendbegegnungsprojekt** (Youth Exchange Project) will be visiting Ars Electronica Festival and taking the chance to participate on the Critical ChangeLab through the OpenLab set up for the occasion. Thus, 10-15 teenagers from 4 different countries (Austria, Hungary, Ireland and Romania) will take part in this second PAR Cycle.
- FM4 – national youth radio station will be offering equipment and technical expertise to the participants.
- Student's union of JKU master's degree Political Science – a workshop with the student's union is planned to reflect on process and methods of PAR Cycle 2

PAR Cycle Objectives

Key Concepts

Democratic practice & citizenship (understanding)

Challenge

Often when you ask a teenager what democracy is, they answer that it is about the right to vote your representatives, leaving aside all questions related to their participation in the decisions of everyday life.

PAR Cycle Mission

To make the participants understand the strength of their agency, making them take decisions in different situations proposed throughout the sessions.

Recognizing conflict & contradictions in democratic systems (identifying)

Challenge

At a time when it seems that all possibilities are within our reach, it is difficult to make people understand, especially those who are not politically engaged, the contradictions that the system we live in can have.

PAR Cycle Mission

To confront participants with diverse perspectives. so that they can understand the challenges and complexities of contemporary society.

Interrogating cultural construction, social, political context and societal transformation (deconstructing)

Challenge

Making it apparent that there is a manifold of perspectives on societal issues.

PAR Cycle Mission

Through the different methods used, the aim is to activate empathy and critical thinking so that participants can become aware of the conflicts in our society.

Alternative futures (activating change)

Challenge

Making participants think beyond the status quo.

PAR Cycle Mission

The mission of this cycle is to allow participants to think about possible and impossible futures and relate them to their own everyday life and agency.

Please rate the importance of each concept within your PAR Cycle, marking one value per row (1 is lowest, 5 is highest)

	1	2	3	4	5
Democratic practice & citizenship	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Recognizing conflict & contradictions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Interrogating constructions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Alternative futures	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Outcomes

Outcome 1: to encourage participants to think and reflect critically on the society around them and the future that is being built to familiarise them with their own agency and to engage them with the tools they need to build alternatives to that future.

Outcome 2: to familiarise participants with the stages of the creative process, starting with reflection, acquiring a perspective and searching for answers.

Outcome 3: to make participants understand artistic expression as a tool for individual and collective reflection.

All of the outcomes will be reflected in the participant’s podcast episodes. Based on the collaborative reflections on the current state of society and its contradictions,

every participant / group will create a podcast episode, where they express their opinions, speculate about their vision of the future and think about solutions that can be implemented.

Plan and Activities

This PAR Cycle will include an OpenLab to be carried out throughout the Ars Electronica Festival, mainly with around 15 participants from 5 different countries. Local participants have been invited, exact number TBA. All participants will participate in all activities but as the CCLAB progresses there are more options, e.g. participants can, but don't have to do interviews with festival visitors.

Activities

Activity 1: *Frischer Wind*

First activity of this PAR Cycle will be the first episode of a Podcast series called *Frischer Wind* (Fresh air), designed, written and produced by the Viennese participants of the Critical ChangeLab PAR Cycle 1.

Activity 2: **OpenLab at Ars Electronica Festival 2024**

Each day of the OpenLab (Activities A-F) will be opened by an icebreaker activity to start the participants thinking about the main topics of the project – democracy, activism, participation within defined thematic clusters (technology, environment, gender, education etc.). The first days will follow a more structured approach to ease the participants into a more self-sufficient working style on the later days. Additionally, we encourage peer-to-peer learning (with assistance if needed). The five Critical ChangeLab sessions will take place in a room set up for the Jugendbegegnungsprojekt at the main venue of the Ars Electronica Festival.

A – Onboarding

An online meeting is held in August to welcome the participants of the youth exchange project and introduce them to the Critical ChangeLab Project. Participants of PAR Cycle 1 (the aforementioned *Frischer Wind* group) will share their experiences, challenges and approach with the young people in a peer-to-peer approach (moderated and supported by AE)

B – OpenLab – Introduction to Podcasting

For the first session with the 15 participants, we will start with a session about technical know-how in podcasting, provided by national youth radio station, FM4, and an input session about creating content by an expert, so that they can keep it in mind during the whole process.

C – OpenLab – The Future Exhibition

This activity developed in PAR Cycle 1, will on this occasion be extended by inviting participants to visit some of the projects exhibited at the Ars Electronica Festival. In this way they will not only be aware of how the future has been seen over the years in pop culture, as happened at PAR Cycle 1, but also become familiar with art as a tool to imagine other futures.

They will be given a series of terms (such as gender, environment, technology) to think about how they are reflected in the different works and projects.

The participants will also conduct interviews with festival visitors, artists etc. To gain insights into a variety of perspectives on the topics. This also serves as an empathy exercise that can help them to identify contradictions in the present socioeconomic system.

D – OpenLab – Coming up with a concept and Research

This session will focus on coming up with a concept or idea for their podcast. They will also have time and materials to do some research on the topic they want to talk about. The research activities will be framed in the context of open access to knowledge and democratic principles by the facilitators.

E – OpenLab – Script writing

This will follow a very open approach, where participants can work collectively or alone and write a script where they will express their reflections and conclusions after the first sessions to create a podcast episode about their vision of the future. They will have the space and the necessary materials (e.g., planning templates) for this, but facilitators only step in when asked for help.

F – OpenLab – Podcast production

For the last session of the OpenLab, participants will have access to the podcast production station that *create your world* has made available at the Ars Electronica

Festival. With the help of a professional technician, they will start recording the previously prepared script and then post produce (edit, include interviews from the first day, for example) with the program Descript, a user-friendly audio-editing-program. Finished podcasts will be published on the Frischer Wind Spotify channel. As other sessions, this one will not have a fixed schedule, letting participants take their time and letting other potential participants that might visit the festival be part of the process.

G – OpenLab – Feedback / Wrapping up

On the last day there will be a session to give the participants a chance to reflect on their process, the outcomes and overall experience and collect valuable feedback for coming CCLABs, The focus group will be incorporated in this session.

Activity 3: Critical Change Conference

Organized and moderated by the Viennese group that participated on PAR Cycle 1, who are also producing the podcast series 'Frischer Wind' ('Fresh Air'), the conference will open with interviews with experts in which the status quo is critiqued and examined. On this basis, the audience will then discuss with other experts, artists, intellectuals, politicians and young people the possibility of changing the world. Ideally, the conference will end with new perspectives on alternatives and possible paths towards changing and reshaping the world.

Activity 4: Sharing the CCLAB with students enrolled in a Political Education Master's Degree in Linz

The researcher will go on the next Semester to the Johannes Kepler University in Linz to share with at least 10 Political Education Master students the experience of the project. As future educators, although some of them are already professional educators, the researcher will show them how the first two PAR Cycles took place, including tools, material, design process and participants evaluation, so that they can give their feedback on the pedagogical perspective of the project.

Activity 5: Second Part of PAR Cycle 2 with students of HTL Spengergasse

Detailed in second PAR plan (see below)

Table 3 – Activity Planning

Please indicate (by placing an X or changing the cell to a different colour) when each activity will take place during your PAR Cycle.

	Aug 2024	Sep 2024	Oct 2024	Nov 2024	Dec 2024	Jan 2025
Act 1	x					
Act 2	x	x				
Act 3		x				
Act 4						x
Act 5					x	x

Obstacles and mitigation

Table 4 – Obstacles and mitigation

Description	Probability	Impact	Mitigation Measure
Conducting the CCLAB in English when not all the participants are native speakers	M	L	Various researchers will be present to support them when needed and to moderate any conversation if necessary.
Bringing together participants with different cultural and educational backgrounds	S	M	Various researchers will be present to support them when needed and to moderate any conversation if necessary.
Time management	S	S	This PAR Cycle has been designed to be more flexible than the first one, giving more room for reflection and to create a more concrete outcome.

Spengergasse

The second part of PAR 2 taking place at a secondary school in Vienna will focus on expressing participant’s opinions and ideas on the topic “envisioning futures” through podcasts. HTL Spengergasse is a secondary school in Vienna with a focus on technology. Students can choose a focus point (IT, engineering, game design, media design etc.) and get a hands-on education in the chosen area alongside a general education. In the PAR cycle sessions participants will be invited to design, write and produce a podcast about their perspective on tensions in society and what the future will bring.

Stakeholders & target audiences

This is an overview of the general stakeholders that are to be involved over the course of the project. The stakeholders that are made **bold** are also considered the target audience for the main objectives of the PAR Cycle.

- HTL Spengergasse: **students of the media design class** at HTL Spengergasse, a secondary school with a focus on technology
- Peer to peer input / Participants cycle 1
- Student's union of JKU master's degree Political Education – a workshop with members of the student's union is planned to reflect on process and methods of PAR Cycle 2 at HTL Spengergasse

PAR Cycle Objectives

Key Concepts

Democratic practice & citizenship (understanding

Challenge

At a time when it seems that all possibilities are within our reach, it is difficult to make people understand, especially those who are not politically engaged, the contradictions that the system we live in can have.

PAR Cycle Mission

To make them confront situations where inequality is evident so that they can understand the challenges of contemporary society.

Recognizing conflict & contradictions in democratic systems (identifying)

Challenge

At a time when it seems that all possibilities are within our reach, it is difficult to make people understand, especially those who are not politically engaged, the contradictions that the system we live in can have.

PAR Cycle Mission

To confront participants with diverse perspectives. so that they can understand the challenges and complexities of contemporary society.

Interrogating cultural construction, social, political context and societal transformation (deconstructing)

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Challenge

Making it apparent that there is a manifold of perspectives on societal issues.

PAR Cycle Mission

Through the different methods used, the aim is to activate empathy and critical thinking so that participants can become aware of the conflicts and complexities in our society.

Alternative futures (activating change)

Challenge

Making participants think beyond the status quo.

PAR Cycle Mission

The mission of this cycle is to allow participants to think about possible and impossible futures, and relate them to their own everyday life and agency.

Please rate the importance of each concept within your PAR Cycle, marking one value per row (1 is lowest, 5 is highest)

	1	2	3	4	5
<i>Democratic practice & citizenship</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Recognizing conflict & contradictions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Interrogating constructions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Alternative futures</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Outcomes

Outcomes

Outcome 1: to encourage participants to think and reflect critically on the society around them and the future that is being built to familiarise them with their own agency and to engage them with the tools they need to build alternatives to that future.

Outcome 2: to familiarise participants with the stages of the creative process, starting with reflection, acquiring a perspective and searching for answers.

Outcome 3: to make participants understand artistic expression as a tool for individual and collective reflection.

All of the outcomes will be reflected in the participant’s podcast episodes. Based on the collaborative reflections on the current state of society and its contradictions, every participant / group will create a podcast episode, where they express their opinions, speculate about their vision of the future and think about solutions that can be implemented.

Plan and Activities

Action plan

The plan and activities are identical to the Open Lab plan, detailed above.

Obstacles and mitigation

Description	Probability	Impact	Mitigation Measure
Low interest of the students due to their advanced knowledge of media production (podcasts being perceived as not advanced enough)	S	M	Extensive needs assessment with the school/teacher to get a grasp of how students engaged with audio-media before; additionally, engaging methods are being implemented to engage participants in complex discussion that are interesting to them beyond the medium podcast
Time management - especially the postproduction of the podcast might take longer than foreseen	M	M	Close monitoring of the time management in each session, as well as participants’ skill level to see if more time has to be allocated for postproduction; using an easy and intuitively to use tool for post-production; it has been agreed with the teacher that more time can be allocated to the 3 rd session if necessary
School as an inherently undemocratic environment	S	S	Providing sufficient time and a safe space for discussion and reflection, while not enforcing ‘school rules’ (being quiet, sitting still etc.)

Kersnikova PAR Cycle 2 Plan

In PAR Cycle 2 we will work with 9–14-year-old children in a non-formal education context. It will be an open-lab environment where children will develop a technological solution to a problem they recognize in their environment.

PAR Cycle Background and Introduction

The second PAR Cycle will build upon the first one. The changes are the following: Participants of PAR Cycle one were regular attendees of the workshops at Kersnikova who were selected and invited by the mentor community, while the second PAR cycle will be open to any children in this age range that apply for the workshop via our communication channels. The focus of the first PAR cycle was democracy in school, technology and nature. This time we will focus more on addressing a particular problem the participants recognize in their environment with a technological solution in form of a gadget they will design during workshops. Democracy, as we understand it, isn't just people voting during elections, but every practice where people engage in the society with the purpose of improving common good. The participants will engage in one such action of their own choosing and by doing this develop active citizenship. Mentors will put the chosen topic into the context of democracy and encourage reflection among participants. Participants will also be developing critical attitude to technologies they use, access to knowledge and learn about open-source software and hardware through hands-on activities and practical examples.

Stakeholders & target audiences

This is an overview of the general stakeholders that are to be involved over the course of the project. The stakeholders that are made **bold** are also considered the target audience for the main objectives of the PAR Cycle.

1. Mentor community at Kersnikova
2. Center Rog
3. Osmo/za
4. **Youth (9-14) who applied for the workshop**

PAR Cycle Objectives

Key Concepts

Democratic practice & citizenship (understanding)

Challenge

How can participants as young children recognize they have a role in democracy. How can they experience democratic practice as something they can actively participate in?

PAR Cycle Mission

First step towards active citizenship is empowering people, especially young people with the idea that they can contribute to a change in society. We hope to achieve it by giving them an opportunity and means to do so in practice.

Recognizing conflict & contradictions in democratic systems (identifying)

Challenge

Children are rarely interested in politics and if they do think about current societal issues they usually adopt viewpoints of their parents.

PAR Cycle Mission

Encourage critical thinking, awareness of inequalities, sustainability concerns, especially in their use of technology. Focus on their experience and give them the opportunity to build on them.

Interrogating cultural construction, social, political context and societal transformation (deconstructing)

Challenge

Transforming society usually isn't possible without understanding complex relations and social context that shape it. This is a high barrier for young people.

PAR Cycle Mission

In this PAR cycle we focus on de-constructing our relation to technology. How accessible is technology, are we using it in the right way for the right goals?

Alternative futures (activating change)

Challenge

D2.1 Report: Critical ChangeLab cycle 2

New technologies often put people in the position of passive consumers. Demystifying technologies and granting access to knowledge can change this.

PAR Cycle Mission

Empower the participants with technical skills that can help them actively improve their environment and society, as well as ability to work together in doing so.

Please rate the importance of each concept within your PAR Cycle, marking one value per row (1 is lowest, 5 is highest)

	1	2	3	4	5
Democratic practice & citizenship	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Recognizing conflict & contradictions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Interrogating constructions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Alternative futures	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Outcomes

Outcome 1: Participants develop awareness of the concept of opensource hardware/software, how it relates to ecology, inclusivity and access to knowledge.

Outcome 2: Participants recognize themselves as peers in a democratic learning process. They apply sharing of knowledge in practice and learn to work in a team.

Outcome 3: Participants recognize a problem with one aspect of their daily life or society around them and apply their newly acquired knowledge as well as open source technology in preparing a prototype gadget/action they present on a public event Haip park 2024.

Plan and Activities

During this PAR cycle the idea is to establish a community of young participants (9-14 years) who will work on a project that addresses one of the issues they identify in their environment/society. The workshops will take place weekly at Kersnikova Institute (in Rampa lab - a maker-space equipped with 3d printers, laser cutter and similar equipment). Par cycle will encourage sharing knowledge between the children as well as between mentors skilled in STEAM and children.

Activities

Activity 1: Onboarding session

Participants discover the CCLAB workshop concept and they get the overview of the themes that are crucial for the PAR Cycle. They engage in ice breaker activities and group work to get to know each other and the mentors. They are encouraged to share information on things they are passionate about in free form presentations to develop peer2peer sharing skills.

Materials: paper, whiteboard, pens...

Activity 2: Hackathon

In a debate the participants recognise one aspect of society/everyday life that they want to change. The solution has to be in form of some technological device that they imagine. Working in groups the participants engage in brainstorming and rapid prototyping a model of the solution to a problem. The participants are required to adhere to one of the topics : sustainability, inclusivity and technology and well-being. Mentors can suggest some issues/topics if the participants can't identify them on their own. Final choice of the project idea is left to participants.

Materials: whiteboards, pen, paper, computers, crafting material.

Activity 3: Exploring micro controllers

Through hands on experiments participants learn what Arduino platform is, what it can do. They learn about different types of sensors and actuators - they reflect on how they could incorporate it in the solution of their problem as defined in previous session. During this session the mentors will also try to assess the participants understanding of the problem in society they are addressing and provide activities to help them analyse it.

Material: Electronic components Arduino Uno boards, sensors, actuators, breadboards...

Activity 4: Designing the gadget/prototype

After sketching out the device the participants make a list of required material and development, in this they are guided by the mentor. Participants then prototype their gadget or some of its features on breadboards.

Materials: pen, paper, material from the previous workshop.

Activity 5: Developing the prototypes

Through hands on activities participants learn the basics of KiCad software for pcb design and how to “hack” it – use it for artistic purposes. With the help of mentors they draw a schematic and make the layout of their device.

Materials: computers.

Activity 6: Designing a message

The gadget will include some message or graphics that communicate the problem they are addressing. Participants will learn how to design it with Inkscape, open source software for vector graphics. Participants will think about how images/ messages convey their ideas about the change they want to make/be in the society.

Materials: computers

Activity 7: Finalizing prototypes

Participants will continue working on their prototype, they will be encouraged to democratically split work between themselves, recognize their respective skillsets and learn how to make decisions as a team. Mentors will provide technological support. Material will depend on the type of the project the participants chose.

Materials: computers, other materials as needed

Activity 8: Testing the prototypes in practice

Mentors and participants resolve technical issues, if any, test the prototype (possibly in the desired environment) and reflect on the finished prototype: is it successful in helping with the problem? Is it a sustainable solution? Do they like it, or would they iterate on the design? Have participants learned anything during the process and recognized themselves as a part of democratic process? An overview of all prior activities will be made and participants will be encouraged to find links to democracy in the nature of opens–source ideology, their own decision making as well as their prototype/action.

Activity 9: Presenting the work

During the last session that is followed by a public presentation, the participants prepare presentations of their prototype (if time doesn't allow for a finished prototype, a well presented idea is considered a satisfactory outcome) that will be

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held at Haip park 2024 event hosted by Osmo/za gallery. They are encouraged to find a creative way of presentation through games, performance, video, etc. In developing a presentation they are encouraged to think about adult centrism.

Table 3 - Activity Planning

	Aug 2024	Sep 2024	Oct 2024	Nov 2024	Dec 2024	Jan 2025
Act 1			x			
Act 2			x			
Act 3			x			
Act 4				x		
Act 5				x		
Act 6				x		
Act 7				x		
Act 8					x	
Act 9					x	
Act 10						

Obstacles and mitigation

Table 4 - Obstacles and mitigation

Description	Probability	Impact	Mitigation Measure
Time constraints	M	L	Assessing and tailoring activities between sessions, prolongation of the workshops?
Unwillingness to work in groups	M	M	Ice-breaker activities
Conflicting ideas on important concepts.	S	L	Discussing concepts together in groups . Activities for negotiation skills.
Technical difficulties with materials or equipment	S	L	Have backup materials and plan for contingencies

Waag Futurelab PAR Cycle 2 Plan

In Par cycle 2 we will work with fourth-year VMBO students on a costume that represents their identity. They must work together equally on a product, which automatically requires them to apply all kinds of democratic principles.

PAR Cycle Background and Introduction

In par cycle 1 we worked with children who did not speak the Dutch language and have little background knowledge about democracy. This par cycle we choose to work with fourth-year VMBO students within the subject of history, art, philosophy and humanism. The VMBO students will take their final exams for the first time next year and democracy has become an important knowledge domain. This makes it extra important. That is why the school is interested in the Critical Change Lab. We will have to find a balance between artistic objectives and final objectives that concern knowledge about democracy and the rule of law. It is important to us that students experience democracy. Because we did not really take the step towards the future in Par cycle 1, we want to pay more attention to that this time. We hope that, as they grow older, these children will know more about democracy and will therefore link democratic cooperation to society outside the classroom. We also hope that they can imagine the future of democracy and represent this in their costume.

Stakeholders & target audiences

The stakeholders who play a role in the development of Par cycle 2 are: 4VMBO students and teachers of the Corderius College and developers of the course of the Corderius College. The stakeholders needs are: The teachers have a strong need for engaging education on democracy for the target group of vocational education (VMBO). They have a new subject that combines social studies, philosophy, and cultural and artistic education (CKV), and are looking for ways to effectively implement this. They are in need of new teaching methods to increase student engagement. The students' need is to receive more meaningful education where they are allowed to create.

Target audience are: teachers and school management of the Corderius College and the VMBO 4 students of the Corderius College

- Teachers Corderius college

- Developers course Corderius college
- School management Corderius college
- VMBO 4 students

PAR Cycle Objectives

Key Concepts

Democratic practice & citizenship (understanding)

Challenge: The challenge in understanding democratic practice and citizenship is to link classroom experience to social issues from democratic practice. Are the students able to link their own experience of collaboration to structures and rules in society?

PAR Cycle Mission: The mission is to give them a small experience through democracy so that they realize that this is what happens in society. We want them to realize that democracy is more than voting once every four years and that it is not something we should leave to politicians, but that they themselves are the democracy.

Recognizing conflict & contradictions in democratic systems (identifying)

Challenge: The challenge in recognizing conflict & contradictions in democratic systems is that we ask students to reflect in a rather abstract way. They are in a school context where many conversations are intended to test whether they have acquired knowledge about certain topics. We want to see through an open and free conversation whether they are able to recognize advantages, disadvantages, contradictions, etc., in society. Creating an environment in which students feel comfortable/safe in expressing their opinions is a major challenge in this project.

PAR Cycle Mission: The mission is that students engage in open and free dialogue about the contradictions and the pros and cons of a democratic system and that they are free from each other's judgments.

Interrogating cultural construction, social, political context and societal transformation (deconstructing)

Challenge: The big challenge is that they can even comprehend culture, politics, and society as concepts and see that this all has to do with themselves. Are the

students able to recognize their own role?

PAR Cycle Mission: The mission is that students are able to recognize that they play a role in critically questioning political, cultural, and social issues.

Alternative futures (activating change)

Challenge: The challenge is enabling students to envision and actively participate in creating alternative futures. Can they move beyond current paradigms to imagine and work towards a different democratic future?

PAR Cycle Mission: The mission is to empower students to actively engage in shaping their future by applying democratic principles creatively and collaboratively.

Please rate the importance of each concept within your PAR Cycle, marking one value per row (1 is lowest, 5 is highest)

	1	2	3	4	5
<i>Democratic practice & citizenship</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Recognizing conflict & contradictions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Interrogating constructions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Alternative futures</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Outcomes

Outcomes

Outcome 1: Students realize that they themselves are a democracy and that their behaviours and interactions influence what our society is like.

Outcome 2: Students feel that they matter, experience a perspective for action, and know they can intervene when they notice injustice.

Outcome 3: Students understand and apply democratic principles in decision-making processes, realizing the importance of their role in a democratic society.

We gain insight into these outcomes by having them create mood boards, a design, and a product, while also reflecting in writing throughout the process. We hope to gain understanding of their work process and their thoughts on it.

Plan and Activities

In our PAR Cycle, we will engage students in designing and creating a uniform that represents their collective identity. This process will involve three sessions where students will explore identity, collaborate democratically, and create a final product. Through these activities, they will experience and reflect on democratic principles in action.

Activities

Activity 1: Teacher Onboarding Session

We begin with an essential onboarding session for teachers to familiarize them with the program and prepare them for parallel implementation. In this session, we introduce the program's objectives, share insights and feedback from the pilot program, and discuss how to adapt it for their students. We involve teachers in co-creating the upcoming workshops, encouraging their input and ideas. To ensure the program's relevance, we invite a few students to share their perspectives and help tailor the activities, making the session collaborative and inclusive.

Materials Needed:

- Program outline
- Feedback reports from the pilot program
- Co-creation tools (e.g., sticky notes, whiteboards)
- Discussion guidelines

Activity 2: Identity Exploration

In the first student workshop, we dive into identity exploration. We start with a discussion on what identity means and how it can be visually represented. Students engage in group discussions about their personal identities, sharing experiences and key aspects that make them unique. Using "Exactitudes" photos (<https://exactitudes.com/>), we analyse how people express their identities through clothing and accessories. Students then bring objects that represent their identity and create visual representations. We capture these moments with a photo session, providing a tangible and reflective start to our journey.

Materials Needed:

- Exactitudes photos
- Objects for personal representation

- Photo printer
- Cameras

Activity 3: Democratic Design

Next, we introduce democratic principles and their importance in decision-making. Students draw lots to determine the materials for their uniform designs, introducing an element of fairness. They then collaborate using democratic tools like voting and consensus to make design choices. This phase emphasizes inclusivity and the practical application of democracy as students work together to create a design that represents their collective identity.

Materials Needed:

- Overalls for each student
- Various art supplies (e.g., fabric paint, markers, patches)
- Democratic instrument cards (e.g., voting cards, consensus tools)

Activity 4: Final Design and Creation

In the third session, we review the previous designs, gather feedback, and make necessary adjustments. Students then finalize and create their uniform designs, using sewing and crafting techniques. This hands-on phase ensures that the design process is inclusive, allowing every student to contribute and see their ideas come to life. A photoshoot captures the final product, celebrating their collaborative effort.

Materials Needed:

- Final design materials (e.g., sewing kits, fabric)
- Cameras and photo equipment

Activity 5: Reflection and Presentation

Our final activity involves reflecting on the entire process and presenting the final products. Students discuss their learnings about democracy and identity, sharing insights on how their understanding has evolved. Each group presents their uniform and the design journey to the class and invited guests. This session not only highlights their achievements but also reinforces the democratic principles they've practiced. We conclude by gathering feedback to refine and improve future cycles, ensuring the program's continuous development.

Materials Needed:

- Presentation materials (e.g., slides, posters)
- Feedback forms

Activity 6: Internal and project evaluation

After completing the workshops, we will schedule an evaluation with the teachers, students, and our internal project team to reflect, assess, and identify areas for improvement for the next time.

Table 3 – Activity Planning

	Aug 2024	Sep 2024	Oct 2024	Nov 2024	Dec 2024	Jan 2025
Act 1			x			
Act 2				x		
Act 3				x		
Act 4					x	
Act 5						x
Act 6						x

Obstacles and mitigation

Table 4 – Obstacles and mitigation

Description	Probability	Impact	Mitigation Measure
Students not engaging or participating fully	M	M	Create engaging activities and ensure inclusive facilitation
Limited understanding of democratic principles	M	M	Provide clear explanations and relatable examples
Conflict between creative process and ‘school process’	S	M	Agreeing on different rules within these Critical Change Lab hours.
The involvement of the teachers and their needs that do not relate to our needs (final exams)	M	H	Speak out and stay in communication
Organisational difficulties with materials etc.	S	L	Have backup ideas when the different stations in the hall is not working

University of Barcelona PAR Cycle 2 Plans

NB: While UB conducted three labs, only one plan was produced for the BAU lab as the second lab was added later.

BAU

In the UB case, we will carry out two implementations of the PAR cycle 2 in two different institutions. The present document presents the plan for implementing PAR cycle 2 at BAU College of Arts and Design of Barcelona.

PAR Cycle Background and Introduction

The PAR Cycle will be implemented at BAU College of Arts and Design, a private arts and design college in El Poble Nou, Barcelona. El Poble Nou is a district characterised by the 22@, an urban planning initiative that started in the early 2000s aimed at hosting and fostering innovation hubs and start-ups in the city.

The PAR cycle will be conducted with a group of 26 first-year students enrolled in the Degree in Design program. Specifically, the PAR cycle will be integrated into the Sociocultural Anthropology course, a compulsory subject in the first academic year of the degree. At this stage in their academic journey, the students have not yet chosen their specialisation area, so the group consists of prospective graphic, audio-visual, fashion, and interior design students. The group is comprised of young people aged 17-18, the majority of whom are girls (this is a forecast based on previous cohorts, as concrete demographic data is not yet available).

The cycle is aimed at fostering basic research skills and guiding the participants in investigating a social problem of their interest. From an intersectional perspective, participants will be encouraged to critically reflect on the privilege-oppression relationships and social structures they are embedded in to identify the research topic, that will be collaboratively defined by the participants during the PAR cycle. Additionally, facilitators will encourage them to use creative practices (artistic, maker, and design) to effect change on the chosen issue.

Stakeholders & target audiences

- **Undergraduate design students: 26**
- Professors at the college: 2

- Local community

PAR Cycle Objectives

Key Concepts

Democratic Practice & Citizenship (Understanding)

Challenge: To understand democracy as a part of life and as something that affects them personally, not as a distant system.

PAR Cycle Mission:

- To provide meaningful references through a mirror of experiences.
- To facilitate debate through multimodal participatory dynamics.

Recognizing Conflict & Contradictions in Democratic Systems (Identifying)

Challenge: To identify issues that create conflict and contradictions in their daily lives and that can be relevant to developing a design or a creative intervention.

PAR Cycle Mission:

- To offer research and documentation tools to articulate well-founded and contrasted arguments.
- To promote a non-dichotomous view of the notions of theory and practice in the field of arts and design.

Interrogating Cultural Construction, Social, Political Context and Societal Transformation (Deconstructing)

Challenge: To identify the power relations they are embedded in from a critical and intersectional perspective, identifying their privileges, situations of oppression, and resistances.

PAR Cycle Mission:

- To generate a safe space for openness, sharing experiences and opinions, and promoting critical reflection.
- To use design thinking strategies to map and relate the different visions on the same topic.

Alternative Futures (Activating Change)

Challenge: To understand design as a transformative force of habits, spaces, and forms of relationship in contemporary environments.

PAR Cycle Mission:

- To guide participants in the development of a transformative design proposal or creative intervention that addresses a real eco-social issue.

Please rate the importance of each concept within your PAR Cycle, marking one value per row (1 is lowest, 5 is highest)

	1	2	3	4	5
<i>Democratic practice & citizenship</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	X	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Recognizing conflict & contradictions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	X	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Interrogating constructions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	X
<i>Alternative futures</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	X

Outcomes

Four outcomes are being produced as the participants organised themselves into four teams:

Outcome 1: patched sweatshirt with *sashiko* technique and an “affectively responsible communication manual” for adults.

Outcome 2: interactive collective online photo archive.

Outcome 3: bullying prevention game prototype.

Outcome 4: communal-areas map of a neighbourhood (which one is still to be defined) of Barcelona.

Plan and Activities

The PAR cycle consists of one introductory session at the beginning of the course and six intervention sessions. The introductory session will be brief and integrated into the introductory session of the Sociocultural Anthropology course in the Design Degree at the beginning of the academic year. Each intervention session will last 2 hours and will take place during the course’s scheduled time (utilizing 2 of the 4 hours of each class) once a week.

Activities

Activity 1: Stakeholders needs assessment

A preliminary meeting is held with a teacher to gather the needs and priorities of the group based on the project competencies.

Activity 2: Introduction to the CCLAB project

Basic information about the project and the structure and objectives of the PAR cycle will be provided through a PowerPoint presentation.

Activity 3: Mapping expectations

Interactive activity to map expectations and priorities with participants based on the project competences.

Activity 4: What are you fed up with

This onboarding activity has the goal of identifying issues that matter to participants. Participants are invited to bring images and produce images or texts that related to issues they are fed up with. Together we will create a mural on continuous paper using the images and ideas they provided. The mural will be used to map and debate. Based on that, we will work together towards defining a focus of common interest that will constitute the main topic of the rest of the PAR cycle.

Activity 5: Development of the creative projects

In this process, different dynamics are proposed aimed at promoting the development of the creative change projects that emerge in the group.

Activity 6: Presentation of results

Each team presents their results to the rest of the participants in the lab. The outcomes are discussed.

Activity 7: Evaluation of the process and Focus Group with participants

A focus group is conducted to collectively evaluate the Critical Change Lab process.

Table 3 – Activity Planning

Please indicate (by placing an X or changing the cell to a different colour) when each activity will take place during your PAR Cycle.

	Aug 2024	Sep 2024	Oct 2024	Nov 2024	Dec 2024	Jan 2025
Act 1						

Act 2						
Act 3						
Act 4						
Act 5						
Act 6						
Act 7						

Obstacles and mitigation

Table 4 – Obstacles and mitigation

Description	Probability	Impact	Mitigation Measure
Participants are not engaged and committed to the project.	M	L	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Work collaboratively in all the stages of the process (defining the topic, deciding the artistic/design tools and the concrete output). – Highlighting the importance of producing something of high quality that will be part of the Ars Electronica exhibition.
Participants feel overwhelmed by their academic obligations beyond the PAR cycle.	L	L	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Dedicate class hours to the PAR cycle process and the outcome. – The participation in the PAR cycle and the outcomes produced replace evaluable midcourse works.
Some participants stray from the project as the group is very big.	L	S	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Work in a parallel way in small groups. – To be several facilitators accompanying the process during the PAR cycle.

Tactical Tech PAR Cycle 2 Plan

In PAR Cycle 2 Tactical Tech will coordinate 10 external CCLABs with organisations working with youth across 10 European countries. Each external lab will consist of at least two sessions with a group of 10-15 young people ages 11-18. The overarching topics are youth, democracy, and technology, particularly focusing on how digital influence shapes everyday democracy. Tactical Tech will design and provide the pedagogical materials. The organisations working with youth are responsible for conducting the labs in their own countries and ensuring their localisation to serve the community of young people involved.

PAR Cycle Background and Introduction

Tactical Tech is an international organisation based in Berlin that works to enable individuals and communities to navigate the challenges and the impacts in society arising from technological developments. Our youth initiative, What the Future Wants, aims to empower young people to take control of their digital futures through education, co-creation, and capacity building.

Taking stock of our experience collaborating with local organisations to implement creative interventions, we will partner with 10 organisations working with youth in 10 European countries to implement 10 external Critical Change Labs. Each Critical Change lab will consist of at least two sessions with a group of 10-15 young people, focusing on the topic of digital influence and everyday democracy.

Following our experience with PAR Cycle 1, we plan to maintain the topic of Digital Influence and Democracy. However, given the inputs and experiences collected from young people, educators and partners during PAR Cycle 1, we will redesign the framework for the external labs to accommodate recommendations for improvement. We plan to feature more research-based activities that allow a better understanding of the topics by young people. We plan to refine the maker's activities so young people have more time to define their vision for the future and better plan actions they want to take. Moreover, we are planning to reduce the number of sessions required for a lab to two instead of three, maintaining the number of hours of work. We hope this change will reduce the risk of drop-out in between sessions and allow more continuous work by teens.

Stakeholders & target audiences

*This is an overview of the general stakeholders that are to be involved throughout the project. The stakeholders that are made **bold** are also considered the target audience for the main objectives of the PAR Cycle.*

Similarly to the PAR CYCLE 1, Tactical Tech is responsible for coordinating 10 External Critical Change Lab in partnership with 10 organisations/collectives working with youth from 10 different countries.

- Organisations working with youth in 10 different European countries
- **Young people ages 11-18 years old**
- Schools, youth centres, libraries
- Educators including teachers and youth workers

PAR Cycle Objectives

Key Concepts

Democratic practice & citizenship (understanding)

Challenge: Awareness by young people of the different ways digital technologies are impacting democratic practices and how this intersects with their role in democracy

PAR Cycle Mission: Build knowledge and critical understanding of how digital influence is shaping the attitudes, opinions and behaviours of citizens, particularly young people.

Recognizing conflict & contradictions in democratic systems (identifying)

Challenge: Recognize tensions, conflicts and opportunities that technology poses to democratic systems.

PAR Cycle Mission: Provide a space where young people can have critical conversations on the tensions and contradictions in democratic systems and how technologies is shaping the current democratic ecosystem. We expect that providing the space for exploration and analysis will enable them to explore the intersections with their personal experiences to then formulate their understanding of the different issues.

Interrogating cultural construction, social, political context and societal transformation (deconstructing)

Challenge: Ability to analyse the social and cultural constructions around participation, democracy and youth engagement, incorporate multiple perspectives and envision new possibilities

PAR Cycle Mission: Prioritise and design activities and methods that enable young people to pursue their curiosity on the topics of democracy and influence and foster critical conversations and collaborative work with their peers

Alternative futures (activating change)

Challenge: Ability for people to see themselves as relevant actors that can shape democracy and enable positive change at local, national and global levels

PAR Cycle Mission: Prioritise and design activities that enable young people to advocate for what they care about while practising co-decision and co-management skills with their peers and the other stakeholders involved.

Please rate the importance of each concept within your PAR Cycle, marking one value per row (1 is lowest, 5 is highest)

	1	2	3	4	5
<i>Democratic practice & citizenship</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	x
<i>Recognizing conflict & contradictions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Interrogating constructions</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Alternative futures</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Outcomes

Outcome 1: A refined outline and structure to the CCLABs that better fits the overall goals of the Critical Change Labs model. This will be done by redesigning some of the workshop activities and methods to ensure more clarity for both the organisations and the young people involved in the CCLABs to understand the goals of each session and the lab as a whole.

Outcome 2: Increase young people's ability to identify tensions, conflicts and opportunities in democratic systems and assess their context and democratic practices.

Outcome 3: Increase young people's awareness of their agency and enable them with competencies to transform ideas into action

Plan and Activities

Action plan

Activity 1: Call for new partners

Engage new partners or countries.: Following an assessment of partners involved in PAR Cycle 1 and, taking into consideration partners' interest, we will replace new partners in PAR Cycle 2. This will result in a PAR Cycle 2 with a balance between old and new partners and countries involved in the External Labs. We expect this to enrich the inputs we will receive from the labs.

Activity 2: Redesign External labs workshops

At the end of PAR Cycle 1, we conducted a debrief session with the organisations that implemented the external labs. In this session, we collected inputs on what went well and what could be improved. Similarly, in the project consortium meeting, we were able to exchange knowledge and practices with the other project partners. These inputs will be analysed and support our work redesigning and adapting the model for PAR Cycle 2.

Materials:

Workshop outlines with methods and activities that will be introduced to the external labs partners

Activity 3: Contracting and Onboarding to the new methodology

Following a positive experience for PAR Cycle 1, and once we have confirmed the 10 organisations and countries, we will sign agreements with the organisations conducting the external labs. At this stage, we will host an onboarding session with all of them. The onboarding session has the following goals:

- Onboard partners to CCLAB methodology, timeline and procedures
- Provide a space for the organisations to get to know each other

- Questions & Answers about the cycle
- Present the different ways partners can be involved in the project.

Materials:

- Contract agreements defining Tactical tech and External labs organisations roles and responsibilities
- Partners handbook with essential information partners partnership folder
- Slide presentation of the workshop outlines

Activity 4: External CCLAB implementation of PAR Cycle 2.

Between September 2024 and January 2025, the organisations working with youth will implement the external labs in their respective countries. During this period Tactical Tech will provide pedagogical support to partners and do regular check-ins to ensure all activities are implemented within the timeframe defined by the project for PAR Cycle 2.

Activity 5: Reporting and offboarding

This is a coordination activity. We will secure constant communication with partners to ensure that they submit their reports on time. We will provide open-house sessions for clarifications concerning the reporting system.

Activity 6: Cycle Evaluation

When the external labs are concluded, we will run a debrief session with all the partners. This session will be facilitated by Tactical Tech and entails the following goals:

- Provide a space for external labs to share their experience running the labs,
- Collect feedback concerning what went well, what could have been better and recommendations for the next cycle.

Table 3 – Activity Planning

	Aug 2024	Sep 2024	Oct 2024	Nov 2024	Dec 2024	Jan 2025
Activity 1: Call for new partners	X	X				
Activity 2: Workshop development	X	X				

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Activity 3: Contracting and Onboarding to the new methodology	X	X				
Activity 4: External CCLAB implementation of PAR Cycle 2.		X	X	X	X	
Activity 5: Reporting and offboarding						X
Activity 6: Cycle Evaluation						X

Obstacles and mitigation

Description	Probability	Impact	Mitigation Measure
Risk of partners dropping out during implementation	S	M	Establishing formal contract agreements, early onboarding to ensure partners are fully aware of the tasks and workload involved; Maintain some organisations as a backup plan
Securing the same group of young people throughout the whole each External CCLAB	M	L	Reduce the number of sessions of the PAR Cycle to two sessions for external CCLABs
Scheduling conflict - three sessions over a short period of time	M	M	Onboarding in early September to provide as much time as possible for organisations to organise their labs

Annex 2 – External Partner Lab Document

This document was provided by Tactical Tech to external partners to ensure that labs were consistently organised according to the CCLAB Framework.

Session 1: Onboard, Question & Analyse (90 minutes)

Theme: What is Influence?

Participants explore how influence operates online, focusing on social media, algorithms, and technology's role in shaping opinions.

Activities:

Define and discuss "influence"

Analyse real-world examples of digital influence

Examine how algorithms affect behaviour and democracy

Group discussion on ethical concern

Methods: co-design, brainstorming, case study research analysis; group discussions, plenary debate, self-assessment rating

Outcome: Participants gain a foundational understanding of influence and digital media.

Session 2: Analyse, Envision & Examine (100-120 minutes)

Theme: What Matters to Us?

Participants identify social issues they care about and define problem statements for advocacy.

Activities:

Brainstorming participation in democracy

Identifying and clustering key issues

Refining problem statements with peer feedback

Methods: brainstorming, spectrograms; co-design; group and plenary discussions

Outcome: Participants develop clear topics for advocacy and prepare for creative campaign work.

Session 3: Envision, Act & Reflect (90-100 minutes)

Theme: Influencing for Change

Participants create advocacy materials (e.g., posters, videos, campaigns) based on their chosen issues.

Activities:

Design and present advocacy materials.

Receive feedback from peers and external stakeholders.

Reflect on personal growth and next steps

Methods: If this ...then; co-creation, advocacy gallery, final self-assessment rating

Outcome: Participants produce tangible advocacy projects and enhance their critical thinking and engagement skills.